

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

D5.3 Results of the dissemination and Exploitation including communication activities

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BioRural Consortium

BioRural Consortium			
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2	DELPHY BV	DELPHY	NL
3	ASSOCIATION DU POLE DE COMPETIVITE VALORIAL	VALORIAL	FR
4	NATUREPLAST SAS	NATUREPLAST SAS	FR
5	IZES GGMBH	IZES	DE
6	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	AU	DK
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11	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	UC	PT
12	CENTRO DA BIOMASSA PARA A ENERGIA	CBE	PT
13	AIEL ASSOCIAZIONE ITALIANA ENERGIE AGROFORESTALI	AIEL	IT
14	REFRAME FOOD ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	RFF	EL
15	INCOMMON NON-PROFIT CIVIL LAW COMPANY	ICO	EL
16	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	UL	SI
17	ALGEN, CENTER ZA ALGNE TEHNOLOGIJE, DOO	ALGEN	SI
18	ASOCIATIA GREEN ENERGY	GEA	RO
19	ZDRUZENIE PLATFORMA ZA ZELEN RAZVOJ SKOPJE	GGP	MK

Executive Summary

BioRural seeks to establish a pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network to promote the currently available small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas and to increase the share of Bioeconomy, giving increased value in such remote areas. BioRural will contribute to bridge the gap between the novel high-end bio-based solutions currently available and the everyday rural life in Europe by:

- evaluating and assessing the current state of the European rural bioeconomy,
- identifying grassroots needs and ideas,
- fostering effective knowledge and information exchange,
- looking into potential opportunities for regional development through the expansion of bio-based solutions integration in rural Europe.

This way, BioRural will develop a transition framework towards a sustainable, regenerative, inclusive, and just circular Bioeconomy across all Europe at local and regional scale and support innovators to scale up inclusive and small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas. To do so, the project will:

- (i) Assess and evaluate the **current performance of the European rural Bioeconomy** in the EU and identify factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas;
- (ii) Create four regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms (RBPs) that will form a **European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN)**;
- (iii) Assess and promote **success stories** of bio-based solutions in rural areas;
- (iv) Develop and continuously optimise an online open stakeholders' tool, named **BioRural Toolkit**;
- (v) Facilitate knowledge exchange and **capacity building** for the European rural Bioeconomy through a series of workshops at a local, regional, and European level;
- (vi) Create **rural development blueprints** for regional and business scale-up of resilient and circular bio-based solutions in rural areas and
- (vii) Disseminate and communicate all activities for maximum visibility and rural Bioeconomy expansion.

The Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities provides the guidelines for effectively sharing information within the consortium and an extensive strategy for transferring project knowledge and results to the intended stakeholders.

This document is the final update of the D5.1 Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (DEC plan), providing the documentation of the attained results of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities by the project partners until M36.

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
AKIS	Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems
DEC	Dissemination Exploitation and Communication
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
EC	European Commission
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and Sustainability
ERBN	European Rural Bioeconomy Network
EU	European Union
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RBPs	Regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
SOSTAC	Situation, Objectives, Strategy, Tactics, Action, Control

1 Introduction

1.1 Project Summary

1.1.1 Challenge

The EU economy is heavily reliant on linear production systems and non-renewable resources and materials. Since the extraction of fossil fuels continues to release more carbon into the atmosphere, it exacerbates already major environmental and climatic issues and the well-known greenhouse effect. Further, climate change has an impact on the entire economy in addition to having an immediate consequence on the environment and humans.

The climate change impact over food security, human health, migratory flows, biodiversity loss and rising sea levels, will lead to a decline in productivity and wealth creation.

In this context, the bioeconomy has a key role to play.

Strengthening Europe’s bioeconomy can significantly accelerate progress towards achieving key EU policy objectives, such as transitioning to a circular economy, becoming climate neutral by 2050, and strengthening the EU industrial base.

BioRural aims to create a pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network under which related stakeholders cooperate to promote the currently available small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas to increase the share of Bioeconomy, giving increased value in such remote areas. This framework will contribute to bridging the gap between the available novel high-end bio-based solutions and the everyday European rural life by assessing the existing situation of European rural Bioeconomy, capturing grassroots-level needs and ideas, promoting effective exchange of knowledge and information, and investigating the possible opportunities for regional development through the expansion of bio-based solutions integration in rural Europe.

1.1.2 BioRural is built on a three-pillar intervention scheme:

Table 1: BioRural three-pillar intervention scheme

Pillar 1 - Knowledge	Pillar 2 - Network	Pillar 3 – Business Models
<p>1 overview of the EU Bioeconomy current status</p> <p>440 interviews with end users/experts</p> <p>5 knowledge exchange workshops</p>	<p>1 European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN)</p> <p>4 Regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms - RBPs</p> <p>8 Rural Bioeconomy Success Stories</p> <p>42 capacity building workshops</p> <p>4 Regional workshops</p> <p>1 European Bioeconomy Challenge</p>	<p>5 Business model blueprints (for each of the main Bioeconomy themes)</p> <p>1 Post project sustainability plan</p>

BioRural's key activities

BioRural's workplan is comprised of the following key activities:

- Assessment and evaluation of the current performance of the European rural Bioeconomy in the EU and identification of the factors affecting innovation, adoption, and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas;
- Creation of four regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms (RBPs) that form a European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN);
- Assessment and promotion of success stories of bio-based solutions in rural areas;
- Development and continuous optimization of an online open stakeholders' tool, named BioRural Toolkit;
- Facilitation of knowledge exchange and capacity building for the European rural Bioeconomy through a series of workshops in local, regional, and European level;
- Creation of rural development blueprints for regional and business scale-up of resilient and circular bio-based solutions in rural areas and
- Dissemination and communication of all activities for maximum visibility and rural Bioeconomy expansion.

Figure 1: BioRural's conceptual approach

1.2 BioRural Consortium

BioRural practiced a “Multi Actor Approach”, as it included 19 partners from 14 European countries representing research entities, extension services, associations, SMEs, and innovation brokers. The consortium is very well framed by 8 Research entities on Bioeconomy, 4 of which are core partners of BIOEASTsUP project, 4 partners that are focused on innovation brokerage, social integration of novel solutions and business development, 2 SMEs representing Bio-based industry together with the 6 other success stories participating as subcontractors and 5 professional associations and extension touching end-users in the core.

Research: P1-CERTH (GR), BioRural coordinator, has broad expertise on bio-based solutions and has been involved in key H2020 projects in the field. P5-IZES (DE) is specialised in biogas systems and waste management to produce bio-fertiliser and compost. P6-AU (DK) has hoary experience on bio-based solutions, designing new technologies and preparing training material. P7-IUNG is a leading research entity in bioenergy, LCA and training and will lead WP4 based on its experience on developing ICT Platforms. P8- VDU (LT) is WP1 leader as it has extensive experience in empirical social research among various rural actors, being familiar with participatory approaches and interdisciplinary research. P9-LLU (LV) specialises on life sciences and Bioeconomy aspects and produces training material on these subjects. P11-UC (PT) works heavily on forest biomass handling, logistics and use for multiple purposes, as well as specialises on LCA of Biosystems. P16-UL (SI) leads WP3 as a University specialised in Bioeconomy issues especially related to forest management and inland aquatic production systems.

Association/Extension: P2-DELPHY (NL), P10-AVE (ES), P12-CBE (PT), P13-AIEL (IT) and P19-GEA (RO) are significant regional professional associations and extension services specialised in all aspects of Bioeconomy and will support BioRural with their extensive network of end-users in organising successful workshops and disseminating the project. They will also feed the RBP workshops and the European Challenge event with “ambassador” actors. P10-AVE will act as the leader of WP2 to create the ERBN.

Industry: P4-NP (FR) is a bioplastics SME providing knowledge on biomaterials and biotechnological aspects. P17-ALGEN (SI) is an SME specialised in wastewater treatment and microalgae production used for multiple purposes. Both companies will act as success stories and also as mentors to ideas from the workshops’ activity. Innovation and Social Sciences: P3-VAL (FR) is an innovation scheme running the largest network devoted in agri-food innovation, but also has expanded in other Bioeconomy sectors. 14 RFF (GR) is an SME that works as innovation broker in Bioeconomy and has high expertise in dissemination/communication activities, but also in business models and open calls organisations in EU projects. P15-ICO (GR) works heavily on social innovation to assist on integrating environmentally friendly bio-based solutions in modern society. Finally, P18-GGP (NMK) is an active innovation broker with participation in EU projects and significant national activity.

A main advantage of the BioRural consortium is that the core team has previously or is collaborating in EU projects, being already familiar with project management, communication, and decision-making workflows to enable smooth and timely implementation of BioRural. The consortium has received 6 letters of acceptance to act as Advisors and 32 letters of support by Bioeconomy stakeholders that recognize the potential of BioRural.

1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The document is the final update on the D5.1 Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities, providing information with regards to the monitoring of the plan’s implementation by the project partners.

Certain highlights and updates have been incorporated into the document to present the progress made by partners with the closure of the project in month 36.

This document is comprised of the following chapters & Annexes:

Chapter 1 provides a summary of the project and the document’s scope, structure, and objectives.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the project’s DEC methodology and approach, the identified target groups,

and relevant key messages.

Chapter 3 delves into the specific dissemination and communication activities, tools and channels including the visual identity, communication material and the channel mix with updated information until month 36.

Chapter 4 specifies the reporting and monitoring procedures and tools, focusing on KPIs and the specific activities that have been carried out until month 36.

Chapter 5 presents the identified Key Exploitable Results, the potential pathways to bring BioRural results to all targeted user communities as well as the identified IPRs and IPR strategy followed by the project partners.

Chapter 6 presents the conclusions of the deliverable.

Annex A provides the project logo variations.

Annex B presents BioRural's covers that are used on social media.

Annex C provides images of the dissemination and communication material that has already been designed including the brochure, the banner, and the press release template.

Annex D provides the deliverable template.

Annex E provides the event planning template used for gathering information from partners regarding the events that had been planned on attended.

Annex F provides the synergy mapping template that partners complete with information on existing projects, networks, alliances etc., that they are currently part of and could be relevant to BioRural.

Annex G provides the publication planning template that partners complete with information on peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, and any other planned publications.

Annex H provides the project's brand book.

Annex I provides the template for the Identification of new KERs & IPR process.

2 DEC methodology and approach

2.1 BioRural DEC Time plan [including after the end of the project]

A division of the DEC plan into four phases (Figure 2) is crucial, ensuring both its successful implementation and the achievement of the objectives. The four phases of the DEC plan (Phase 1: Vision, Phase 2: Raise cognition, Phase 3: Multiplier effect, Phase 4: Sustainability) lasted from the beginning of the project until after its end, enhancing post-project sustainability.

Figure 2: BioRural's DEC phases

Key Highlights up to M36

By the time of this deliverable's submission, all project phases up to M36 have been successfully completed. The project's visual identity and communication materials, including the brochure and banner, were fully developed and translated for all participating countries. Partners carried out mapping and outreach to the identified target groups and established connections with other EU-funded projects to jointly promote bioeconomy (D2.1: European Regional Bioeconomy Network creation and stakeholder mapping). BioRural partners actively engaged targeted stakeholders through participation in the project's activities, particularly the online knowledge exchange workshops (T3.1), the multi-actor national workshops (T3.2), the regional workshops and the European Bioeconomy Challenge (T3.3) fostering interactive innovation at European level.

Throughout these phases, BioRural initially showcased eight small-scale bio-based solutions and success stories from all European countries represented in the consortium (T2.3: Innovation processes of selected success stories). More than 30 additional success stories were identified and made accessible through the BioRural Toolkit (T2.4: Identification of success stories in each Rural Bioeconomy Platform), demonstrating the project's broad impact and contribution to rural bioeconomy development. The BioRural toolkit and its features have been promoted through several events and dissemination activities highlighting the importance of its content to relevant stakeholders. A significant number of liaisons with other EU projects and initiatives have been achieved throughout the duration of the project, which has maximized BioRural's impact on bioeconomy by fostering collaboration, knowledge exchange, and integrated efforts, ultimately enhancing the project's effects and delivering more comprehensive and sustainable results. The joint effort of the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance, involving BioRural and other related projects, along with the co-organisation of the European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference (EuRCBC), underscored the significance of this collaborative approach and enhanced the overall impact across Europe's rural regions.

2.2 DEC methodology

A strong DEC plan is fundamental for creating lasting impact and provides a concrete roadmap for partners to boost the growth of the BioRural ecosystem, raise awareness of project activities and maximise impact among key stakeholders and target groups at the broader social, policy, and industry level. The BioRural DEC plan is inspired by the **SOSTAC** model which includes the following key elements: Situation analysis, Objectives, Strategy, Tactics, Actions and Control.

Figure 3: BioRural DEC methodology

Situation analysis: A state-of-play analysis in which the current challenges to be addressed by the project, the consortium's expertise, the scientific, societal, and economic impacts during and after the project and the potential IPR of the results are identified and explained.

Objectives: The DEC plan elaborates upon clear and measurable objectives that will be achieved through the implementation of communication, dissemination, and exploitation measures.

Strategy: Identification of target groups and key messages for effective communication.

Tactics: Identification of the tactics that allow the BioRural consortium to implement its strategy.

Actions: The DEC plan builds upon the activities, tools and channels defined in the GA and includes the contribution expected from the partners over the project duration. A living list of planned events has been created. Open Science practices are being factored into all aspects of the DEC implementation.

Control: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) with specific targets determined during the GA, are used to monitor the progress of the DEC implementation. Templates for partner reporting are also used and are presented in Chapter 4.

2.3 Multi-actor approach

BioRural uses a multi-actor approach, considering all relevant forms of experience and knowledge from a diverse set of partners and stakeholders to achieve the project aims and ensure broad communication from the start. Figure 4 presents the six different stakeholders' groups that are involved in BioRural.

Figure 4: BioRural's stakeholder's groups

2.3.1.1 Interactive innovation process

The 'multi-actor' approach is key for interactive innovation. The way diverse actors work well together (the 'multi-actor approach') is crucial for interactive innovation to deliver unique project results and benefits.

Multi-actor innovation brings together a diverse range of public and private innovation actors as shown in figure 4, with complementary types and sources of knowledge to appraise, gather, cocreate and disseminate practical solutions to real needs.

The multi-actor approach of BioRural requires a participatory 'bottom-up approach', facilitating those at the core of the project to influence project outcomes. Taking a 'bottom-up' approach to development, allows members to be involved in the entire development process, from decision-making to evaluation. Interactive innovation is a social process rather than a 'top-down' scientific approach. Multi actor interactive innovation brings all the competent actors with various knowledge together, with the aim to plan and codesign practical and implementable solutions to real-life problems.

The process of interactive innovation followed by BioRural involves a series of specific scenarios and tools (based upon the LIAISON project Practitioner Handbook)¹, shown in Figure 5. These range from engaging and incentivising actors/stakeholders to become involved, to co-creation, to applying new knowledge on the ground.

¹ <https://liaison2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/LIAISON-Assessment-Tools.pdf>

Figure 5: Key scenarios in multi-actor approach

For each of the above-mentioned 6 key scenarios, relevant tools have been identified while some of them have been tested during the proposal and implementation stage:

Scenario 1: ENGAGING

Tool: STAKEHOLDERS PRIORITISATION

The tool is used for the prioritisation of the identified stakeholders' groups assessing the types of actors involved in the multi-actor approach. The prioritisation has already been made by the project partners during the proposal and team-building phase and it was based on the specific needs that BioRural aims to address. An assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of each of the stakeholders' groups was also made. The specific order of this prioritisation process is presented in Figure 6.

Prioritisation of Stakeholders

Figure 6: Prioritisation of Stakeholders

Other tools that were considered for engaging stakeholders throughout the project implementation refer to understanding stakeholders and registering their needs with service design methods such as Personas².

² <https://servicedesigntools.org/tools/personas>

Scenario 2:**Tool: JOURNEY MAPPING**

The tool is used for understanding the experiences and knowledge of the stakeholders within the project, identifying impacts of the project and their subjective evaluations of the project. The tool intends to assess the extent to which the stakeholder's experiences match with what the project envisaged and intended, pinpointing particular events and experiences.

Scenario 3: CREATING**Tool: GROUND RULES: IDENTIFICATION OF OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF AGREEMENT-BASED COOPERATION**

The tool is used for assessing cultural norms, held by different actors involved in multi-actor work, that should be respected in the interactive innovation process to enhance how the potential of a diverse group is realised. The tool has been used during the project development stage.

Scenario 4: ADDRESSING**Tool: TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem-Solving)**

The tool is used for assessing how actors are examining challenges and opportunities in the interactive innovation process, facilitating them to look at challenges and opportunities from new perspectives as well as engage in new forms of external knowledge to fuel interactive innovation.

Scenario 5: APPLYING**Tool: WHAT, WHO, WHY, WHERE, WHEN & HOW**

The tool is used for planning multi-actor tasks in advance, identifying:

- Which actors & stakeholders will be involved – Who?
- The tasks they will be involved in – What?
- Why would they want to be involved in such tasks – Why?
- The logistics and approach of the tasks – Where? When? and How?

The tool has been used during the project development stage allowing partners to avoid fatigue, duplication and to maximise opportunities for synergies between tasks.

Scenario 6: EVALUATING**Tool: 'CAUSES AND EFFECTS': BUILDING HYPOTHESES: LINKING ACTIONS TO RESULTS**

The tool is used for facilitating partners to generate hypotheses regarding the causes and effects of actions leading to actions, then to results and subsequently to objectives and breaking it down, fact-checking and proofing. It also allows participants to continuously reflect and evaluate the decision-making process regarding the choice of project actions, revising and adapting their plans.

Multi-actor approach & DEC actions

The project's multi-actor approach is extended to the creation and implementation of the DEC plan, which means:

- Translating materials into partner's languages;
- Focusing on communicating information that matters to the end user;

- Using language, vocabulary and communication channels that are appealing and audience appropriate;
- Seeking synergies and collaboration opportunities with other projects, initiatives, networks, with and between academia, industry, society, and government;
- Capitalising on partners existing connections, networks, and events program;
- Including knowledge exchange activities and discussion in event programs.

Material including the project brochure and banner has been translated into the languages of the partner countries and the responsibility has been assigned to specific partners (See Table 2).

Table 2: Translation task among partners

Partner		Language	
	NL		
	FR		
	DE		
	DK		
	PL		
	LT		
	LV		
	ES		
	PT		
	IT		
	GR		
	SI		
	RO		
	MK		

2.3.1.2 Consideration of the Gender Dimension in Project Activities

Throughout the implementation of the project, gender equality and inclusiveness were systematically integrated across communication, dissemination, and engagement actions. The project’s approach went beyond compliance, aiming to actively promote balanced representation, visibility, and participation of all genders in BioRural's activities.

Under **T5.1 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan**, all communication materials were developed using gender-sensitive language. Visuals and storytelling deliberately avoided reinforcing conventional male and female stereotypes, instead portraying individuals in realistic and diverse roles within agriculture and innovation. The emphasis was placed on competence, collaboration, and community—values that transcend gender identity. This approach ensured that the project’s visual and narrative outputs aligned with principles of equality and inclusiveness.

In addition, drawing upon both the BioRural Practice Abstracts, a holistic consideration of the gender dimension, while often implicit rather than explicitly disaggregated, is woven into the project's foundational

commitment to inclusivity, social equity, and broad stakeholder empowerment within rural bioeconomy solutions. This is achieved through the promotion of inclusive success stories and innovative solutions that aim to benefit all members of rural communities, creating new opportunities, improving livelihoods, and enhancing quality of life without excluding any demographic. The abstracts frequently highlight initiatives empowering diverse rural actors, small-scale producers, and family-owned businesses – often key platforms for women's participation in agriculture and local economies – by providing accessible knowledge, practical tools, and fostering local employment and social cohesion, particularly in remote areas. Moreover, by emphasizing social impact alongside economic and environmental gains in methodologies like the Triple Layered Business Model Canvas, the project ensures that the benefits of solutions, whether in improved resource management, community-led energy systems, or new bio-based value chains, are intended to be shared equitably across the population. This pervasive focus ensures that BioRural's innovations contribute to a bioeconomy that is responsive to the diverse needs and opportunities of all individuals in European rural areas.

Within **T5.2 – Stakeholder Engagement and Outreach**, gender inclusiveness was further embedded in the project's engagement strategy. Outreach activities proactively involved rural women's associations and, whenever possible, organisations advocating for broader gender inclusion in agriculture and rural development. This inclusive engagement helped diversify stakeholder participation, while maintaining a voluntary and interest-driven approach rather than imposing prescriptive requirements.

In addition to these structural measures, the project also conducted annual campaigns celebrating the International Day of Women and Girls in Science. These campaigns invited female scientists from the BioRural consortium to share their perspectives, experiences, and reflections on gender and scientific careers, thus giving visibility to their contributions and inspiring future generations of women in STEM. Finally, in the project's podcast series (10 episodes), particular attention was given to achieving gender balance among speakers. Efforts were made to ensure equitable representation of male and female participants, fostering a dialogue that reflects the diversity of expertise and experiences across the consortium and the broader rural innovation community. Through these combined actions, the project not only upheld gender equality principles but also contributed to fostering a more inclusive and representative narrative around bio-based innovation and rural development.

2.4 Target groups

Defining the project's target audience was a critical step for focusing objectives and pursuing meaningful impact. A clear understanding of the target audiences (e.g., who they are, where they are, what are their needs and their typical characteristics) was an essential part of an effective DEC plan. This was needed to ensure that communication and dissemination channels, as well as the undertaken activities are maximising and extending the reach of the project results. This chapter presents the seven target groups that have been identified explaining the benefits they gain through their engagement to the project (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Target groups and respective benefits

2.5 DEC Objectives & KPIs

The DEC plan objectives are S.M.A.R.T (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time bound) and provide a verifiable trajectory towards clear milestones and an estimated timeline to attain the goals and ensure impact maximisation.

Dissemination Objectives

The dissemination activities were expected to diffuse the knowledge generated in the context of the project, aiming to ensure both a mid- and long-term impact. More specifically the dissemination activities have been carefully planned to ensure that the project's advancements are widely spread to the intended targeted audiences with appropriate tools and that the key stakeholders have been engaged early and actively participated during each of the project's phases. BioRural applied an intensive dissemination strategy that led to all the relevant actions from the very early stages of the project. The intended strategy was aligned with the dissemination objectives below:

- Bring together a critical mass of stakeholders and maximise outreach opportunities for BioRural with targeted messaging and customised content;
- Diffuse scientific and technological knowledge generated in the project and put it to productive use via capacity building under BioRural activities;
- Nurture collaborative relationships with projects, initiatives, pan-European networks of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and AKIS actors to avoid duplication of efforts, and capitalise on the results;
- Receive and utilise feedback from key stakeholder segments and potential users to make sure project developments are going in the right direction;
- Align and integrate dissemination, communication, community building activities with exploitation efforts to ensure sustainability of our reusable assets;
- Encourage new initiatives and support those already being carried out.

Exploitation Objectives

The exploitation refers to the action of making use of and benefiting from project results. Hence, BioRural's exploitation activities were recognized as the key enabler for success of the

project. All the consortium partners have been committed to the exploitation of the project's results and their diverse and complementary research and business contexts provide all potential exploitation modalities and routes to bring BioRural results to all targeted stakeholders (including bio-based raw material producers, bio-based industries, rural and urban citizens, local and regional government, local rural schools and universities, NGOs, environmental and citizens' groups and unions). A combination of activities spanned throughout the project duration and varied in intensity, based on the amount of information that was available and the results that were produced during the project's lifetime. The objectives of the project's exploitation measures include:

- Secure positive engagement from relevant stakeholders since it is important to attain both their contributions to the process as well as their willingness to use the results.
 - Enhance and facilitate the exploitation of the project's results both by the consortium partners and the stakeholders.

BioRural aimed to capture the added value of project results, which were valorised by:

- Creating feasible paths to deliver project results to stakeholders interested in their use/reuse
- Elaborating upon and defining new Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to expedite development and commercialization when possible

Communication Objectives

All actions that contribute to the diffusion of the project's results beyond the consortium and the direct stakeholders are considered as communication activities. In essence, communication activities are focused on maximising the visibility of the project, through widely attracting a wide range of stakeholders who are invited to embrace the project's results and benefit from the project's advancements. To achieve this, attention was paid to adapt the communication means, the measures, and the content both to the need and knowledge levels of the target groups as well as to the status, progress and needs of the BioRural project. To ensure that the communication measures would effectively meet the project's expectations, communication objectives were set:

- Raise awareness, facilitate information exchange and capacity building on data-driven sustainability- oriented technology innovations;
- Encourage positive reception and acceptance by farmers, their advisors, policy makers;
- Reflect gender equality and inclusivity in the approach, tools, and channels.

2.6 Key messages

Key messages have been used to articulate in a simple straightforward manner the unique benefit of engaging with BioRural. Specific key messages have been identified depending on the communication channel and tool selected.

Arising from the concepts previously mentioned, a set of "backbone" messages per target group have been defined, as the basis for a deeper approach, while aiming to highlight the advantages provided by BioRural. The following table presents the key messages per target group.

Table 3: Target audience, objectives & key messages

Target audience (WHO)	Communication objectives (WHY)	Communication Key messages (WHAT)
Bio-based raw material producers & industries	Long term competitiveness, linkages with bio-based industries, support for scaling. Improved access to renewable raw materials, direct support for scaling, rural job security and satisfaction.	“BioRural can add value to your business by connecting you with bioeconomy innovators and stakeholders. Discover trends and needs of the industry, enter new markets and expand network with end users, researchers and policy makers.”
Rural /urban citizens	Local ownership and economic opportunities, local redevelopment, increased environmental awareness, better quality of life, access to sustainable products	“Find out how bioeconomy and biobased practices and innovations can benefit your daily personal and professional life by getting to know BioRural project.”
Government, policy makers etc.	Knowledge of Bioeconomy and, realisation of its multiple benefits, receive policy recommendations, support local redevelopment and resilience	“Align with BioRural and get support in the design of policies towards innovation adoption and the diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural area in order to strengthen them, and to receive benefit nation- wide.”
Local rural schools, universities etc.	Growing environmental awareness, focus on inter- and transdisciplinary research, hands-on knowledge on Bioeconomy applications	“Contribute to the identification of latest technologies in bio-based solutions and take advantage of interdisciplinary opportunities and collaborations with other academia stakeholders across Europe.”
NGOs, environmental groups, citizen groups, think tanks	Platform for sharing ideas, knowledge and capacity, access to practical and scientific Bioeconomy knowledge	“Join BioRural networks and gain knowledge and tools for the adoption of circular bio-based proven solutions supporting the development of the wider circular bioeconomy.”
Private sector, Bioeconomy unions/projects	Sustainable business activities, access to sustainable raw materials, multi-actor partnerships, and improved impacts	“Be at the forefront of Bioeconomy developments and take advantage of opportunities and collaborations between similar goal-oriented projects.”

Specific communication tools and channels have been elaborated to reach the identified target groups:

Communication tools and channels	Bio-based raw material producers	Bio-based industries	Rural /urban citizens	Government, policy makers etc.	Local rural schools, universities etc.	NGOs, group, citizen groups, think tanks	Private sector, Bioeco-nomy unions/projects
Website & social media	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
E-newsletters	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Press outreach	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Interviews and outreach videos	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Networking, synergies & liaison activities				✓	✓	✓	✓
Scientific, industry and policy publications	✓	✓		✓	✓		

Figure 8: Communication tools and channels for target audience Channels, tools, and activities

3 Channels, tools and activities

This chapter outlines the communication tools and channels that have been used to connect with the BioRural target groups throughout BioRural duration and until month 36.

3.1 Visual identity

To target the broadest possible audience, BioRural has created a strong, memorable brand that visually reflects the unique identity and objectives of the project. BioRural have exploited multiple digital platforms to share updates and results and to facilitate ongoing dialogue with stakeholders. Posts, and other inputs have been curated to the target audiences at a frequency that demonstrates consistency and accessibility.

3.1.1 Visual identity and moto

The visual identity is the visible representation of the project. A strong visual identity combines images, colours, and shapes to create a powerful, memorable message to the viewer. BioRural 's visual identity was created considering the following:

- ✓ **Simplicity:** The selected visual identity must be able to tell the story in a simple manner.
- ✓ **Relevance:** An appropriate aesthetic that can be easily correlated with the project objectives.
- ✓ **Uniqueness:** The elements selected must lead to the design of a recognisable and unique visual identity.
- ✓ **Versatility:** A logo that can be easily used in different communication channels (digital and printed).

The logo has been used in all internal and external communication and dissemination activities (project website, presentations, brochures, press releases etc.) to help enhance brand continuity and raise awareness. Eight logo variations have been selected for different uses (Annex A). The most frequently used logo for the communication and dissemination material is shown in the figure below:

Figure 9: BioRural logo

3.1.2 The use of the EU emblem

BioRural's deliverables are following the requirements set out by the European Commission and will include the EU flag and the source of funding as follows.

Figure 10: EU Emblem

The ready-to-use EU emblem including the funding statement can be downloaded in all EU languages.

3.1.3 Disclaimer for publications

In addition to the EU Emblem, all dissemination and communication material must include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”⁴⁴

3.1.4 Colour palette

The colour palette was selected to represent the project’s values. The colours are optimised for use on both screen (RGB) and print (CMYK) and the contrast is high enough for black and white printing. The project's brand book is provided in Annex H.

Figure 11: BioRural colour palette

3.1.5 Templates

BioRural was presented at numerous events, conferences, meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results.

A **presentation template (ppt)** has been designed in line with BioRural’s graphic identity to maintain consistency, professionalism and promote its recognition.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/logos_downloadcenter/

⁴ Based on the Annotated Model Grant Agreement: [V0.2 DRAFT– 30.11.2021](#). For any changes, the DEC plan will be updated accordingly.

Figure 12: BioRural presentation template

The BioRural deliverable template (doc) is also consistent with communication and dissemination material graphic identity and was used by the consortium partners for the development of all project deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project’s logo in a prominent position, its acronym, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number, and title) as well as the author’s details.

Figure 13: BioRural deliverable template

3.2 BioRural channel mix

3.2.1 Website

The project's website has been the primary communication and dissemination platform to enable target groups and BioRural's stakeholders' access to the project development and results, and to see and assess the added-value and the impact of bio-based solutions in rural areas. **The site has been regularly updated with contributions from all partners throughout the project implementation period.** It hosted all the public dissemination deliverables, promoting relevant content (news, editorials, videos, events, etc.) for key stakeholder groups, thus engaging them in the content and objectives of the project.

Mobile-Friendly Design: Finally, the website was mobile-friendly, which enhanced accessibility and maximized the project's impact.

Throughout the implementation period, BioRural's website had a twofold role as it served as the principal reference point for the project, explaining the project's aims, providing new updates, documents for download and enabling access to the project's social media accounts, and it also acted as a resource centre for research on topics related to biobased solutions and innovations mainly for rural areas, providing important updates.

Delivered in M3, the BioRural website is hosted at www.biorural.eu and contains the following sections and features.

Home/Landing page

The section includes the project logo, image, project graphics, social media icons (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, SlideShare, YouTube), a button for sign-up in the BioRural's newsletter and navigation menu providing easy access to information on the project. It also includes a button leading to the BioRural Toolkit and Network.

Figure 14: BioRural website home page

The Project

The section includes the following elements:

- **About BioRural:** Presenting information about the project aim and specific objectives.
- **Bioeconomy State-of-play:** Presenting some key information about Bioeconomy in the EU and the contribution of the project to address the challenges faced.
- **BioRural Toolkit & Network:** Presenting the BioRural toolkit which is an online repository of bio-

based solutions that enables the interaction between rural actors and provides the ground for wider application of bio-based solutions. Presentation of the Bioeconomy Network (ERBN) and the 4 regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms (RBPs) is also included. The section provides direct access to users in order to access the Toolkit and register to the Network.

- **Partners:** Presenting the project consortium and providing active links to their respective websites.
- **Deliverables:** Providing links to public project deliverables deposited on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/biorural/>.
- **Rural Bioeconomy Alliance:** Presenting a cluster of EU-funded projects aimed at accelerating and supporting the development of circular rural Bioeconomy. BioRural has established this network along with 10 other projects.

Figure 15: BioRural website - "The Project" tab

Important Addition during RP2: As part of the dissemination and engagement activities, a new section was introduced to the BioRural website in May 2024: the **Bioeconomy Challenge and Workshops**. This section provided comprehensive guidance to potential applicants interested in participating in the online call for Bioeconomy Innovators, organized per region of interest (Southeast, Northeast, Southwest, Northwest).

The BioRural Online Call

Ensure your bio-based solution meets the eligibility criteria and submit your application for the Region you apply for.

Figure 16: BioRural website - "The BioRural Online Call"

The content outlined the timeline of the application process, key deadlines, and procedural steps necessary to submit a successful proposal. Additionally, the section featured practical guidelines for participation, including instructions on how to access the online registration form, documentation requirements, evaluation criteria, and contact information for further support per region.

Applications to this Circular Bioeconomy Challenge can be submitted from applicants located in Southwestern countries: Spain, Italy, Portugal, Malta, Monaco and Andorra. **The South-West Online Call is open from 31st May until 20th August 2024 (23:59h – CET).**

But, what are “bioeconomy innovations”?

You can submit any innovative idea that may resolve the management of an organic by-product applying circularity. You may know in your region or country about some by-products in rural areas that are accumulated, which management is linear and not circular, which involve high costs or result in a final use of low added value.

Where to start from?

The first you need is an idea. Do you already have one? Then we encourage you to form a group with colleagues at work, students, usual collaborators, and put heads together. Transforming your idea into an application to the SW Call will require you to browse for information, read news, or consult some experts. You need to state that your idea is original, and has not been put into practice yet, but also that it is feasible, by using existing or promising technologies, applicable in rural-areas. This is well explained in the BioRural Open Call Applicants guide.

Applying for the South-West Online Call

The timing for the SW Online Call is organised in three phases:

Phase 1: Until 20th August 2024

- Prepare your application.
- Form a group of researchers, students, company technicians and submit your application.

Phase 2: Until end of August 2024

- The evaluation committee will review the applications, and organise a meeting with each applicant. There you will be able to explain by voice your ideas!
- Among the applicants, 10-15 will be selected and have access to the Southwest regional final.

BioRural Online Call opens its doors to Northeastern Europe! Applications to this Circular Bioeconomy Challenge can be submitted from applicants located in Northeastern countries: Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Finland, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Slovakia and Ukraine. **The North-East Online Call is open until 18th August 2024 (23:59h – CET).**

Where to start from?

The first you need is an idea. Do you already have one? Then we encourage you to form a group with colleagues at work, students, usual collaborators, and put heads together. Transforming your idea into an application to the NE Call will require you to browse for information, read news, or consult some experts. You need to state that your idea is original, and has not been put into practice yet, but also that it is feasible, by using existing or promising technologies, applicable in rural-areas. This is well explained in the BioRural Open Call Applicants guide.

Applying for the North-East Online Call

The timing for the NE Online Call is organised in three phases:

Phase 1: Until August 18th 2024

- Prepare your application.
- Form a group of researchers, students, company technicians and submit your application.

Phase 2: Until September 6th 2024

- The evaluation committee will review the applications, and organise a meeting with each applicant. There you will be able to explain by voice your ideas!
- Among the applicants, 10-15 will be selected and have access to the North-East regional final.

Figure 17: BioRural Online Call dedicated blog posts

This addition was designed to facilitate smooth and informed participation in the **online call**, ensuring transparency and providing potential applicants with the necessary resources and clarity to encourage broad regional engagement in the bioeconomy innovation landscape.

Success stories

The section includes a presentation of the 8 success stories that have been identified and mentioned in the GA.

Figure 18: BioRural website “Success stories” tab

Important Addition during RP2: The additional success stories that have been identified throughout the course of the project have been incorporated into the dedicated **"Success Stories"** tab within the News section. To ensure a focused and organized presentation the success stories have been categorized by bioeconomy theme as follows:

- BioRural Success Stories: #1 Powering Rural Europe with **Bioenergy**: Showcasing 7 success stories.

- BioRural Success Stories: #2 Strengthening Rural Europe through **Food & Agriculture Innovations**: Showcasing 15 success stories.
- BioRural Success Stories: #3 Sustaining Rural Europe through **Aquatic & Water System Solutions**: Showcasing 6 success stories.
- BioRural Success Stories: #4 Revitalising Rural Europe through **Forestry & Natural Habitat Solutions**: Showcasing 4 success stories.
- BioRural Success Stories: #5 Driving Innovation with **Biomaterials** in Rural Europe: Showcasing 8 success stories.

All the success stories are also presented on the BioRural toolkit.

Newsroom

The section contains the project press releases as well as the events and project’s news informing target stakeholders about the project’s activities. The media kit is also available in this section, providing access to all the project communication material (e.g., logo, brochure, banner).

Latest News

Figure 19: BioRural website "Newsroom" tab

Project News

This subsection gathers all news and updates related to **BioRural**, highlighting key project milestones and partners’ activities. It features important announcements, such as the launch of the **BioRural Toolkit** and the **Online Call**, as well as developments linked to the **EU Bioeconomy Challenge**. In addition, it presents news and insights connected to the project’s core themes—**bioeconomy, circular economy, and bio-based solutions**—shared by BioRural partners, ensuring a comprehensive overview of both project-driven initiatives and broader sectoral progress. Throughout the duration of the project, **63 blog posts** have been generated, exceeding the initial target of 61 blog posts. An indicative overview of the blog posts is presented in the image below.

Figure 20: BioRural website | Indicative blog posts

Contact us

All the contact information of the BioRural project will be available under this section enabling the easiest communication with the project’s stakeholders.

Figure 21: BioRural website “Get in touch” tab

The Privacy Policy, together with the Terms and Conditions have also been included in the BioRural website, set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors’ use of the website.

Figure 22: BioRural website “Privacy Policy” tab

1. What are Cookies?

"Cookies" are small text files that are stored on your computer through the Internet browser, only retaining information related to your preferences and therefore not including your personal data.

2. What are Cookies for?

Cookies help determine the usefulness, interest and number of uses of your websites, allowing for faster and more efficient browsing, eliminating the need to repeatedly enter the same information.

3. What type of Cookies do we use?

There are two groups of cookies that can be used:

Permanent Cookies: These are cookies that are stored in the browser in your access equipment (PC, mobile and tablet) and are used whenever you visit our website more than once. They are generally used to direct the browsing to the user's interests, allowing us to provide a more personalised service.

Figure 23: BioRural website "Cookies Policy" tab

RFF provided a template enabling partners to contribute to the site's content and describe their specific role and activities in the project:

Partner description for the website	
Full name of the partner	
Short name of the partner	
Country	
Website	
Short description of the partner	
Short description of the partner's role in the project	

Figure 24: Template for Partners description

Important Highlights until M36

At the time of this deliverable's submission, the BioRural project website demonstrated strong performance and user engagement. The informative and appealing content related to the project's activities—such as the European Bioeconomy Challenge, the various workshops, and the development of the BioRural Toolkit—attracted considerable attention, as reflected in the high number of visits and interactions. The interest shown by visitors in exploring the project's progress underscores the effectiveness of the communication strategy. According to the analytics below, **6.2K users** visited the website and engaged with its content for an average duration of **1 min and 36 secs**.

Figure 25: BioRural website analytics [01 September 2022 - 29 July 2025]

3.2.2 Digital and printed outreach

3.2.2.1 Social media

The project aimed at a strong social media presence and established two-way communication channels, to better reach and interact with target audiences and the broader public. To enhance interactive communication, five (5) media channels were selected based on the following three factors:

- The most **cost-effective** set of channels for sharing immediate updates from the project to all stakeholders' groups;
- The most **adequate, valid, and powerful** media channels for spreading and influencing with novel practices, a wide spectrum and number of key-stakeholders and
- The most **popular** social media platforms to communicate and interact with various stakeholders. BioRural is registered and active in LinkedIn, Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), SlideShare and YouTube since M3 and has established metrics for each channel to monitor its effectiveness and implement mitigation measures when necessary.

The social media channels described above have been selected to further enhance the multi-actor approach of the project. Different kinds of stakeholders require different means of approach. In that sense, the following characteristics have been taken into account:

- **Facebook:** This channel is used mainly for building relationships and keeping contact with peers and contacts. It is a good platform for building loyalty to the existing network base. Because of the plain language and messages, the content can reach out to several target groups regardless of social and business backgrounds. BioRural will use this channel to reach biobased professionals, rural /urban citizens, training institutions, NGOs, citizen groups, think tanks by sharing any project and partner news and updates.
- **X (formerly Twitter):** This channel is used mainly for building awareness and enhancing public relations. Twitter is also often used to provide real time updates. BioRural will use this channel to reach regional

or national governmental bodies, policy makers, research institutions, NGOs and media actors by focusing on workshops and events that will be happening throughout its course.

- **LinkedIn:** This channel is used mainly for creating awareness and generating networking and collaboration opportunities due to its professional character and style of communication. BioRural will use this channel to reach Bio-based innovators and professionals, Bioeconomy experts, think- tanks and other relevant stakeholders by promoting the creation of the ERBN and sharing updates about project key activities.
- **YouTube:** This channel is mainly used for awareness and training purposes due to its character and features. BioRural will use this channel to reach any stakeholder interested in Bioeconomy by promoting testimonial videos on the identified success cases, interviews, and outreach videos.
- **SlideShare:** This channel is mainly used for communication and education purposes. Project presentations will be uploaded for easy access to anyone interested.

To maximise visibility and impact of the project's events and outcomes, BioRural exploited the consortium's already developed social media networks. This means that partners were expected to share, publish, and retweet content from BioRural's social media accounts and website, which increased traction for project-related work and increased traffic on partner's websites and social media. Partners were also encouraged to create relevant content to the project's actions and share it through their channels.

After selecting the most appropriate channels there were several parameters to be considered when creating social media content:

✓ **Interactivity** is the main pillar of the generated content and is the best way to reach and engage an audience. Posts will be easily understood by non-specialists to facilitate interaction.

✓ **Eye-catching** posts will lead to higher conversions with prioritisation into visuals and graphics will make the piece unique.

✓ **Adaptability** of the social media assets to the format and functionality of the several devices. The assets will be used in such a frame to maximise their placement, especially taking into consideration the placement on mobile devices.

Social Media Strategy and Key Points

Social media posts were published on BioRural’s official accounts on LinkedIn, Facebook, and X, with a standard frequency of at least one post per week, adjusted according to project needs and activities. This strategy aimed to maintain audience engagement and provide timely updates on various project-related topics, including:

- Partners’ event participation and project activities, such as webinars and workshops
- BioRural success stories
- The BioRural Toolkit
- The BioRural online call and regional workshops
- The European Bioeconomy Challenge
- Interesting articles, news, and resources on the project’s main concepts
- Media features about BioRural
- Newsletter and blog post updates
- Relevant International Days

Followers and subscribers actively interacted with the content—commenting, sharing, and sparking conversations depending on the platform—thereby strengthening BioRural’s visibility and outreach.

To further enhance the project’s presence, **two dedicated Facebook campaigns** were launched to promote BioRural’s key results, with a particular focus on the BioRural Toolkit. The first campaign aimed to build an engaged community around the project’s core themes—bioeconomy, circularity, and rural development—and successfully attracted a significant number of new followers, generating strong traction. Building on this momentum, the second campaign strategically promoted the Toolkit, aligning with the release of new materials and features. This timing maximized impact, driving stakeholders to explore and utilise the Toolkit at its most comprehensive stage. As a result, the campaign not only increased awareness but also stimulated active engagement with the Toolkit, showcasing BioRural’s success in translating communication efforts into tangible stakeholder uptake. An overview of the successful campaigns is presented below.

Figure 26: BioRural Facebook campaigns overview

3.2.2.2 Hashtags

Throughout the project's duration, relevant hashtags were created to enhance the visibility of BioRural's objectives and outcomes. These hashtags helped target specific audiences and facilitated the easy retrieval of knowledge generated by the project. They served to break down the project's main themes into engaging, digestible keyword phrases, thereby increasing visibility in social media environments and making our messages stand out within relevant communities. The monitoring of these hashtags enabled the consortium to analyze both quantitative and qualitative data to assess outreach and engagement.

Official distinctive hashtags such as **#Bioeconomy**, **#Rural**, **#Circular**, **#BioBasedSolutions**, and **#CircularEconomy** were consistently used to track project-related posts.

Additionally, EU-recommended hashtags like **#HorizonEurope** and **#ResearchImpactEU** accompanied each post to underline the project's alignment with the broader European Union research and innovation framework.

LinkedIn

A [LinkedIn profile](#) was created to network with the BioRural target audiences and promote the project's activities. As such, all the project's news was published on its LinkedIn profile and partners had the opportunity to start conversations on particular themes to attract a wider audience. Figure 27 provides an overview of BioRural's LinkedIn profile.

Figure 27: BioRural LinkedIn profile

Current Status

Figure 28 illustrates the project’s LinkedIn account’s visitor highlights over the course of the last one year [28 July 2024 – 27 July 2025]. **The page views reached 1,424, with 756 unique visitors.** Additionally, the graph shows that most visitors chose to navigate the project’s LinkedIn page from their desktop, with the mobile navigation also being of high preference.

Figure 28: BioRural LinkedIn account - Visitor highlights [28 July 2024 – 27 July 2025]

Regarding the LinkedIn page’s content, figure 29 presents the total impressions, reactions, comments and reposts that the page’s content sparked over the course of the past year [28 July 2024 – 27 July 2025]. The content of the project’s LinkedIn page reached **51,228 impressions** in the last year, marking an important reach for the project’s communication. Respectively, the total reactions accounted for **3,223**, with the comments accounting for 65 and the reposts for 50.

Figure 29: BioRural LinkedIn account - Visitor highlights [28 July 2024-27 July 2025]

Facebook

BioRural's [Facebook page](#) was developed to communicate directly with target audiences on an individual level.

Figure 30 provides an overview of BioRural's Facebook profile.

Figure 30: BioRural Facebook page

Current Status

Figure 31 presents the project's Facebook page's reach, regarding the period from 01 September 2022 to 28 July 2025. The total accounts reached throughout this period account for 120,4K, revealing an important potential audience for the project. The content interactions reached 4,8K while the total watch time was 4 days and 17 hours.

Figure 31: BioRural Facebook Analytics [Performance 01 September 2022 - 28 July 2025]

Another important Facebook metric is presented in Figure 32, which shows the number of page followers—1,300—as well as their age, gender, and top locations. BioRural’s Facebook followers are almost evenly divided between men and women, with women aged 35–44 emerging as the predominant audience. Additionally, Greece, Ukraine, and North Macedonia are identified as the top countries among BioRural’s followers.

Figure 32: Followers' Age & Gender Division [01 September 2022 - 28 July 2025]

X (formerly Twitter)

An **X** (formerly Twitter) **account** was created to increase the visibility of the project and engage specific audiences such as policy makers and advisors. BioRural will use short messages (less than 280 characters) to interact with them, and post news, events, and updates on the project's status.

Twitter's popularity and concise, simple format makes it extremely important and useful for informing and engaging with our targeted audiences and their respective communities. Twitter is also used to connect to 'high influencers' in the research and business topics of the BioRural project to successfully build an active community.

Figure 33: BioRural X profile

Current Status

X has undergone significant changes in recent months, resulting in restricted access to the project's account analytics. These platform policy updates have limited the availability of comprehensive performance data, now allowing only per-post analytics instead of aggregated account-level insights. As a result, it is no longer possible to track overall audience trends or long-term engagement patterns directly from the platform. Indicatively, in the figure below, we can see the analytics of the post published on August 1st, presenting BioRural on CORDIS. This post gathered 554 impressions, 15 engagements, 4 detail expands, and 4 link clicks

Figure 34: BioRural X post indicative analytics [August 1st, 2025]

SlideShare

A [SlideShare account](#) has been created to present project material in an engaging visual format that appeals to BioRural’s audience. However, over the course of the project, the account was not used extensively.

This was primarily due to the platform's relatively limited engagement levels compared to other social media channels, as well as the preference of the target audience for more interactive and familiar platforms such as LinkedIn, which offers better integration and reach. Additionally, resource constraints and strategic prioritization of channels that demonstrated higher engagement led to less frequent updates on Slideshare. Consequently, the platform was underutilized during the project’s lifetime.

YouTube

The [BioRural YouTube channel](#) has been actively maintained as a central hub for hosting and promoting the project's audiovisual content. It features the eight success stories produced within the project, recordings of presentations from the online knowledge exchange workshops, the ten podcast episodes developed, as well as a variety of other video materials created throughout the project's duration. This channel has served not only as an archive of project outputs but also as an accessible and engaging platform to reach diverse audiences, enhance visibility, and extend the lifespan and impact of the content beyond the project's immediate activities.

Figure 35: BioRural YouTube page

Current Status

The audiovisual material hosted on the BioRural YouTube channel is both rich and diverse, showcasing the project's outcomes in an engaging and accessible way. It includes the BioRural success stories, presented in a visually captivating format, as well as recordings from the five Knowledge Exchange Workshops organised by BioRural partners and hosted online. In total, **105 videos** are carefully organised into **eight thematic playlists**, facilitating audience navigation and enabling users to easily locate content of interest. Specifically, visitors can access:

01. [BioRural Success Stories playlist](#)
02. [Biochemicals & Biomaterials Knowledge Exchange Workshop playlist](#)
03. [Aquatic Systems Knowledge Exchange Workshop playlist](#)
04. [Agriculture & Food Knowledge Exchange Workshop playlist](#)

- 05. [Forestry & Habitats Knowledge Exchange Workshop playlist](#)
- 06. [Bioenergy Knowledge Exchange Workshop playlist](#)
- 07. [Innovation and Entrepreneurship in Circular Bioeconomy training materials playlist](#)
- 08. [BioRural Podcasts playlist, featuring all ten episodes](#)

This structured categorisation not only enhances user experience but also strengthens the visibility and long-term impact of the project’s audiovisual outputs by ensuring content is discoverable, well-presented, and relevant to diverse stakeholder interests.

Figure 36 presents an overview of BioRural’s YouTube analytics from the project’s launch to date, illustrating the channel’s growing reach and audience engagement. To date, BioRural’s videos have accumulated **5,271 views**, amounting to **214.3 watch hours**, and the channel has attracted a total of **92 subscribers**. These figures reflect the steady interest in the project’s audiovisual content and its ability to engage viewers over time, contributing to the broader dissemination and impact of BioRural’s results.

Figure 36: BioRural YouTube analytics [01 September 2022 – 17 August 2025]

Important highlight | Omni-channel campaign

To promote the **BioRural EU Bioeconomy Challenge**, a key milestone for the project, BioRural activated all its digital communication channels to maximise outreach, engage target audiences, and attract participants and stakeholders. An **omni-channel campaign** was strategically implemented, achieving strong visibility, high levels of engagement, and remarkable results.

The campaign leveraged **newsletters, blog articles, social media posts, press releases, and the project website**, ensuring a consistent and impactful message across platforms. This integrated approach not only boosted participation in the Challenge but also increased awareness of BioRural’s mission and activities among a wider community of stakeholders.

The following image presents an overview of the campaign’s impact and outcomes.

Figure 37: EU Bioeconomy Challenge Omni-Channel Campaign

3.2.2.3 Brochure

Brochures were distributed at the project's events (regional and National workshops, EU Bioeconomy Challenge) as well as relevant events where the project was promoted, to provide concise project information relevant to the target groups. The 3-fold brochure that has been disseminated, is presented below (Figure 38) as well as in [Annex C](#) along with its translated versions to all partners' languages.

Figure 38: BioRural Brochure sides A&B

3.2.2.4 Banner

Banners were used at physical events for eye-catching identification of the BioRural booth. Two versions of the banner have been created, with the latest to include the project’s social media as well as a QR code leading to the project website providing direct access to the project’s scope and activities. The BioRural banner is presented in Figure 39 and Annex C along with its translated versions to all partners’ languages.

Figure 39: BioRural Roll-up Banner

3.2.3 Multiplier campaigns

3.2.3.1 Newsletter

An electronic newsletter was published on a six-month basis to provide updates and relevant information to subscribers and consortium members. It included the latest developments, promotional material, as well as activities, upcoming events, and workshops.

Important highlights until M36

In total, **7 issues** of the BioRural newsletter have been published, including special editions dedicated to the EU Bioeconomy Challenge, gathering **510 newsletters subscriptions**. The issues have been promoted via BioRural's social media and website.

Biorural Newsletter [1st Issue](#)

Issue 1 of the newsletter was released on March 22nd, 2023, and was focused on introducing the project

and presenting the main actions taken by the project partners in the first 6 months since its kick-off meeting.

The 1st BioRural Newsletter included:

- An introduction to the project
- Kick-off meeting in Athens
- Meet the consortium
- Our Success Stories
- BioRural at a glance
- Recent BioRural activities
- Other Bioeconomy news

Figure 40: Newsletter #1 overview

1st Newsletter Analytics

Figure 41 provides an overview of the 1st newsletter’s analytics, regarding the audience’s location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens and total clicks:

Figure 41: Newsletter #1 Analytics

BioRural Newsletter [2nd Issue](#)

Issue 2 of the newsletter was released on 21/07/2023 and was focused on bringing the latest project

updates to the audience, as well as announcing upcoming activities.

The 2nd BioRural Newsletter included:

- Announcement of the BioRural Toolkit upcoming release in September 2023
- Call interested stakeholders to join the European Rural Bioeconomy Network
- Our consortium travels around Europe: BioRural partners' activities
- BioRural joined the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance
- Latest BioRural synergies

Figure 42: Newsletter #2 overview

2nd Newsletter Analytics

Figure 43 provides an overview of the 2nd newsletter's analytics, regarding the audience's location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens and total clicks:

2nd Issue Newsletter Analytics

Successful deliveries 144 98.6% Clicks per unique opens 18.7%
 Total opens 214 Total clicks 31

Top locations by opens

	USA	90	45.9%
	France	75	38.3%
	Germany	7	3.6%
	Portugal	6	3.1%
	Greece	6	3.1%

Geographical distribution

Figure 43: Newsletter #2 Analytics

BioRural Newsletter [3rd Issue](#)

Issue 3 of the newsletter was released on 22/12/2023 and was focused on bringing the latest project updates to the audience, as well as announcing upcoming activities.

Figure 44: Newsletter #3 overview

The 3rd BioRural Newsletter included:

- The launch of the BioRural Toolkit
- The promotion of our Knowledge - Exchange workshops on the BioRural YouTube channel
- The announcement of the upcoming Knowledge - Exchange workshops
- The BioRural national workshops in rural areas
- An overview of the BioRural national workshops in Spain, Lithuania and Greece
- The promotion of the BioRural Success stories videos on the BioRural YouTube channel
- The annual project meeting
- Wishes for the holiday season

3rd Newsletter Analytics

Figure 45 provides an overview of the 3rd newsletter’s analytics, regarding the audience’s location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens and total clicks:

3rd Issue Newsletter Analytics

Successful deliveries	193	96.0%	Clicks per unique opens	28.4%
Total opens	181		Total clicks	52

Top locations by opens

	USA	82	50.3%
	Greece	30	18.4%
	Portugal	16	9.8%
	France	15	9.2%
	Slovenia	5	3.1%

Geographical distribution

Figure 45: Newsletter #3 Analytics

BioRural Newsletter [4th Issue](#)

The 4th BioRural Newsletter included:

- Invitation to the BioRural Online Call
- Categorisation per region
- Workshops on YouTube channel
- Circular Bioeconomy into practice: Local biomass into heating pellets for municipal kindergarten!
- Other news:
 - Where the built environment meets Circular Bioeconomy
 - What is Circular Bioeconomy? The CBE concept explained
 - The EU Bioeconomy Strategy Action Plan and Progress
 - Early BioRural recommendations transferred in 2 Referential bioeconomy events!

Figure 46: Newsletter #4 overview

4th Newsletter Analytics

Figure 47 provides an overview of the 4th newsletter’s analytics, regarding the audience’s location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens and total clicks:

4th Issue Newsletter Analytics

Deliveries	190 (96.4%)	Clicks per unique opens	14.0%
Total opens	521	Total clicks	55

Top locations by opens

	Opens	% of total opens
United States	127	24.4%
Netherlands	32	6.1%
Greece	21	4.0%
France	20	3.8%
Denmark	19	3.6%

Geographical distribution

Figure 47: Newsletter #4 Analytics

BioRural Newsletter [5th Issue](#)

Figure 48: Newsletter #5 overview

The 5th BioRural Newsletter included:

- Reminder for participating in the BioRural Online Call
- Categorisation of the Online Call per region
- Useful files for the applicants
- Knowledge-Exchange workshops on YouTube

5th Newsletter Analytics

Figure 49 provides an overview of the 5th newsletter’s analytics, regarding the audience’s location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens and total clicks:

5th Issue Newsletter Analytics

Deliveries	188 (96.9%)	Clicks per unique opens	15.9%
Total opens	216	Total clicks	54

Top locations by opens

	Opens	% of total opens
United States	151	69.9%
France	19	8.8%
Greece	11	5.1%
Portugal	9	4.2%
Netherlands	7	3.2%

Geographical distribution

Figure 49: Newsletter #5 Analytics

BioRural Newsletter [6th Issue](#)

Figure 50: Newsletter #6 overview

The 6th BioRural Newsletter included:

- BioRural Regional Workshops: Bioeconomy innovators at the forefront!
- South-West Region’s Winners | Spain
- South-East Region’s Winners | Greece
- North-East Region’s Winners | Poland
- North-West Region’s Winners | Denmark
- Invitation to the Final in Brussels

6th Newsletter Analytics

Figure 51 provides an overview of the 6th newsletter’s analytics, regarding the audience’s location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens and total clicks:

6th Issue Newsletter Analytics

Deliveries	484 (92.7%)	Clicks per unique opens	7.4%
Total opens	328	Total clicks	49

Top locations by opens

	Opens	% of total opens
United States	230	70.1%
Greece	20	6.1%
Australia	16	4.9%
Spain	13	4.0%
Poland	9	2.7%

Geographical distribution

Figure 51: Newsletter #6 Analytics

BioRural Newsletter [7th Issue](#)

Figure 52: Newsletter #5 overview

The 7th BioRural Newsletter included:

-BioRural Invitation to the EU Bioeconomy Challenge Final in Brussels: The European Bioeconomy Challenge comes to a close and we want you there!

Newsletter Analytics

Figure 53 provides an overview of the 7th newsletter’s analytics regarding the audience’s location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens and total clicks:

7th Issue Newsletter Analytics

Deliveries	484 (96.4%)	Clicks per unique opens	16.7%
Total opens	278	Total clicks	92

Top locations by opens

	Opens	% of total opens
United States	190	68.3%
Poland	15	5.4%
Greece	13	4.7%
Portugal	9	3.2%
Spain	6	2.2%

Geographical distribution

Figure 53: Newsletter #6 Analytics

Subscription to the newsletter was made through the project's website. For the development of the newsletters a Mailchimp account has been created by RFF.

Figure 54: BioRural Newsletter subscription form

Data security

BioRural paid special attention to security and respect of the privacy and confidentiality of the users' personal data and newsletter recipients are asked to provide their consent prior to receiving any information related to the project. All relevant activities and aspects related to personal data are fully compliant with the applicable national, European, and international legal framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/6798. Interested parties are able to subscribe and unsubscribe at any given point from the BioRural Newsletter and all the collected data is stored and saved in the responsible partner's servers. Data security is presented in the dedicated deliverable D6.3 Data Management Plan (M4) and in the D6.4 Data Management Plan 1st update due in M36. Data security is paramount for BioRural, the protection of personal data have been ensured through procedures and appropriate technologies, like the use of HTTPS protocol for the encryption of all internet transactions and appropriate European and Internet security standards from ISO, ITU, W3C, IETF and ETSI. During the lifetime of the project IUNG-PIB was responsible for the security of the BioRural's Toolkit and RFF have been responsible for the security of the BioRural website, keeping regular backups and solving all the technical issues that were raised in terms of the storage and representation of the data.

3.2.3.2 Press releases

Press releases were strategically produced and distributed to national, regional, and EU-level media outlets, serving as a key tool to promote the project, showcase its latest activities and achievements, and engage a wider audience, including targeted stakeholder groups. **To ensure accessibility and visibility, all press releases are available on the BioRural website under the "Newsroom" tab**, while their dissemination was further amplified through the project's social media channels, broadening outreach and stakeholder engagement.

The table below outlines the publication of **nine press releases**, aligned with project milestones and key tasks. While the initial communication plan presented in D5.1 provided the framework, slight adjustments were made in the timeline to reflect the project's dynamic progress. As milestones were achieved and significant updates emerged, additional press releases were crafted and distributed. This adaptive approach ensured that communication activities not only mirrored BioRural's advancement but also strengthened its visibility, credibility, and impact among stakeholders and the broader public.

Table 4: Press releases announcements

#	Month	Press release content	Status	Content
1	M2	<p>Press Release #1: BioRural has kicked-off!</p> <p><i>Linked to the project kick off (Milestone 1).</i></p> <p>The first press release was circulated on the 24th of October 2022 introducing the BioRural project. The release highlighted the project's objectives to promote sustainability in the rural bioeconomy, its strategic approach, and the importance of collaborative efforts across Europe to support innovation and regional development.</p>	✓	link
2	M15	<p><i>Linked to InCommon's first workshop in Greece</i></p> <p>The press release was circulated on the 13th of November 2023 and included details about InCommon organizing the first workshop in Greece. The release highlighted the event's focus on fostering collaboration, sharing knowledge on sustainable practices, and advancing bioeconomy initiatives within the region to promote regional development and innovation.</p>	✓	link
3	M17	<p>Press Release #2: The BioRural Toolkit is available!</p> <p><i>Linked to the launch of the toolkit (Milestone 7) and the progress of the online and national workshops (T3.1 and T3.2).</i></p> <p>The second press release was circulated on the 16th of January 2024, informing the audience about the launch of the BioRural Toolkit, as well as mentioning the knowledge exchange and national workshops of the project. The release emphasized ongoing activities, key achievements, and the project's commitment to advancing sustainable practices in rural bioeconomy development across Europe.</p>	✓	link
4	M29	<p>Press Release #3: Bioeconomy Regional Workshops: Driving Sustainable Innovation Across Europe</p> <p><i>Linked to the national workshops and online workshops – progress update (T3.1 and T3.2).</i></p> <p>The third press release was circulated on the 27th of January 2025, informing the audience about the four Regional Bioeconomy Platforms' workshops and the unique bio-based solutions that stood out per region- 12 in total. The release</p>	✓	link

		highlighted how these workshops facilitate knowledge exchange, promote local bioeconomy solutions, and strengthen regional capacities to support the transition towards sustainability in rural areas.		
5	M32	<p>Press Release #4: BioRural invites you to the EU Bioeconomy Challenge Final – set to Spotlight Europe’s Top Bio-Based Innovations!</p> <p><i>Linked to the announcement and invitation to the EU Bioeconomy Challenge Final in Brussels</i></p> <p>The fourth press release was circulated on the 16th of April 2025, announcing and inviting stakeholders to attend the BioRural EU Bioeconomy Challenge Final that was held in Brussels in May 2025. The release highlighted the event's focus on showcasing cutting-edge sustainable solutions, fostering collaboration among key stakeholders, and promoting the future development of the bioeconomy across Europe.</p>	✓	link
6	M33	<p>Press Release #5: The European Bioeconomy Challenge: Spotlight on Europe’s Sustainable Game-Changers</p> <p><i>Linked to the outcomes of the European Bioeconomy Challenge</i></p> <p>The fifth press release was circulated on the 23rd of May 2025, presenting the results of the European Bioeconomy Challenge and announcing the 3 winning bio-based innovators of the event. The release highlighted key innovative initiatives and stakeholders driving the transition towards sustainable bio-based solutions across Europe, emphasizing their role in promoting environmental, economic, and social sustainability.</p>	✓	link
7	M34	<p>Press Release #6: BioRural Leads the Discussion on the Future of the EU Bioeconomy at EuRCBC</p> <p><i>Linked to the project’s organisation and participation at the EuRCBC conference.</i></p> <p>The sixth press release was circulated on June 4th 2025, presenting the results of the European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference (EuRCBC) which was co-organised by BioRural along with five aligned EU-funded projects: SCALE-UP, ROBIN, MainstreamBIO, RuralBioUp, and Biomodel4Regions in Brussels. The release highlighted the project's role in shaping policy dialogues, fostering collaboration among stakeholders, and advancing sustainable bioeconomy strategies within Europe.</p>	✓	link

8	M35	<p>Press Release #7: BioRural Success Stories from 12 Countries Showcase the Future of Sustainable Rural Europe</p> <p><i>Linked to the promotion of the BioRural success stories</i></p> <p>The seventh press release was circulated on July 24th 2025 and included the showcase of BioRural success stories from 12 countries. The release highlighted how these stories demonstrate the future of sustainable rural Europe by emphasizing innovative practices, regional initiatives, and the positive impact on local communities across diverse rural settings.</p>	✓	link
9	M36	<p>Press Release #8: BioRural Successfully Concludes Its 3-Year Journey, Leaving a Lasting Legacy in the Rural Bioeconomy</p> <p><i>Linked to the completion of the project and its achievements throughout its duration</i></p> <p>The eighth press release was circulated on July 29th 2025 and included the announcement that BioRural successfully concluded its three-year initiative, achieving significant advancements in the rural bioeconomy. The release highlighted the project's contributions to innovative sustainable practices and regional development efforts, leaving a lasting impact within rural communities.</p>	✓	link

To maximise influence on local stakeholders, the consortium was asked to translate the press releases into all consortium partners' languages (14 in total). A press release template has been developed from the beginning of the project (Annex C) and shared with partners to facilitate the process.

3.2.3.3 Interviews

Interviews on radio and TV aimed to maximise the visibility of the project activities and reach a target audience that is not familiar with other digital channels such as the website and social media. The interviews were focused on the promotion of key activities of the project (e.g. success stories, creation of the ERBN, the BioRural toolkit etc.) and mainly targeted to the general public as well as bioeconomy actors (farmers, fishermen/women, foresters etc.).

Across Europe, BioRural partners have been engaged with local media outlets to share the project's vision and impact. These interviews showcased the diverse approaches and opportunities within the bioeconomy for rural areas. The interviews given are presented below:

#	Country	Partner	Communication channel	Content
1	Portugal	University of Coimbra	Participation in 90 s of science for a national radio 	link
2	Portugal	CENTRO DA BIOMASSA PARA A ENERGIA	Interview with RUC (University of Coimbra's Radio) 	link
3	Romania	Green Energy Romanian Innovative Biomass Cluster	Agriplanta Romagrotec Fair presence 	link
4	Romania	Green Energy Romanian Innovative Biomass Cluster	Interview/podcast: National program for biomass	link

5	Spain	AVEBIOM	<p>BioRural innovation event on inspiring practices for enhancing biomass use with >26 EU & innovation projects</p>	link

3.2.3.4 Promotional videos

The BioRural consortium has developed marketing-style videos promoting the project’s success stories ([Success stories playlist](#)) as well as the innovators behind them. The videos are available on the project’s [YouTube channel](#). The first eight success stories are presented in the table below.

Table 5: BioRural initial 8 Success stories

Partner	Success story
	“Bio-based Garden” success story
	“Bioplastics” success story
	“Pustelnia” success story
	“Latvia’s State Forests” success story
	“Gasification and Biochar from olive waste” success story
	“SCIVEN” success story
	“Staramaki” success story

	<h2>“Algae production” success story</h2>
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Figure 55: BioRural initial 8 Success stories | Videos

Throughout the course of the project **more than 15 additional marketing style videos** have been showcased promoting success stories that have been identified by project partners. A list with the additional marketing style videos is provided on the table below:

Table 6: BioRural additional Success Stories

Success story	Video material
MicrobePlus - Biological solutions provided by nature	Link
No waste from residual wood - A wood biorefinery around the gasification plant	Link
Aquaponics Iberia - Small-scale, closed and dynamic systems combining Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (RAS) with hydroponics techniques	Link
OXYGEN OF AGRAFA Social Cooperative Enterprise of Collective and Social Benefit (Koin.S.Ep.)	Link
Forest silviculture for fire prevention at ecotourism resort	Link
Re-using olive washing wastewater for fertigation	Link
Alcarrás BioProducers - Cooperative composting and biogas production	Link
The Fonda fish aquaculture	Link
Egg Energy Ltd	Link
Innovative biostimulants and plant protection bioproducts from wood residues	Link

Algae Spirulina: tasty superfood for health and energy	Link
Paper and packaging solutions made from invasive plants or horticultural residues from the idea to the prototype	Link
APIMI - Natural bee cosmetics manufacturer	Link
ENERGY COMMUNITY OF KARDITSA	Link
Wood Waste Processing Company Druplat	Link
Green protein to replace soya in feed	Link
AgFutura Technologies	Link

The above-mentioned success stories are also available on the BioRural toolkit.

Figure 56: Additional success stories | Marketing style videos

3.2.3.5 Podcast series

Podcasts, as a modern means of communication, have gained remarkable popularity in recent years. Easy to access and engaging to follow, they allow listeners to explore topics of interest on demand, with new episodes delivered automatically to subscribers. Their appeal continues to grow, with listener penetration across Europe expected to reach or even exceed 30% by 2030. Building on this trend, BioRural developed its own podcast series to promote the project’s objectives, diversify communication tools, and connect with audiences in a more dynamic and accessible way.

The BioRural podcast series follows an overarching theme, ensuring a cohesive and engaging narrative throughout. Each episode, lasting approximately 15–20 minutes, features a special guest from either within or outside the consortium, offering fresh perspectives and diverse insights. The full series is available free of charge on BioRural’s YouTube channel and Spotify, making it easily accessible to a wide audience.

Notably, three episodes highlighted voices from within the consortium: **Coordinator Thanos Balafoutis (CERTH), Mara Angelidou (Incommon), and Despina Kampouridou (reframe.food)**. Each of these contributors shared their expertise and perspectives, introducing listeners to the core concepts underpinning BioRural, while also reflecting on their role and contributions to the consortium. This approach ensured that the series not only informed but also built stronger connections with stakeholders by giving them direct access to the people driving the project forward.

The remaining seven podcast episodes (**Episodes 4–10**) **place the spotlight on the inspiring journeys of the winners from BioRural’s Regional Bioeconomy Platform workshops and the European Bioeconomy Challenge**. These episodes invite listeners into the stories behind each bio-based innovation, how their founders began, what motivated their solutions, and what they gained from participating in BioRural’s workshops and the EU Bioeconomy Challenge.

These episodes vividly illustrate the diversity of creative bio-based solutions—from sustainable packaging to new food ingredients. Each narrative underscores not just the technical achievements but also the transformative experiences gained through collaborative feedback, workshop mentorship, and the high-profile showcase at the Brussels final. The series thus succeeds in conveying the practical impact of BioRural—not just as a platform, but as a springboard that empowers innovators and strengthens Europe’s bioeconomy network.

The podcast episodes are briefly presented on the table below.

Table 7: BioRural podcast episodes descriptions

No	Title	Guest	Description
#1	Exploring BioRural with our Coordinator Thanos Balafoutis CERTH	Thanos Balafoutis CERTH	In the first episode, Thanos Balafoutis, Project Coordinator at CERTH, introduces BioRural’s core concepts, key achievements from its first two years, and future objectives.
#2	Bioeconomy Challenge & Collaboration in the Spotlight with Mara Angelidou Incommon	Mara Angelidou Incommon	In this episode, Mara Angelidou, Co-Founder and Director at Incommon, discusses the project’s Open Call, Incommon’s role in the RBP workshops, and offers insights into the upcoming Bioeconomy Challenge Finale in Brussels, along with next steps within BioRural.
#3	Communicating with BioRural's audience Despina Kampouridou reframe.food	Despina Kampouridou reframe.food	In the third episode, Despina Kampouridou from reframe.food discusses BioRural’s main audience, stakeholder engagement, and shares details about the upcoming Bioeconomy Challenge Final in Brussels on May 12.
#4	BioHide: Biodegradable, cruelty-free kombucha-based	Angelina Serafimovska BioHide	In this episode, Angelina Serafimovska, CEO of BioHide, presents their kombucha-based leather alternative, a sustainable and cruelty-free material. She reflects on how BioRural’s Thessaloniki workshop supported their

	leather Angelina Serafimovska		growth as they prepared for the European Bioeconomy Challenge Final in Brussels.
#5	Noema: Creating compostable clothes from bio-based materials	Sandra Vassilopoulou and Barbara Panopoulou Noema	In this episode, the Noema team discusses their compostable clothing solution, its role in promoting circular fashion, and shares insights from their participation in the BioRural Southeast workshop, highlighting mentorship and collaboration.
#6	YeastTech: Turning brewery spent yeast into high-quality, functional food products	Andrejs Bānis and Olga Latisenko YeastTech	In this episode, YeastTech (CircYeast) discusses their solution of converting spent brewer's yeast into sustainable, high-quality food products and reflects on mentorship and collaboration gained through the BioRural Northeast workshop.
#7	Energy from Forests: Decentralised Wood-Chip Power Plants	Luca Pacifico Energy from Forests	In this episode, Luca Pacifico presents Energy from Forests' small-scale gasification systems that convert forest debris into heat and power for rural communities and reflects on the mentorship and opportunities gained through the BioRural Southwest workshop.
#8	Protiberia: Proteins from Spent Mushroom Substrate	Alvaro Alemany Protiberia	In this episode, Alvaro Alemany presents Protiberia's circular solution using spent mushroom substrate for insect farming, producing proteins and compost, and reflects on development, local partnerships, and preparation for the European Bioeconomy Challenge final in Brussels.
#9	Nonstop Food: Turning Brewer's Spent Grain into Nutritious Food	Eva Mustafa Nonstop Food	In this episode, Eva Mustafa from Nonstop Food discusses their award-winning solution, its development journey from the regional BioRural workshop to the European Bioeconomy Challenge Final in Brussels and shares next steps and future plans.
#10	Prosevation: A Sustainable Alternative to Packaging	Henning Tschunt Prosevation	In this episode, Henning Tschunt from Prosevation presents their sustainable, plant-based cushioning packaging, shares its development journey from the BioRural regional workshop to the European Bioeconomy Challenge Final in Brussels, and outlines next steps and future plans.

Figure 57: BioRural podcast episodes overview | YouTube

Figure 58: BioRural podcast episodes overview | Spotify

BioRural foresaw the development of several scientific, industry and policy publications as well as practice abstracts to influence a wide range of targeted stakeholders and to promote the project and its findings in accordance with current EU regulations on Open Access and Open Science.

A key aspect for Open Science is to make collected data available for future research and analysis, while avoiding the exposure of any personal data without consent. The availability of project outputs as Open Access ensures:

- far higher citation counts for academic publications and reports;
- greater impact due to increased visibility with practitioners and the wider stakeholder community;
- high likelihood that future research and analysis will be able to build on and reuse our results rather than start ab initio, thereby helping in terms of the reproducibility and continuity of research results.

3.2.3.6 Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences

BioRural strived to publish peer reviewed scientific papers in respected and highly rated journals and scientific magazines. Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project’s results to the research community and providing scientific credibility for the project’s work. The publications made by the project partners during the 2nd reporting period include the following:

Publication Title	Partner	Scientific journals and conferences	Screenshot
A review of the EU bioeconomy: concepts, current state and the transition to a circular bioeconomy	CERTH	Open Research Gate	
The Role of Entrepreneurial Clusters in Advancing Circular Bioeconomy and Innovation: A Case Study from Romania	GEA	MDPI	

<p>Advances in Spirulina Cultivation: Techniques, Challenges, and Applications</p>	<p>ALGEN</p>	<p>intechopen.com</p>	
<p>EUROPEAN CONFERENCE ON RENEWABLE ENERGY SYSTEMS ECRES 2024</p> <p>16-17 May 2024</p> <p>Mallorca / Spain</p>	<p>IUNG</p>	<p>EUROPEAN CONFERENCE ON RENEWABLE ENERGY SYSTEMS 2024</p>	
<p>Strategic directions for supporting bioeconomy in Poland</p>	<p>IUNG</p>	<p>Monographs and Scientific Dissertations of IUNG</p>	<p>(To be published in September 2025)</p>

3.2.3.7 Industry publications

During the 1st reporting period BioRural published 16 articles in leading industry magazines, as presented in the previous version of the deliverable (5.2). During the 2nd reporting period, BioRural partners published 17 articles in industry magazines. **In total, 33 publications** have been made exceeding the target of 16 (KPI D2.2 Articles in industry magazines).

Important highlights until M36

During the 2nd reporting period **17 articles** have been published by the BioRural partners in several local industry magazines. Some articles are showcased indicatively below:

Figure 59: Publications in industry magazines of partners countries

3.2.3.8 Policy Guideline Report

Building on the full breadth of project results, BioRural has developed a comprehensive set of **23 policy briefs** to support and accelerate the transition to a circular bioeconomy. These are presented in Deliverable 3.5 and are publicly accessible via the BioRural Toolkit. The collection includes 12 horizontal briefs addressing cross-cutting challenges and opportunities across the entire bioeconomy, as well as 11 specific briefs that provide targeted recommendations for particular sectors and value chain stages.

The topics covered range from enabling frameworks for smart farming, circular business models, and modular biorefineries, to the promotion of bioenergy villages and better integration of urban-rural biomass flows. System-level recommendations address the alignment of funding, governance, and regulatory instruments such as the Waste Framework Directive. In addition, BioRural has co-authored a joint policy brief with the three other Horizon Europe projects funded under the same topic, offering consolidated insights from across the EU bioeconomy landscape. Together, these outputs provide policy makers with a robust, stakeholder-informed foundation for accelerating the circular transition.

3.2.3.9 White papers

A white paper has been developed presenting key findings and recommendations from the BioRural project, aimed at advancing a sustainable and circular bioeconomy in Europe. It highlights the importance of coherence, innovation, and targeted investment in the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. Drawing on insights from grassroots stakeholders and technical experts, the paper addresses critical areas such as ensuring long-term competitiveness, increasing resource efficiency, securing sustainable biomass supply, and positioning the EU in the global bioeconomy. It emphasizes the need for policy alignment, harmonized regulations, infrastructure investment, and enhanced education and training to support a thriving rural bioeconomy.

Key to this vision are the paper's "Cross-Cutting Insights and Strategic Recommendations," which emphasize:

- **Policy Coherence:** Aligning the Bioeconomy Strategy with the Green Deal, Circular Economy Action Plan, and Carbon Removal Certification Framework to maximize synergies and reduce inefficiencies.
- **Harmonized Regulations:** Establishing clear and consistent standards for End-of-Waste criteria and bio-based products to build trust and accelerate the transition.
- **Infrastructure Investment:** Funding logistics, modular biorefineries, and rural innovation platforms to unlock local potential and drive innovation.
- **Education and Training:** Developing tailored programs and integrating Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) to empower a skilled workforce and promote sustainable practices.

The paper emphasizes the need for policy alignment, harmonized regulations, infrastructure investment, and enhanced education and training to support a thriving rural bioeconomy.

3.2.3.10 Practice Abstracts

The goal of the PAs is to develop short summaries that describe the main information/ recommendation/ practice regarding the deployment of biobased solutions that can be used by the end-users to enhance circular economy and bioeconomy in the rural areas. According to the GA, BioRural had to produce 30 practice abstracts in the EIP Agri format dedicated to the project's activities and outcomes. However, project partners have developed 52 Practice Abstracts in total.

Important highlights until M36

As already presented in D5.2 partners have produced the first batch of Practice Abstracts (D5.4 submitted in February 2024) comprised of 27 Practice Abstracts. With the inclusion of the EIP-AGRI Project Database

to the EU CAP NETWORK platform, a project profile has been created for BioRural, and the first batch has been uploaded.

With regards to the second batch of Practice Abstracts (D5.5) which is due on August 30, project partners have developed 25 Practice Abstracts dedicated to the following subjects:

- "Bio-based solutions innovation report – Outcomes from BioRural’s 43 National Multi-innovation Workshops on Transitioning to Circular Biobased Value Chains
- Update of the ERBN creation, rural Bioeconomy stakeholders mapping, identification of competences, inventory creation
- Presentation of bioeconomy success stories
- Training material and video tutorials
- Presentation of the awarded solutions of the regional workshops and the Bioeconomy Challenge
- Policy guidelines for rural Bioeconomy development
- Presentation of the toolkit and new features
- Business models for resilience and circularity

The PAs have been uploaded on the EU CAP NETWORK platform.

3.2.4 Event planning

The event planning took part in two phases throughout the duration of the project. On a 6-month basis an event planning form was sent to the partners to describe the events that were already in their calendars (Annex D). A brief description including the date, location, target groups and a preliminary suggestion as to the role/implication for BioRural (i.e., workshop, booth) was requested to support the decision-making process. Responses were compiled using an online reporting tool (Table 8) for easy reference and record keeping.

Table 8: BioRural's event participation template

BioRural Event Planning						
#	Name and Type of event	Event link	Date(s) / Location(s)	Scale	Target groups	Potential BioRural involvement

The second phase involved the selection of events for which certain guidelines were provided to the partners. These necessary actions and when they should occur; aimed to ensure that event participation aligned with the project objectives and budget.

Figure 60: Guidelines for event selection and planning

3.2.5 Networking and synergies

Building synergies and expanding the BioRural ecosystem was a significant priority of the DEC plan. The project successfully built upon the experience, knowledge, and data developed by partners during other projects. This collaborative approach was integral to the DEC and involved a three-step process.

Phase 1: Identification

As part of this process, a template was distributed to all partners to gather information on any other projects, networks, or initiatives relevant to BioRural in which they were currently participating. This template was regularly updated throughout the project to incorporate new projects.

Table 9: BioRural's synergy & liaison mapping template

BioRural Synergy & Liaison mapping						
#	Type of Initiative	Full name	Website	Initiative Leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities

Phase 2: Evaluation

To ensure the identified synergies would benefit the project and align with BioRural's objectives, each

potential project, initiative, and network was assessed against qualitative/quantitative indicators such as:

- Relevance
- Estimated impact (e.g., visibility, added value);
- Feasibility (e.g., timeline and resources)
- Terms for collaboration, etc.

The results of the evaluation were consolidated with the information provided by partners.

Phase 3: Contact

Once it was agreed that a synergy should be established, the most appropriate approach for making contact was decided on a case-by-case basis.

Phase 4: Action

Communication pathways and joint activities were decided after discussions with their representatives and the BioRural consortium and included (but are not limited to):

- Joint communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities;
- Joint policy events;
- Coordinating research and/or joint publications;
- Sharing data, inputs and/or outputs;
- Participation in other events & networks;
- Links to project and project events on website, social media.

All the project’s templates have been uploaded by RFF to the project’s Google Drive folder that has been created, providing direct and continuous access to partners for updating reasons.

Important highlights until M36

Throughout the project duration, partners explored partnerships with other projects. A list of projects that have been identified as relevant to the projects is presented below:

Table 10: BioRural relevant EU projects list

	<p>SEEDSPRO2WINE implements one circular business model based on a pioneering & mature-R&D-results industrial process for the extraction of proteins from de-tannified grape to be exploited as a fining agent in the wine industry and to replace the traditionally-used protein gelatin of animal origin and protein extracts from food crops. A MoA has been signed between SEEDSPRO2WINE and BioRural for awareness raising & networking activities, communication and dissemination activities, as well as development of joint project ideas around circular Bioeconomy.</p>
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	<p>BBioNets will constitute a thematic network that will rely on, promote, and further advance the work carried out by EIP AGRI Operational Groups (OGs) with respect to management and/or processing of agricultural and forest biomass with Bio-Based Technologies (BBTs). BioRural partner IUNG presented BioRural and the toolkit during the kickoff meeting of BBioNets that took place in November 2023.</p>
	<p>EOM4SOIL aims at proposing best management practices of external organic matter (EOM) pre-processing and application on soil to contribute to climate change mitigation and improve soil health. Representative farming systems in Europe (arable crops and vineyards) are selected, taking into account the diversity of pedoclimatic conditions. The net budget of soil C storage and greenhouse gas emission including the pre-process step and field application, is assessed as well as the multiple effects of EOM application on soils including contaminants are quantified. Innovative pre-processing is recommended to improve C budget and soil health. BioRural project partner AIEL participated in the event “ State of the biochar supply chain in Italy” organized by the EOM4SOIL project by presenting BioRural and the toolkit. The event took place in May 2023.</p>
	<p>The Alps4GreenC project, funded by INTERREG Alpine Space, aims at setting-the-scene for transnational utilisation of biomass residues in the Alpine region, with a focus on Northern Italy, Austria, and Slovenia. The project searches biomass conversion opportunities and transnational biochar value chains. BioRural partner AIEL along with Alps4GreenC organised a workshop named after “The present and the future of biochar Innovation, regulation, and real application cases”. The workshop took place in March 2023.</p>
	<p>The AgriFoodTe project aims to launch four demonstration pilots (Living Labs), which will be monitored to calculate the environmental, social, and economic sustainability of the innovative measures that are being implemented. The project has a duration of three years. BioRural partner AVEBIOM cooperated with the AgriFoodTe project for the organisation of two workshops on Inland and Biobased Industries (under T.3.2) in October 2023.</p>

	<p>EU4Advice aims to lay the ground for effective capacity building of Short Food Supply Chains (SFSC) actors, by supporting advisors as catalysers of the knowledge flow from research to practice within an EU network of SFSC advisors, and by promoting the integration of SFSC advisors into national AKIS. AVEBIOM had a meeting with EU4Advice to find project synergies and took part in a Community of Practice (CoP) session organized by Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA), within the framework of the European ModernAKIS project. The event took place in October 2024.</p>
	<p>SKILLBILL seeks to raise awareness and the level of education among academia, industry, decision-makers and civil society on the urgent need decarbonize our societies through extensive deployment of renewable energy sources (RES). AIEL had meetings with SKILLBILL to explore collaboration pathways. The meetings took place in October 2024.</p>
	<p>ARGONAUT aims to address key uncertainties in the bio-products sector by developing a digital tool that gathers, analyzes, and maps data on production systems, helping users optimize resources and assess environmental impacts. BioRural partners that also participate in ARGONAUT project made a presentation of BioRural during the ARGONAUT's kick off meeting that was held in January 2025.</p>
	<p>The Greet CE project focuses on the green transition in Central Europe, aiming to increase the capacity of regional innovation ecosystems, especially SMEs, in less developed Central European regions. GEA as partner of Greet CE presented BioRural and explored synergies during a meeting that was held in August 2024.</p>
	<p>SAGRE project is comprised by a learning framework that represents the first stage of the development of the learning material for the project "TOOLS FOR DIGITAL AND SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE - SMART AGRI EXPERT". Representatives of AgFutura Technologies (SAGRE project partner) took active participation in the national capacity building workshop on Biomaterials and in the national capacity building workshop on Aquaculture held by BioRural in March and April 2024.</p>

	<p>Bio-LUSH aims to overcome obstacles in establishing a sustainable and thriving biofibrous industry in Europe. It focuses on ensuring a sustainable biomass supply, developing eco-friendly and scalable processing methods, optimizing biomass value chains, and embracing circular design principles for decarbonization and reduced eutrophication. GGP participated in Bio-LUSH Project - online workshop (initiating synergy between BioRural and Bio-Lush) that was held in October 2024.</p>
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Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA)

A significant update is the formation of the [Rural Bioeconomy Alliance \(RBA\)](#) with the participation of BioRural and 10 other projects. The Rural Bioeconomy Alliance is a newly established cluster of European-funded projects with a primary mission to promote the development of circular rural bioeconomy initiatives in the European Union, launched at the COOPID Bioeconomy Conference, on 31 May 2023, in Brussels.

The RBA comprises several European-funded projects, including:

1. BioRural;
2. [MainstreamBIO](#);
3. [P2Green](#);
4. [RELIEF](#);
5. [RuralBioUp](#);
6. [SCALE-UP](#);
7. [COOPID](#);
8. [BioModel4Regions](#);
9. [ShapingBio](#);
10. [CEE2ACT](#);
11. [ROBIN](#).

These projects share a common goal of developing and analysing success stories, best practices, pilots, and strategies to enhance the adoption of circular bioeconomy concepts in rural areas. As a part of the alliance, BioRural and other members can share insights and knowledge on innovative advancements. The Alliance actively promotes information exchange on successful case studies and pilots and provides support for organising workshops and seminars. Additionally, the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance encourages collaborative presentations at high-level events and conferences, granting members access to wider and more relevant audiences. Through collaborative efforts within the Alliance, members can accelerate the development of

circular rural bioeconomy initiatives across the EU, thereby contributing to a sustainable future for all. The RBA will include additional members within the coming months.

To strengthen their partnership and shared objectives within the **Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA)**, the **European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference (EuRCBC)** was held on **13–14 May 2025** in Brussels, co-organised by six EU-funded projects—**BioRural**, **SCALE-UP**, **ROBIN**, **MainstreamBIO**, **RuralBioUp**, and **Biomodel4Regions**. The event showcased how collaboration accelerates the transition towards a **circular, inclusive, and sustainable rural bioeconomy**. In this joint effort, BioRural took centre stage, actively shaping the conversation on the future of the EU bioeconomy while reinforcing its commitment to strong partnerships and shared goals.

Figure 61: BioRural at the EuRCBC

Other synergies

On the 9th of May 2023, a [Conference](#) was organised by AVEBIOM through the BioRural and BRANCHES projects with the collaboration of **more than 10 National and European innovation projects**. The conference included the organisation of a workshop dedicated to Innovative business practices that enable new businesses in bioenergy and bioeconomy, the presentation

of the participating projects and the creation of synergies as well as networking between them. A list of the participating projects and initiatives is presented below:

Table 11: Projects participating in the Expo biomasa

Project	Programme	Type
MainstreamBIO	Horizon Europe	BIOECONOMY - promotion
SCALE-UP	Horizon Europe	BIOECONOMY - promotion
BIOTRANSFORM	Horizon Europe	BIOECONOMY - promotion
ROBIN	Horizon Europe	BIOECONOMY - promotion
AGROFOSSILFREE	H2020	BIOENERGY - promotion and transfer
Biomasa CAP	INTERREG POCTEP	BIOENERGY - Promotion and transfer
AURORAL	H2020	BIOENERGY - ICT tools support

BEcoop	H2020	BIOENERGY
MOR-e	AECID	BIOENERGY
Forest Biomass in the industrial sector in Jalisco, Mexico	Private promotion	BIOENERGY
BIOCOGEN	ERDF. Portugal 2020 Programme	BIOENERGY
LIFE4DRYGAS	LIFE	BIOENERGY
ALL-TO-GAS	AEI	BIOENERGY
LDBA	ERDF-MRR	BIOENERGY
RE4Industry	H2020	BIOENERGY
Use of agricultural residues for the development of biobased materials	Private promotion	BIOPRODUCTS
LIFE Bioreformed	LIFE	BIOPRODUCTS
BeonNAT	BBI-JU	BIOPRODUCTS
BIOCISTUS 4.0	National R&D&I Plan	BIOPRODUCTS
BIOVALOR	PRTR - NextGeneration EU	BIOPRODUCTS
ESjara	PDR	BIOPRODUCTS
TREEADS	HE	FORESTRY
FIREPOCTEP	INTERREG POCTEP	FORESTRY
CHAMELEON	H2020	FORESTRY
transForm	Next Generation (Portugal)	FORESTAL

3.2.6 EC tools

BioRural made extensive use of the European Commission’s tools to strengthen the dissemination (D), exploitation (E), and communication (C) of its results. In particular, Zenodo, the EU CAP Network, and CORDIS were strategically employed as key platforms to host, showcase, and further promote the project’s publications, deliverables, and practice abstracts, thereby ensuring wide accessibility and long-term visibility of outcomes.

Figure 62: EC Tools utilised

4 Monitoring and evaluation

4.1 KPIs

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are concrete, measurable targets used for monitoring and evaluating the project's progress and enabling adaptation when necessary. A set of dissemination and communication KPIs and targets have been identified and are presented in the following tables:

Table 12: Dissemination KPIs

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target
D1	Project events	
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)	5
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops	42
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops	4
D1.4	Participation in conferences	>10
D1.5	Participation in workshops	>5
D1.6	Participation in webinars	>5
D2	Scientific publications	
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences	3
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines	>15
D3	ERBN	
D3.1	Representation in fairs	>5
D3.2	Representation in working groups	>5
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions	>5
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge	1
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders	10000
D4	Synergies	
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects	>15
D4.2	Representation in working groups	>4
D4.3	Representation in alliances	>5
D5	Policy guidelines	
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report	>1
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials	>5

Table 13: Communication KPIs

#	Communication KPIs	Target
C1	Branding & material	
C1.1	Visual identity	1
C1.2	Motto in all project languages	1
C1.3	Website	1
C1.4	Social media channels	5
C1.5	Flyers	4000
C1.6	Banners	15
C2	Digital outreach	
C2.1	Unique visitors (website)	1000
C2.2	Blog posts	60
C2.3	Social media Posts (in all social media)	>500
C2.4	Social media audience	>1000
C2.5	Hashtags in social media	3-5
C2.6	Distributed printed/digital promotional materials	2000
C3	Multiplier campaigns	
C3.1	E-newsletter subscriptions	>500
C3.2	Press releases	9
C3.3	Interviews in radio/TV & outreach videos	11
C3.4	Marketing-style videos with introduction success stories & innovators interviews	20
C3.5	2 Podcast series (10 episodes) in Google podcasts app	10

4.2 KPIs per year

Furthermore, the KPIs have been distributed between the three years in which the DEC plan will be also updated. Table 11 and 12 include a breakdown of the expected KPIs and their targets to be achieved during each year. This will be a preliminary plan that is foreseen and is subject to change and updated by each deliverable based on projections of the project activities and the scope of each partner. Furthermore, the reporting mechanism will help maintain accountability and achieve these targets.

Table 14: Dissemination KPIs per Year

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
D1	Project events				
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)	5		5	
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops	42		42	
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops	4		4	
D1.4	Participation in conferences	>10	1	7	3
D1.5	Participation in workshops	>5	1	3	2
D1.6	Participation in webinars	>5		3	5
D2	Scientific publications				
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences	3			3
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines	>15		6	10
D3	ERBN				
D3.1	Representation in fairs	>5			6
D3.2	Representation in working groups	>5		2	5
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions	>5			6
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge	1			1
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders	10000			
D4	Synergies				
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects	>15		9	10
D4.2	Representation in working groups	>4			5
D4.3	Representation in alliances	>5		3	3
D5	Policy guidelines				
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report	>1			2
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials	>1			2

Table 15: Communication KPIs per Year

#	Communication KPIs	Target	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
C1	Branding & material				
C1.1	Visual identity	1	1		
C1.2	Motto in all project languages	1	1		
C1.3	Website	1	1		
C1.4	Social media channels	5	5		
C1.5	Flyers	4000	4000		
C1.6	Banners	15	15		
C2	Digital outreach				
C2.1	Unique visitors (website)	1000			
C2.2	Blog posts	60	10	21	29
C2.3	Social media Posts (in all social media)	>500	135	195	175
C2.4	Social media audience	>1000			
C2.5	Hashtags in social media	3-5	5		
C2.6	Distributed printed/digital promotional materials	2000			
C3	Multiplier campaigns				
C3.1	E-newsletter subscriptions	>500			
C3.2	Press releases	9	1	4	4
C3.3	Interviews in radio/TV & outreach videos	11	2	9	
C3.4	Marketing-style videos with introduction success stories & innovators interviews	20	8		12
C3.5	2 Podcast series (10 episodes) in Google podcasts app	10			10

4.3 KPIs per partner

In order to effectively share the responsibility for spreading project results and maximising the impact derived from partners' expertise, experience, and networks, KPIs and targets have been assigned to each partner as presented in the following tables:

Table 16: Dissemination KPIs per partner

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	Sum	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	P17	P18	P19
D1	Project events																					
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop	5	5	•			•		•	•		•		•					•	•		•
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops	42	42	1	3	3	3	3		3	3	3	3	3		3	1	1		3	3	3
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops	4	4	•	•					•		•	•									
D1.4	Participation in conferences	>10	11	4						2	2	1		1					1			
D1.5	Participation in workshops	>5	6	2						1		1		1					1			
D1.6	Participation in webinars	>5	8	1	1	1				1	1	1		1					1			
D2	Scientific publications																					
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences	3	3						1	1	1											
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines	>15	16			2	1						4		1	1	4			1	1	1
D3	ERBN																					
D3.1	Representation in fairs	>5	6	1	1	1							1			1						1
D3.2	Representation in working groups	>5	7	1					1	1	1	1		1					1			
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions	>5	6	1		1							1			1					1	1
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge	1	1														1					
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders	10000	10000																			
D4	Synergies																					
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects	>15	17	4		4				2			3			2	2					
D4.2	Representation in working groups	>4	5	1		1				1			1			1						
D4.3	Representation in alliances	>5	6	2	1					1			1					1				
D5	Policy guidelines																					
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report	>1	2	2																		
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials	>1	2							1	1											

Table 17: Communications KPIs per partner

#	Communication KPIs	Target	Sum	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	P17	P18	P19
C1	Branding & material																					
C1.1	Visual identity	1	1														1					
C1.2	Motto in all project languages	1	1														1					
C1.3	Website	1	1														1					
C1.4	Social media channels	5	5														5					
C1.5	Flyers	4000	4000	450	200	200		200	200	300	200	300	300	200		200	450	200		200	200	200
C1.6	Banners	15	15														15					
C2	Digital outreach																					
C2.1	Unique visitors (website)	1000	0																			
C2.2	Blog posts	60	60	8	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	6	2	2	2	11	6	2	2	2	2
C2.3	Social media Posts (in all social media)	>500	505	50	20	20	20	20	20	10	20	20	30	20	20	20	85	50	20	20	20	20
C2.4	Social media audience	>1000	1100																			
C2.5	Hashtags in social media	5	5														5					
C2.6	Distributed printed/digital promotional materials	2000	2000														2000					
C3	Multiplier campaigns																					
C3.1	E-newsletter subscriptions	>500	505																			
C3.2	Press releases	9	9	1						1	1		1				2	1	2			
C3.3	Interviews in radio/TV & outreach videos	11	11	1	1		1			1		1	1		1		2	1		1		
C3.4	Marketing-style videos with introduction success stories & innovators interviews	20	20	2	2		2			2		2	2		2		2	2		2		
C3.5	2 Podcast series (10 episodes) in Google podcasts app	10	10														10					

4.4 Reporting tools

Event and communication reporting

During the first months of the project, the seamless execution of timely reporting and effective monitoring for all dissemination and communication activities was of paramount importance. To facilitate this process, RFF devised an online form, exemplified below, to systematically gather input from our consortium partners. This form was designed to capture the intricacies of their undertaken measures while ensuring a streamlined reporting structure. Within this framework, partners were entrusted with the responsibility of furnishing comprehensive feedback on their dissemination and communication endeavours on a monthly basis. This practice allowed for a meticulous tracking of project progress and a real-time assessment of the alignment between planned activities and actual implementation.

The screenshot shows a Google Form with the BioRural logo at the top. The title is "BioRural Event, Activity and Communication Reporting". The text inside the form reads: "Dear BioRural partners, This form will be used for reporting all activities and events organized or attended by the BioRural consortium members as well as communication channels engaged by the consortium members on a monthly basis. You are kindly requested to fill in the relevant information **prior to the monthly consortium meeting** so we may update the website and social media in a timely manner. Information will also be used to track KPIs and ensure we are meeting them. Sincerely, Foodscale Hub Team".

Figure 63: Google forms for collecting partner information regarding events and communication

However, as the project evolved, the need for an even more refined and collaborative approach to KPI reporting was recognized. As a result, a transition was made from the initial online form to a more interactive and adaptable tool, constructed using Google Spreadsheets. This solution fostered enhanced communication and collaboration between partners, facilitating a more robust data exchange process for the measured outcomes. This strategic shift empowered partners to provide granular insights into their progress. This iterative process ensures that KPIs remain aligned with project objectives, ultimately contributing to more effective impact measurement and strategic decision-making. Still, each month, all partners are requested to update this online inventory of any communication or dissemination activities and deposit corresponding promoting material such as photos, reports, etc. in a designated folder. This procedure has proven that it reinforces accountability and engagement with the dissemination and communication process. RFF is responsible for monitoring the KPIs on a monthly basis and giving updates to the rest of the partners at relevant meetings. In case significant, or repeated deviations are recorded from certain partners, the coordinator will be officially informed. Deviations will have to be justified, discussed among partners, and changes on the DEC strategy will be reported on the updated versions of the DEC plan. In total, this online google spreadsheet has been developed and uploaded on the project's shared Drive and is available to all partners. The spreadsheet includes the following:

- **Sheet 1: Instructions** - The workbook provides instructions, a description of the KPIs, the breakdown per reporting period and a sheet dedicated to each partner. In each spreadsheet, the respective participating organisation can see the KPIs assigned to them, and the dissemination and communication activities that need to be reported, accordingly, per month of action.

Instructions

- This file has been designed to track the KPIs committed in the GA and the targets agreed upon by partners included in the DEC plan. The overall and yearly breakdown of the Dissemination & Communication KPIs can be found on the [Total KPIs sheet](#).
- Each partner has a dedicated sheet with two tables:
 - KPIs distribution**
 - The overall target for each KPI per partner
 - Dissemination & Communication actions including:**
 - Please use the drop down menu to select the category of dissemination & communication activity that your organisation organised, participated and/or executed and provide the date, name and link of the activity.
 - Please indicate if the dissemination activity should be considered a joint activity (**external to the consortium**). If yes, please indicate with whom.
- In case the dissemination/communication activity does not fall under the already existing KPI categories, do not fill in the drop-down menu and leave it empty, while filling-in all the other columns.
- Click on links for each month to upload pictures or relevant materials (e.g., agenda, presentations) from events that may be used for dissemination and communication purposes.

Please note:

- * we suggest posts come from your organization's social media account, rather than a personal account and that you tag BioRural
- * please include the dates and links
- * blog posts refer to the creation of content included in BioRural's website (posts to other websites can be also made)

Figure 64: Instructions for the new reporting form

- **Sheet 2: KPIs per year** - This sheet includes the allocation of the KPIs per year of implementation by taking into account the implementation progress.

#	Dissemination KPIs	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Target
D1	Project events				
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)		5		5
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops		42		42
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops		4		4
D1.4	Participation in conferences	1	7	3	11
D1.5	Participation in workshops	1	3	2	6
D1.6	Participation in webinars		3	5	8
D2	Scientific publications				
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences			3	3
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines		6	10	16
D3	ERBN				
D3.1	Representation in fairs			6	6
D3.2	Representation in working groups		2	5	7
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions			6	6
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge			1	1
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders				10000
D4	Synergies				
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects		9	10	19
D4.2	Representation in working groups			5	5
D4.3	Representation in alliances		3	3	6
D5	Policy guidelines				
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report			2	2
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials			2	2

Figure 65: Total KPIs allocation per year

- **Individual Partner Reporting Sheets**

A set of distinct reporting sheets has been crafted for each consortium partner. These tailored sheets serve as a user-friendly and efficient platform for documenting their executed dissemination and communication activities. The process has been streamlined for ease of use and accuracy. Within these sheets, a user-friendly drop-down menu is integrated under the KPI category tab. This intuitive feature empowers partners to conveniently select the relevant category for their executed dissemination or communication action. Subsequent fields facilitate the input of essential information, encompassing data specifics, activity names, associated links, and other pertinent details. To facilitate differentiation between no reporting and nonparticipation in relevant activities, partners can indicate "Nothing to report" if they have no dissemination or communication activities to report. Additionally, to support visual documentation, each month features clickable links to designated folders for partners to upload photos and other pertinent materials such as agendas, presentations, and minutes. These resources may be leveraged for reporting, dissemination, or communication purposes. This comprehensive framework ensures a holistic approach to tracking, documenting, and sharing project activities. This structured format enhances the clarity and consistency of reporting, ensuring that all vital information is accurately captured. The user-friendly design encourages partners to comprehensively document their activities, fostering an environment of collaboration and data accuracy.

October 2023										
Photos and other material										
Dissemination KPI	Date	Name of Activity	Link	Joint Action (YES)	If yes, with whom?	Communication KPI	Date	Name of Activity	Link	
Please indicate "nothing to report" if needed				<input type="checkbox"/>						
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				

November 2023										
Photos and other material										
Dissemination KPI	Date	Name of Activity	Link	Joint Action (YES)	If yes, with whom?	Communication KPI	Date	Name of Activity	Link	
Please indicate "nothing to report" if needed				<input type="checkbox"/>						
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				

December 2023										
Photos and other material										
Dissemination KPI	Date	Name of Activity	Link	Joint Action (YES)	If yes, with whom?	Communication KPI	Date	Name of Activity	Link	
Please indicate "nothing to report" if needed				<input type="checkbox"/>						
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				

Figure 66: Individual Partner Reporting Sheet

The form is also available on project’s google drive, enabling partners to go back and review or add missing activities and it also allows for different members from the same organisation to provide input without redundancy. RFF monitors the reporting form monthly to keep track of engagement, and on a six-month basis consolidates the results of the reporting forms and evaluates them next to the KPIs. The findings of these reports will serve to monitor targets and inform DEC strategies, enabling pivoting when necessary or to inform partners when additional effort is required.

4.5 Monitoring tool for KPI tracking

To precision and efficiency in monitoring the KPIs, RFF has meticulously developed and deployed a dedicated monitoring tool to track the progress of our partners' achieved KPIs. This robust tool is constructed utilising the capabilities of Google Spreadsheets, enabling real-time monitoring of KPI progress across reporting periods and partners. Figure 67 displays the comprehensive monitoring spreadsheet, where dissemination and communication KPIs are thoughtfully categorised into the three years of project implementation. Within each year, two validation statuses have been established to ensure both the timely completion of KPIs and the prompt implementation of mitigation measures, should the need arise.

#	Dissemination KPIs	Year 1	6 month check	Final check	Status	Year 2	28/11/2023	Final check	Status	Year 3	6 month check	Final check	Status	Sum	Target	Status
D1	Project events															
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)					5	2							2	5	
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops					42	6							6	42	
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops					4	1							1	4	
D1.4	Participation in conferences	1		19	Completed	7	3			3				22	11	
D1.5	Participation in workshops	1		3	Completed	3	2			2				5	6	
D1.6	Participation in webinars					3	1			5				1	8	
D2	Scientific publications															
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences									3				0	3	
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines					6				10				0	16	
D3	ERBN															
D3.1	Representation in fairs									6				0	6	
D3.2	Representation in working groups					2	1			5				1	7	
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions									6				0	6	
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge									1				0	1	
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders													0	10000	
D4	Synergies															
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects					9	1			10				1	19	
D4.2	Representation in working groups									5				0	5	
D4.3	Representation in alliances					3				3				0	6	
D5	Policy guidelines															
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report									2				0	2	
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials									2				0	2	

Figure 67: Monitoring tool for the KPIs

Moreover, within the same integrated spreadsheet file, individual sheets are thoughtfully allocated to each partner. These dedicated sheets are meticulously updated by RFF based on partners' monthly reports, consolidating their achievements and contributions. This meticulous approach further enhances transparency, collaboration, and accountability, streamlining the process of assessing our collective progress and promptly addressing any potential challenges.

#	KPI	TARGET														
Dissemination KPIs																
D1	Project events															
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops	1														
D2	Scientific publications															
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines	4														
D3	ERBN															
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge	1														
D4	Synergies															
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects	2														
Communication KPIs																
C1	Branding & material															
C1.1	Visual identity	1														
C1.2	Motto in all project languages	1														
C1.3	Website	1														
C1.4	Social media channels	5														
C1.5	Flyers	450														
C1.6	Banners	15														

Figure 68: Monitoring tool for each partner

The progress of the Dissemination and Communication KPIs in relation to the targets set for the initial reporting period is outlined in Figure 69. It's important to note that the status is based on the input provided by partners through the reporting form, which may not encompass the entirety of activity engagement. In the table, the status Completed indicates the respective KPIs have been successfully achieved, reflecting the notable progress made in meeting the targets. Also, the Ongoing status signifies the KPIs that are well on track. Conversely, the red boxes highlight KPIs that require heightened attention and effort to ensure successful attainment. This comprehensive overview aids in gauging the alignment of our current progress with the predetermined targets.

#	Dissemination KPIs	Year 1	6 month check	Final check	Status	Year 2	28/11/2023	Final check	Status	Year 3	6 month check	Final check	Status	Sum	Target	Status
D1	Project events															
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)					5	2							2	5	
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops					42	6							6	42	
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops					4	1							1	4	
D1.4	Participation in conferences	1		19	Completed	7	3			3				22	11	
D1.5	Participation in workshops	1		3	Completed	3	2			2				5	6	
D1.6	Participation in webinars					3	1			5				1	8	
D2	Scientific publications															
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences									3				0	3	
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines					6				10				0	16	
D3	ERBN															
D3.1	Representation in fairs									6				0	6	
D3.2	Representation in working groups					2	1			5				1	7	
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions									6				0	6	
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge									1				0	1	
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders													0	10000	

Figure 69: Completed, Ongoing and Uncompleted Dissemination KPIs

4.6 KPIs Final Status

4.6.1 Dissemination KPIs | Final Status

BioRural's commitment to disseminating its results is clearly demonstrated by the outstanding achievement of all dissemination KPIs. The project not only met but consistently exceeded its initial targets, underscoring the success of its comprehensive dissemination and communication strategy. The impressive results are detailed in the table below, highlighting the project's significant impact.

Table 18: Dissemination KPIs | final status

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	Achieved
D1	Project events		
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)	5	5
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops	42	43
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops	4	4
D1.4	Participation in conferences	>10	48
D1.5	Participation in workshops	>5	32
D1.6	Participation in webinars	>5	13
D2	Scientific publications		
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences	3	5
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines	>15	33
D3	ERBN		
D3.1	Representation in fairs	>5	19
D3.2	Representation in working groups	>5	11
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions	>5	9
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge	1	1
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders	10000	235.648 ¹
D4	Synergies		
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects	>15	21
D4.2	Representation in working groups	>4	6
D4.3	Representation in alliances	>5	6
D5	Policy guidelines		

¹ An analysis is provided in the section KPIs until M36- special highlights

D5.1	Policy Guideline Report	>1	1 ²
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials	>1	1 ³

4.6.2 Communication KPIs | Current Status

Similarly, over the course of the project, all communication KPIs were successfully accomplished, consistently meeting or exceeding the initial targets. The planned values and the achieved results are summarised in the table below.

Table 19: Communication KPIs | Current Status

#	Communication KPIs	Target	Achieved
C1	Branding & material		
C1.1	Visual identity	1	1
C1.2	Motto in all project languages	1	1
C1.3	Website	1	1
C1.4	Social media channels	5	1
C1.5	Flyers	4000	4000
C1.6	Banners	15	15
C2	Digital outreach		
C2.1	Unique visitors (website)	1000	6200
C2.2	Blog posts	60	63
C2.3	Social media Posts (in all social media)	>500	598
C2.4	Social media audience	>1000	3126
C2.5	Hashtags in social media	3-5	5
C2.6	Distributed printed/digital promotional materials	2000	2000
C3	Multiplier campaigns		
C3.1	E-newsletter subscriptions	>500	510
C3.2	Press releases	9	9
C3.3	Interviews in radio/TV & outreach videos	11	15
C3.4	Marketing-style videos with introduction success stories & innovators interviews	20	25

² Details about the Policy Guideline report is provided in section 3.2.3.8

³ Details about the White paper is provided in section 3.2.3.9

C3.5	2 Podcast series (10 episodes) in Google podcasts app	10	10
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KPIs until M36- special highlights

Exceptional Conference Participation: BioRural significantly exceeded its target for participation in conferences, attending 48 events compared to the initial target of ">10". This demonstrates a proactive approach to disseminating project findings within the respective community.

Strong Publication Record: The project doubled its target for scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences, achieving 5 publications against a target of 3. The number of articles in industry magazines also more than doubled. This shows a commitment to disseminating knowledge through both academic and industry channels.

Extensive Engagement of Stakeholders: The project demonstrated an exceptional ability to engage stakeholders, reaching **235,648 individuals** compared to the initial target of 10,000. This highlights the project's success in building a broad network and fostering participation.

A testament to this success lies in the significant attendance at BioRural's workshops. Online workshops drew **857 participants**, while national workshops saw an even larger engagement of **1078 attendees**. Regional workshops, crucial for tailored discussions, engaged **141 stakeholders**. The EU Bioeconomy Challenge further amplified this engagement, attracting **72 participants**.

The project's digital presence also played a pivotal role in reaching a vast audience. The BioRural website served as a central hub for information and resources, attracting over **6,200 unique visitors**. Furthermore, BioRural cultivated a substantial and active community on social media, with a combined following of over **227,000** across Facebook (120,000 followers), LinkedIn (102,000 followers), and YouTube (5,300 subscribers).

It's important to note that the remarkable figure of 235,648 individuals engaged refers specifically to those reached through direct, measurable project activities. The extensive interactions of project partners with stakeholders during conferences, workshops, and other external events are not included in this figure due to the difficulty in accurately recording them. Therefore, the project's overall stakeholder engagement is likely even higher than the numbers indicate.

These impressive figures demonstrate BioRural's dedication to fostering collaboration, disseminating knowledge, and building a vibrant community around the European bioeconomy. The extensive engagement achieved through workshops, online platforms, and social media channels underscores the project's impact and its success in connecting stakeholders from diverse backgrounds.

Broad ERBN Representation: BioRural/ERBN exceeded its targets for representation in fairs, working groups, and exhibitions, demonstrating a strong effort to promote the project and its network across various platforms.

Effective Synergies: The project established strong synergies with other EU projects, surpassing its target for liaison with EU projects and representation in relevant working groups and alliances.

5 Exploitation & IPR management

Throughout its duration BioRural produced several commercial and non-commercial Key Exploitable Results (KERs). This chapter provides a presentation of these results, potential pathways for their exploitation and IPRs related to them as identified.

5.1 Exploitation pathways

Each KER requires a unique exploitation approach based upon the type and whether it can be commercialised. A description of the KERs, their target groups and the unique value they offer are described in this section as well as potential exploitation pathways for commercial and non-commercial results.

BioRural has identified 4 key exploitable results (KERs) that are available for use/reuse by partners and target groups stakeholders. Tables 20-23 describe each result, scope of exploitation, UVP, target groups and scope/means of exploitation.

All partners provided their feedback by answering an online table - tailor made to BioRural's exploitation and IPR validation (Annex I).

The following table presents the KERs associated with the partners involved in their exploitation according to the identification process made during DEC preparation.

Table 20: ERBN- Key Exploitable Result

KER name: European Rural Bioeconomy Network	
Partners contributing to its development	All partners
Description of the KER	<p>Four regional RBPs have been formed by splitting Europe into 4 quartiles (NW, NE, SW and SE) to connect neighbouring countries and identify commonalities to impose members' connection and ensure sustainability. The 4 RBPs have constituted the ERBN as a result of T2.1 Development of European Rural Bioeconomy Network. As described in D. 2.1 European Regional Bioeconomy Network and its 2 updates, partners located, made connections, and developed synergies with Bioeconomy actors to stimulate knowledge exchange, cooperation and collaboration and assist in developing future rural Bioeconomy initiatives.</p> <p>Each RBP was led by one partner (NW: DELPHY, NE: IUNG, SW: AVE and SE: CERTH) to ensure the process continuation during the project.</p>
Unique Value Proposition	<p>Creation of a Network of more than 600 members from various sectors including primary sector, Academia, Public Authorities, Industry, Consultants</p> <p>etc. joining forces to boost Bioeconomy in rural areas.</p>
Target groups	<p>Scientific Community, Policy makers, Industry, Society-Citizens, NGOs, environmental groups, think tanks, any other key actor in knowledge transfer" (or any key actor in the national AKIS system)</p>
Scope of exploitation	Non-commercial & Commercial
Means of exploitation	<u>Non-commercial</u>

	<p>More information about the available features and the operation of the BioRural toolkit are presented in D. 4.3 Toolkit Content and Updates (1st update) submitted on M36.</p>
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European Rural Bioeconomy Network - Achievement until M36

Over three years of project BioRural has focused on establishing a durable European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN), aiming to widespread knowledge and vision on circular bioeconomy solutions applicable in rural contexts or by rural actors.

Between Months 12 and 24, efforts focused on two directions: 1) defining the ERBN scope, and 2) forming a community of key actors and stakeholders from multiple EU countries.

Through this period, already by Month 18, the partners identified the core values the ERBN could deliver: aggregation of key stakeholders in small-scale bio-based solutions, active knowledge transfer, a living community of contacts and materials, functional hosting for circular bioeconomy communities, recognition by national AKIS bodies, and connections to EU platforms such as EIP-Agri and EU-Farmbook. These values underpin the ERBN’s potential to attract key organizations willing to invest in maintaining and growing the network.

A re-scoping shifted the ERBN into a thematic driven network. It was envisioned the ERBN would acquire its full functionality if actions and topics were driven by the urgent needs of primary producers, particularly around residues management and circular bioeconomy. SWOT analyses and strategic planning identified key action lines by M24, including engagement with EU-Farmbook, AKIS, RBA projects, and thematic working groups as key items. Driving a change and ensuring continuity required in most BioRural countries to secure resources for the management of the network and the maintenance and update of the toolkit.

By the end of the project, BioRural has grown the ERBN community reaching **616 members**, and multilingual toolkit with numerous entries on success cases, technologies, factsheets, articles, tutorials and trainings, ideas, among others. Funds have been secured in a collaboration going on in parallel to BioRural, by joining forces of Circ-Bio projects (MainstreamBio, Rural BioUp, Scale-UP and BioRural) and EU-Farmbook, with multiple practitioners and advisors’ networks in 8 EU countries. The newly funded thERBN project, starting in January 2025, transitioned the network into a thematic, practitioner-driven structure, linking farmers’ needs, AKIS actors, and EU knowledge platforms. So, in coincidence with the scope for exploitation of BioRural legacy, already identified in period M12-M24.

Thanks to BioRural work in 14 countries with a vast number of national key actors, including AKIS management bodies and principal actors, a good base has been created to start national working groups under the new thematic network ERBN. The collaboration ensures continuity, practical relevance, and sustainable governance of ERBN as an active, value-generating network beyond BioRural.

Table 21: Toolkit- Key Exploitable Result

KER name: BioRural Toolkit	
Partners contributing to its development	All partners
Description of the KER	The Toolkit integrated various levels of information (e.g., scientific publications & reports, policy guidelines, legislation, small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas) and made it available to registered users.
Unique Value Proposition	An effective, all-encompassing BioRural Toolkit with an enhanced repository of up-to-date Bioeconomy data.
Target groups	Innovators, Rural areas’ actors (e.g., farmers, foresters), Policy makers at EU, national, regional, local level

<p>Scope of exploitation</p>	<p>Non-commercial</p>
<p>Means of exploitation</p>	<p>The exploitation of the KER derived from the diffusion of knowledge related to various sources such as factsheets and reports, research projects, policy guidelines, business model blueprints, practice abstracts and initiatives related to bio-based solutions for rural areas.</p> <p>Scientific exploitation is related to a comprehensive set of tools designed to support research and innovation within the rural bioeconomy sector. These tools include standardized data collection templates and guidelines that enable researchers to gather consistent and high-quality data across different projects and regions. The repository of best practice case studies serves as a valuable resource for identifying successful strategies and lessons learned, fostering knowledge sharing. Additionally, policy and strategy frameworks assist in developing and evaluating regional and national initiatives, while stakeholder engagement resources enable effective collaboration among researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders. Together, these tools enhance research efficiency, improve data quality, support evidence-based decision-making, and promote cross-sector collaboration, making the toolkit a vital resource for advancing scientific understanding and innovation in rural bioeconomy.</p> <p>Policy making exploitation: BioRural Policy Briefs serve as a vital resource for policy making by providing evidence-based, targeted recommendations to support national and EU decision-makers in advancing the circular bioeconomy. Rooted in comprehensive data and insights gathered from BioRural activities, these briefs identify existing policy gaps through a triangulated approach that compares grassroots needs, institutional frameworks, and the readiness of solutions. This approach ensures that policy actions are well-informed and aligned with actual regional and sectoral needs. Moreover, the briefs equip policymakers and rural stakeholders with practical tools and strategic guidance to develop more effective, inclusive, and sustainable policies, ultimately fostering a stronger, more resilient rural bioeconomy across Europe.</p> <p>Training exploitation: The BioRural Toolkit offers a range of online tutorials designed to facilitate training and capacity-building for users across diverse stakeholder groups. These tutorials provide step-by-step guidance on how to effectively utilize the toolkit's features, including data collection, analysis, and visualization tools, as well as best practices for implementing sustainable bioeconomy activities. By offering accessible, practical, and easy-to-follow training resources, the tutorials enable users—such as researchers, policymakers, and rural stakeholders—to enhance their skills, improve their understanding of bioeconomy concepts, and apply digital tools more effectively in their work. This makes the toolkit a powerful instrument for capacity development, knowledge dissemination, and fostering technical expertise within the rural bioeconomy community.</p>

Toolkit - Achievement until M36

BioRural toolkit aims to enable networking of stakeholders, knowledge sharing of bioeconomy as well as business models, and will support post-project sustainability.

The BioRural toolkit has **568 registered members**. Those stakeholders represent: Private company/self-employed (256 members), Associations, clusters, NGOs (83 members), Research and education (153 members), Government and public administrations (30 members), Other (37 members). They are interested in themes regarding Bioenergy (294 members), Forestry/natural habitat (206 members), Food/agriculture (392 members), Biomaterials (264 members), Aquatic/water systems (125 members).

Table 22: Business models - Key Exploitable Result

KER name: Bio-based business models	
Partners contributing to its development	All partners
Description of the KER	<p>Business model blueprints for each of the 5 selected Bioeconomy themes have been developed to support the development of successful bio-economy businesses for future innovative bio-based rural regions. D.5.6 represents a highly reusable set of tools and methods that can accelerate the adoption of circular business models in rural communities in a tangible way.</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> </div>
Unique Value Proposition	Tailored to the Bioeconomy domain business models, designed to match the specific needs of rural stakeholders, while incorporating critical technology, business and societal aspects.
Target groups	Innovators, Rural areas' actors (e.g., farmers, foresters), Policy makers at EU, national, regional, local level
Scope of exploitation	Commercial
Means of exploitation	<p>The business model blueprints are publicly available through the BioRural Toolkit and will assist stakeholders in forming their individual circular business models with the support of the business experts of the consortium.</p> <p>Commercial exploitation: The blueprints allow stakeholders to produce either regional Bioeconomy development models with emphasis on the specific bio-based solutions suitable for the local environment or private business plans for new ideas (from inception) and existing solutions (at any stage) that require a Bioeconomy upgrade.</p>

Business Models Blueprints and Tools - Achievement until M36

Deliverable, "D5.6 Business Models Blueprints and Tools," offers a framework and practical tools designed to support the creation of sustainable bio-based businesses across BioRural's five key themes: Aquatic/water systems, Bioenergy, Biomaterials, Food/agriculture, and Forest/natural environments.

By providing essential knowledge on Business Models (BMs) and Market Analysis (MA), the deliverable equips entrepreneurs with the skills to develop robust and viable business plans. It explores various BM types, with an emphasis on circular and bioeconomy-specific models and presents crucial market analysis tools like Porter's Five Forces and SWOT.

The deliverable's focus on the Triple Layered Business Model Canvas (TLBMC) is particularly important for exploitation. The TLBMC allows for a holistic assessment of business models, considering not only economic viability but also environmental and social impacts. The resulting business model blueprints, tailored to each of BioRural's five themes, are a key output of this deliverable and offer significant potential for exploitation. These blueprints provide concrete, actionable roadmaps for entrepreneurs seeking to develop sustainable bioeconomy ventures. They can be used:

- Directly by entrepreneurs to create and refine their business plans.
- By investors to evaluate the potential of bioeconomy startups.
- By policymakers to inform the development of supportive policies and funding programs.
- As a template or framework for developing business models in other bioeconomy sectors or regions.

Table 23: Policy Guidelines - Key Exploitable Result

KER name: Policy Guidelines	
Partners contributing to its development	All partners
Description of the KER	Guidelines on: (i) interactive and multi-actor innovation processes specific to bio-based solutions for rural areas; (ii) new funding formats enhancing innovation-driven research about bio-based solutions; (iii) future research; iv) topics of interest for the nationals and EU research agendas (including further HE programming); (v) fostering a better targeted and shared research agenda on innovation-driven research and multi-actor projects.
Unique Value Proposition	Supporting Bioeconomy development, considering the selected themes and involved regions' specificities. Legislative barriers will be mitigated by developing policy guidelines that feedback into the development of the circular rural Bioeconomy.
Target groups	Policy makers, National & regional government officials
Scope of exploitation	Non-commercial
Means of exploitation	The policy guidelines are publicly available through the BioRural Toolkit. Policy making exploitation: Policy guidelines will consist of research and policy recommendations and produce crisp and focused policy briefs with key messages easily and quickly grasped by the target groups. EU, regional and national policy makers can utilise the project's policy

	<p>guidelines, enhancing the development of evidence-based Bioeconomy policies.</p>
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Policy Guidelines - Achievement until M36

Building on the full breadth of project results, BioRural has developed a comprehensive set of 23 policy briefs to support and accelerate the transition to a circular bioeconomy. These are presented in Deliverable 3.5 and are publicly accessible via the BioRural Toolkit. The collection includes 12 horizontal briefs addressing cross-cutting challenges and opportunities across the entire bioeconomy, as well as 11 specific briefs that provide targeted recommendations for particular sectors and value chain stages.

The topics covered range from enabling frameworks for smart farming, circular business models, and modular biorefineries, to the promotion of bioenergy villages and better integration of urban-rural biomass flows. System-level recommendations address the alignment of funding, governance, and regulatory instruments such as the Waste Framework Directive. In addition, BioRural has co-authored a joint policy brief with the three other Horizon Europe projects funded under the same topic, offering consolidated insights from across the EU bioeconomy landscape. Together, these outputs provide policy makers with a robust, stakeholder-informed foundation for accelerating the circular transition.

Table 24: Identified KERs & involved partners

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)		Partners involved in KERs exploitation																		
		P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	P17	P18	P19
1	European Rural Bioeconomy Network	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2	Toolkit	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
3	Business model blueprints	✓	✓	✓	✓						✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
4	Policy Guidelines	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

All BioRural’s currently identified KERs are openly accessible and available free of charge beyond the project’s lifetime. With the project’s completion the BioRural Toolkit and ERBN will be further developed by all partners ensuring the reuse of assets by the Bioeconomy community. In particular, the further development of the **BioRural Toolkit** and enrichment with relevant Bioeconomy data including scientific research, projects and initiatives, success stories and funding opportunities, will be undertaken mainly by the scientific partners. In this light, it will become freely and openly available through a vast network of relevant stakeholders and the general public. The benefits are twofold: a) ensure that key stakeholders and end-users have continuous access to the platform and its innovative tools and b) get immediate access to new validated data that will continuously populate the Toolkit.

The post project sustainability of the **BioRural network** beyond EC funding will be addressed thoroughly in a comprehensive **Sustainability plan (D5.3 in M36)** addresses the following key aspects of network’s modus operandi, namely:

- i. Institutional plan:** The ERBN's future is ensured by the Horizon Europe project "thERBN," granting legitimacy and funding until 2027. Led by Ghent University, the project builds on BioRural's foundation. A key goal is to establish a permanent, post-2027 legal and financial structure for the ERBN;
- ii. Organisational plan:** The ERBN's 2025-2027 plan focuses on three key areas guided by the BioRural project's strategic lines: addressing end-user needs through demand-driven content and active community management, integrating into the wider European knowledge ecosystem by partnering with platforms like EU-Farmbook and establishing relationships with AKIS bodies and EU institutions, and expanding the network's reach and solidifying its brand by collaborating with the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance and transitioning to the permanent ERBN identity;
- iii. Financial plan:** The financial viability of the ERBN for the crucial 2025-2027 transition period is secured by BioRural partners who will cover the expenses for sustaining the BioRural website and the toolkit for at least 7 years after project’s completion. Moreover, thERBN Horizon Europe project, with a budget of nearly €3 million, could potentially cover operational activities outlined in the institutional and organisational plans, including the refinement of the platform, community management, content creation, and partner coordination.

Identification of new KERs- project procedure

The identification of new Key Exploitable Results (KERs) process was established from the project's onset. However, despite this effort, no additional KERs were identified during project implementation.

The procedure and designed steps are presented in the figure below for reference purposes, showcasing the established methodology even though it didn't lead to the discovery of new KERs in this instance.

Inclusion of newly identified KERs

Figure 70: Newly identified KERs procedure

The first step towards the identification of a KER by a partner is for the latter to inform the Coordinator and WP5 leader providing a detailed explanation of the exploitability potential of the identified result by making sure it aligns with the project exploitation plan. Specific analysis needs to be made covering the following aspects:

- Scope of exploitation
- Target groups (to whom)
- Means of exploitation (how)

A relevant form has been developed and shared with the partners during DEC preparation (Annex I).

Once this step is concluded, the above-mentioned form is sent to the consortium and partners are asked to validate the new KER. Comments and suggestions of the partners are recorded while possible objections are discussed and addressed. Finally, after the new KER is validated, it is included in the project's KERs list mentioned in Table 23.

5.2 IPR strategy

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are the ownership rights for creations of the mind, such as inventions, names, images, or designs and can enable owners to obtain financial benefit from their ideas. Striking the right balance between creator and public interests can foster creativity and innovation.

5.2.1 Types of IPR⁵

The standard forms of IPR protection include:

⁵ World Intellectual Property Organization. "What is Intellectual Property?" <https://www.wipo.int/about-ip/en/>.

- **Patent:** an exclusive right granted for an invention. It allows the owner to decide how and whether the invention can be used by others
- **Trademark:** a sign that distinguishes goods and services of one enterprise from those of another
- **Industrial design:** includes the aesthetic aspect of an object. 2D features can include patterns, lines, and colours, whereas 3D features extend to shape and surface
- **Copyright:** is the legal term to describe the rights over literary and artistic work but can also extend to databases, advertisement, maps, and technical drawings
- **Trade-secret:** commercially valuable confidential information which may be sold or licensed. This can include technical or nontechnical data, formulas, patterns, methods, lists of customers
- **Confidentiality:** information that is not publicly known and warrants protection

The choice of the most suitable form will be based upon the specifications of the activity and its results.

BioRural handled IPR Management on a two-level approach:

During the project: BioRural gave emphasis to the protection of IPRs derived from the project implementation, ensuring that any IPR generated shall rest with the industry that created it and can further exploit it commercially. Under this framework, a set of both protective and supportive measures (such as the obligation to sign Non-Disclosure Agreements) was considered by the consortium to create confidence in all participants. Knowledge Management and democratisation of scientific knowledge: The consortium published the overall project results through publications, seminars and in the project website, without charging intellectual property rights.

Post-Project IPR Strategy: The pre-identified and newly generated IPRs can and will be protected. However, given that BioRural is aiming to support the rural areas, the BioRural Toolkit was licensed under a copyleft license GNU General Public License (GPLv3). The GNU GPLv3 is a free software license that guarantees users the freedom to run, study, share, and modify software. It strengthens protections against practices that restrict user rights, such as hardware “tivoization,” and includes explicit terms for license compatibility and patent protection. By ensuring that derivative works remain under the same license, GPLv3 promotes software freedom, collaboration, and long-term sustainability of open-source projects.

The following table presents the IPRs of the four KERs as they were identified by the partners during DEC preparation.

Table 25: BioRural KERs & linked IPRs

KERs		Linked IPRs to the KERs
1	European Rural Bioeconomy Network	no IPR
2	Toolkit	Copyleft
3	Business model blueprints	no IPR
4	Policy Guidelines	no IPR

Identification of new IPRs- project procedure

A process for identifying new Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) was designed and implemented from the project's beginning. However, throughout the project's duration, no new IPRs were identified. The

Inclusion of newly identified IPRs

Figure 71: Newly identified IPRs procedure

established process, while not resulting in the creation of new IPRs in this specific case, demonstrates a proactive approach to intellectual property management throughout the project lifecycle.:

The identification of new IPRs is closely related to the identification process of KERs described above. In that way, when a new KER is identified, the partner follows the same procedure by informing the Coordinator and the WP5 leader on the relative IPR that is linked to the KER as presented in Annex I.

Following, the partners are asked to validate the new IPR. Comments and suggestions of the partners are recorded while possible objections are discussed and addressed. Finally, after the new IPR is validated, it is included in the project's IPR list.

5.2.2 Partner obligations

BioRural followed all IPR management requirements described in the Grant Agreement as well as the signed Consortium Agreement.

Access rights

The beneficiaries must give each other, and the other participants access to the background identified as needed for implementing the action, subject to any specific rules in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement.

'Background' means any **data, know-how or information** — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights — that is:

- held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement and
- needed to implement the action or exploit the results.

If background is subject to rights of a third party, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it is able to comply with its obligations under the Grant Agreement.

According to the Consortium Agreement and specifically Article 9, the Parties have identified and agreed on the Background for the Project and have also, where relevant, informed each other that Access to specific Background is subject to legal restrictions or limits.

Results and ownership

'Results' means any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights

Joint ownership is governed by Grant Agreement Article 16.2 and its Annex 5, Section Ownership of results, with the following additions:

Unless otherwise agreed:

- each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned Results for non-commercial research and teaching activities including but not limited to research contracts in national and European funded projects with third parties provided it does not lead to any commercial or monetary benefit to third parties involved in such cooperative research project on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s).
- each of the joint owners shall be entitled to otherwise Exploit the jointly owned Results and to grant non-exclusive licences to third parties (without any right to sub-license) if the other joint owners are given: (a) at least 45 calendar days advance notice; and (b) fair and reasonable compensation.

The **granting authority** has the right to use non-sensitive information relating to the action and materials and documents received from the beneficiaries (notably summaries for publication, deliverables, as well as any other material, such as pictures or audio-visual material, in paper or electronic form) for policy, information, communication, dissemination and publicity purposes —during the action or afterwards.

The right to use the beneficiaries' materials, documents and information is granted in the form of a royalty-free, non-exclusive, and irrevocable licence, which includes the following rights:

- i. use for its own purposes (in particular, making them available to persons working for the granting authority or any other EU service (including institutions, bodies, offices, agencies, etc.) or EU Member State institution or body; copying or reproducing them in whole or in part, in unlimited numbers; and communication through press information services)
- ii. distribution to the public (in particular, publication as hard copies and in electronic or digital format, publication on the internet, as a downloadable or non-downloadable file, broadcasting by any channel, public display, or presentation, communicating through press information services, or inclusion in widely accessible databases or indexes)
- iii. editing or redrafting (including shortening, summarising, inserting other elements (e.g., meta-data, legends, other graphic, visual, audio or text elements), extracting parts (e.g., audio or video files), dividing into parts, use in a compilation)
- iv. translation
- v. storage in paper, electronic or other form
- vi. archiving, in line with applicable document-management rules
- vii. the right to authorise third parties to act on its behalf or sub-license to third parties the modes of use set out in Points (b), (c), (d) and (f), if needed for the information, communication and publicity activity of the granting authority

If materials or documents are subject to moral rights or third-party rights (including intellectual property rights or rights of natural persons on their image and voice), the beneficiaries must ensure that they comply with their obligations under this Agreement (in particular, by obtaining the necessary licences and authorisations from the rights holders concerned).

The Sustainability plan (D5.3) will include a Results ownership list as per the periodic reporting requirements of the Grant Agreement.

Transfer of results

According to the Consortium Agreement, each Party may transfer ownership of its own Results, including its share in jointly owned Results, following the procedures outlined in the Grant Agreement.

In the case of ownership transfer to the third party, the third party must be identified in Attachment (3) of the Consortium Agreement and the other Parties must waive their right to prior notice and to object to such a transfer to listed third parties according to the Grant Agreement.

The transferring Party must inform the other Parties at the time of transfer and will ensure the rights of other Parties are not affected by such a transfer. Any addition to Attachment (3) after signing the Consortium Agreement requires a decision of the General Assembly.

Access Rights to Results

Access Rights to Results if needed for exploitation of a Party's own Results shall be granted on Fair and Reasonable conditions and upon written bilateral agreement.

A request for Access Rights may be made up to twelve months after the end of the Project or after the termination of the requesting Party's participation in the Project.

For the avoidance of doubt any grant of Access Rights not covered by the Grant Agreement or the Consortium Agreement shall be at the absolute discretion of the owning Party and subject to such terms and conditions as may be agreed between the owning and receiving Parties.

Dissemination of Results

During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, the dissemination of partner's own results such as publications and presentations, shall be governed by the Grant Agreement.

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the publication.

Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice.

If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

An objection is justified if the intended publication:

- 1) would prevent patenting or other protection of the objecting Party's Results or Background with registrable intellectual property rights or
- 2) includes Background, unpublished solely owned Results or Confidential Information of the objecting Party. The objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications.

In addition, the unpublished results or background of any partner will not be used for dissemination purposes without obtaining the owning Party's prior written approval.

Access rights for software adhere to the same rules as described above. Access rights do not include source or object code ported to a certain hardware platform or software documentation beyond what is available from the party granting the access rights. The **BioRural Toolkit** will be licensed under a copyleft licence (e.g., GPLv3, AGPL), mandating the open distribution of the source code, ensuring freedom of use, and encouraging further knowledge sharing.

Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary **breaches any of the obligations** of the Grant Agreement (Section 2), the **grant may be reduced**.

Non-disclosure of information

D5.3 Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

All information in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Party (the “Disclosing Party”) to any other Party (the “Recipient”) in connection with the Project during its implementation and which has been explicitly marked as “confidential” at the time of disclosure, or when disclosed orally and has been confirmed and designated in writing within 15 calendar days from oral disclosure at the latest as confidential information by the Disclosing Party, is “Confidential Information”.

The Recipients hereby undertake in addition and without prejudice to any commitment on non-disclosure under the Grant Agreement, for a period of 5 years after the end of the Project:

- a) not to use Confidential Information otherwise than for the purpose for which it was disclosed;
- b) not to disclose Confidential Information without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party;
- c) to ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis; and
- d) to return to the Disclosing Party, or destroy, on request all Confidential Information that has been disclosed to the Recipients including all copies thereof and to delete all information stored in a machine-readable form to the extent practically possible. The Recipients may keep a copy to the extent it is required to keep, archive or store such Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable laws and regulations or for the proof of on-going obligations provided that the Recipient complies with the confidentiality obligations herein contained with respect to such copy.

The Recipient shall apply the same degree of care with regard to the Confidential Information disclosed within the scope of the Project as with its own confidential and/or proprietary information, but in no case less than reasonable care.

6 Conclusion

This Deliverable (D5.3) has outlined the comprehensive Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) strategy implemented by the BioRural project. The final update focuses on diffusing information and knowledge generated by the ERBN, the 4 RBNs, the BioRural Toolkit, regional workshops, and the online call, as well as the continuous communication and dissemination efforts of the project partners. This plan, initiated with a clear understanding of the challenges within the European rural bioeconomy (1.1.1), established a framework for impactful knowledge sharing and stakeholder engagement. Through a multi-actor approach (2.3) and a focus on key target groups (2.4), BioRural has leveraged a diverse range of channels, tools, and activities (Chapter 3) to maximize its reach.

This document covers a wide range of key activities and their timelines, all designed to meet dissemination, communication, and exploitation targets. All partners have been actively involved in communicating and disseminating BioRural's outputs to ensure proper exploitation of project outcomes and maximize impact.

The project established a strong visual identity (3.1) and strategically utilized a mix of digital and traditional outreach methods (3.2) including an active website (3.2.1), targeted digital campaigns (3.2.2), and multiplier events (3.2.3). It also focused on fostering synergies with related initiatives (3.2.5) and leveraging EC tools (3.2.6) for wider dissemination.

Continuous monitoring and evaluation (Chapter 4) through defined KPIs allowed for adaptive management. BioRural has successfully pursued identified exploitation pathways (5.1) while also addressing IPR considerations (5.2), establishing a foundation for the long-term impact and sustainability of the project's results.

Through the activities and processes described in this report, BioRural has worked to accelerate the integration of circular bio-based solutions in European rural areas, establishing a network and providing resources that will continue to be valuable beyond the project's lifetime.

Annex A: Logo variations

Annex B: BioRural's covers

Annex C: Dissemination and Communication material

BioRural brochure: English version and translations in partners' languages

Brochure sides A&B [English]

Expected results

- 1 European Rural Bioeconomy Network
- 4 Regional Bioeconomy Platforms
- 20 Rural Bioeconomy Success Stories
- 42 Capacity building workshops
- 4 Regional workshops
- 1 European Bioeconomy Challenge
- 440 Interviews with end users/experts
- 5 Knowledge exchange workshops
- 5 Bioeconomy business models
- Policy recommendations
- >400 Bioeconomy material
- Filmed workshops
- 8 Success stories videos
- Integration with EU's knowledge centre for Bioeconomy

Connecting the dots to **UNLOCK THE POTENTIAL** of European rural areas towards circular **BIOECONOMY**

Register to BioRural's Bioeconomy platform to join European BioEconomy networks!

bio ruraleu

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A Horizon Europe Project
1 September 2022 - 31 August 2025

Introduction

"The bioeconomy means using renewable biological resources, like crops, forests, fish, animals and micro-organisms to produce food, materials and energy" (EC) and a thriving bioeconomy is key to creating a circular European economy

Challenges

- Our economies are based on linear production systems using non-renewable resources
- Rural areas face acute demographic, poverty and climate challenges
- Rural bioeconomy knowledge and technology transfer is not adequately supported

...but opportunities exist

- Circular Bioeconomy solutions and networks exist
- Increased policy, research and innovation support for a circular Bioeconomy
- New bio-based innovations are consistently supporting the transition to a circular economy

Objective

"BioRural's goal is to create a European Rural Bioeconomy Network to promote small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas and to increase the share of the Bioeconomy"

Specific Objectives

- Evaluate the current status of the European Bioeconomy
- Identify factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions
- Create a European rural Bioeconomy network
- Assess and promote bio-based solutions in rural areas
- Facilitate knowledge exchange and capacity building for the rural Bioeconomy
- Develop and continuously optimise an online open stakeholders' tool (BioRural Toolkit)
- Create rural development blueprints for Bioeconomy businesses from conception to scale

Approach

BioRural is centered on three pillars that feed into a publicly available BioRural Toolkit

Pillars

Pillar 1: Knowledge

- Information gap analysis
- Knowledge exchange workshops
- BioRural Toolkit

Pillar 2: Network

- 4 regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms
- Circular success stories
- Synergies with previous and ongoing innovative bio-economy projects
- Capacity building and regional workshops, Bioeconomy challenge

Pillar 3: Business Models

- Business model blueprints for each theme
- Post-project sustainability

Brochure sides A&B [French]

Résultats attendus

- 1 Réseau européen de la bioéconomie
- 4 Plateformes suivant un découpage par zone géographique européennes
- 20 études de cas mise en ligne de bioéconomie rurale
- 42 Ateliers de renforcement des capacités
- 4 Ateliers à échelle de zone
- 1 Événement européen avec challenge sur la bioéconomie
- 440 Interviews d'utilisateurs/experts
- 5 Ateliers d'échanges de connaissances
- 5 Business Modèles pour la bioéconomie
- Recommandations politiques
- +400 Ressources sur la bioéconomie
- Ateliers enregistrés
- 8 Success Story vidéos
- Intégration avec le centre de connaissances de l'UE sur la bioéconomie

→ Inscrivez-vous sur la plateforme bioéconomie de BioRural pour rejoindre le réseau européen de la bioéconomie!

biorural.eu

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[youtube](#) BioRural channel

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Accélérer la mise en place de solutions circulaires et biosourcées au sein des zones rurales européennes

Connecter les acteurs pour

LIBÉRER LE POTENTIEL

des zones rurales européennes vers la

BIOÉCONOMIE CIRCULAIRE

Un projet Horizon Europe
1^{er} Septembre 2022 - 31 Août 2025

Financé par l'Union européenne

Introduction

La bioéconomie consiste à utiliser des ressources biologiques, renouvelables, comme les cultures, les forêts, les poissons, les animaux et les micro-organismes, pour produire des aliments, des matériaux et de l'énergie" (CE) et une bioéconomie prospère est essentielle à la création d'une économie européenne circulaire.

Challenges

- Nos économies sont fondées sur des systèmes de production linéaires utilisant des ressources non renouvelables
- Les zones rurales sont confrontées à de graves changements démographiques, de pauvreté et climatiques
- Les connaissances de la bioéconomie rurale et le transfert de technologies ne sont pas soutenus de manière adéquate

...mais des opportunités existent

- Des solutions de bioéconomie circulaires et des réseaux existent
- Un soutien accru aux politiques, à la recherche et à l'innovation pour une bioéconomie circulaire
- De nouvelles innovations biosourcées soutiennent en permanence la transition vers une économie circulaire

Objectifs

"L'objectif du projet BioRural est de créer un réseau paneuropéen de bioéconomie rurale afin de promouvoir des solutions biosourcées à petite échelle dans les zones rurales et d'accroître la part de la bioéconomie."

Objectifs spécifiques

- Évaluer le statut actuel de la bioéconomie européenne
- Identifier les facteurs affectant l'adoption et la diffusion des solutions biosourcées
- Créer un réseau européen de la bioéconomie rurale
- Faciliter l'échange de connaissances et le renforcement des capacités pour la bioéconomie rurale
- Développer et optimiser continuellement un outil en ligne ouvert aux parties prenantes
- Créer des plans de développement ruraux pour les entreprises de la bioéconomie, de la conception à la mise à l'échelle

Approche

Le projet BioRural repose sur une boîte à outils qui se décline en 3 piliers

Piliers

Pilier 1: Connaissance

- Analyse des lacunes en matière d'information
- Ateliers d'échange de connaissances
- Boîte à outils BioRural

Pilier 2: Réseauage

- 4 plateformes régionales de bioéconomie
- Success Stories
- Synergies avec les projets de bioéconomie innovants précédents et en cours
- Renforcement des capacités et ateliers régionaux, défi de la bioéconomie

Pilier 3: Business Modèles

- Business Modèles pour chaque thématique
- Durabilité post-projet

Brochure sides A&B [Italian]

Risultati attesi

- 1 Network europeo per la bioeconomia
- 4 piattaforme regionali
- 20 Casi reali virtuosi, documentati e condivisi
- 42 workshop di formazione e condivisione
- 4 Workshop internazionali nelle macro-aree
- 1 Contest europeo per start-up e innovazioni

- 440 Interviste con utenti ed esperti
- 5 workshop di condivisione delle informazioni
- 5 modelli di business raccomandazioni ai legislatori

- >400 contenuti informativi e video
- 8 video di storie di successo
- Integrazione con l'EU's knowledge centre for Bioeconomy

Stimolare l'integrazione delle soluzioni bio-based nell'economia circolare delle aree rurali europee

Creare le condizioni per **RIMUOVERE GLI OSTACOLI** Allo sviluppo sostenibile della **BIOECONOMIA** Nelle aree rurali europee

Registrati alla piattaforma BioRural per iscriverti al network!

biorural.eu

in: biorural, @bio_rural, bioruralu, BioRural, BioRural channel

Contatti: **Diego Rossi** (Coordinatore Italiano, rossidie@cia.it), **Giulia Rudello** (Supporto tecnico, rudello.giulia@cia.it)

Progetto Horizon Europe 1 settembre 2022 - 31 agosto 2025

Finanziato dall'Unione europea

Introduzione

"Economia che usa le risorse biologiche rinnovabili di prima e di seconda generazione, provenienti dalla terra e dal mare come materiale per la produzione energetica, industriale, alimentare e mangimistica" (CE) e un sistema di valorizzazione delle risorse biologiche in salute è la chiave per consentire lo sviluppo dell'economia circolare in Europa.

Obiettivi

L'obiettivo di BioRural è quello di creare un network europeo che promuova soluzioni per la valorizzazione della bioeconomia su piccola scala, per far crescere il ruolo della bioeconomia nelle aree rurali"

Approccio

BioRural si focalizza su 3 pilastri che convergono in uno strumento gratuito: il BioRural Toolkit

Sfide

- La nostra economia si basa su modelli lineari di utilizzo di risorse non rinnovabili
- Le aree rurali devono confrontarsi con povertà, spopolamento e cambiamenti climatici
- Il trasferimento delle conoscenze e delle tecnologie, in ambito bio-based, è lento e complesso

...ma esistono delle opportunità

- Le soluzioni tecnologiche e i modelli sono spesso già state sviluppate
- Le politiche, la ricerca e l'innovazione sono fortemente indirizzate verso un'economia circolare
- Le moderne soluzioni bio-based offrono anche un vantaggio nella transizione verso un'economia circolare

Obiettivi specifici

- Valutare lo stato attuale della bioeconomia in Europa
- Identificare i fattori che influenzano l'adozione e la diffusione della bioeconomia nelle aree rurali
- Facilitare la condivisione delle conoscenze e la formazione per creare le professionalità nelle aree rurali
- Sviluppo e ottimizzazione di una piattaforma online per gli stakeholder
- Creazione di progetti di business per la bioeconomia dall'ideazione all'applicazione reale

Pilastri

- Pilastro 1: Informazioni**
 - Analisi delle lacune
 - Organizzazione di workshop informativi
 - BioRural Toolkit
- Pilastro 2: Network**
 - 4 piattaforme regionali
 - Casi virtuosi di bioeconomia circolare
 - Sinergie con progetti, focalizzati su innovazioni nella bioeconomia, conclusi e in corso
 - Formazione, workshop territoriali e contest europei
- Pilastro 3: Business models**
 - Progetti di modelli reali per i principali temi della bioeconomia
 - Valutazione della sostenibilità post-progetto

Brochure sides A&B [Portuguese]

Resultados esperados

- 1 Rede Europeia de Bioeconomia Rural
- 4 Plataformas Regionais de Bioeconomia
- 20 Histórias de Sucesso sobre Bioeconomia Rural
- 42 Ações de formação
- 4 Workshops regionais
- 1 Concurso Europeu de Bioeconomia
- 440 Entrevistas com potenciais beneficiários / especialistas
- 5 Ações de divulgação
- 5 Modelos de negócios na área da Bioeconomia
- Recomendações de políticas
- >400 materiais sobre Bioeconomia
- Ações de formação gravadas
- 8 vídeos de histórias de sucesso
- Integração com os centros de conhecimento da UE na área da Bioeconomia

Registre-se na Plataforma do Biorural para aderir às Redes Europeias de Bioeconomia!

bioruraleu

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Apoiando a integração de soluções circulares de base biotecnológica nas áreas rurais da Europa

Ligando os pontos para **DESBLOQUEAR O POTENCIAL** das zonas rurais da Europa

rumo à **BIOECONOMIA CIRCULAR**

Um projeto Horizonte Europa
1 de setembro de 2022 - 31 de agosto de 2025

Financiado pela União Europeia

Introdução

"A bioeconomia significa usar recursos biológicos renováveis, como colheitas, florestas, peixes, animais e microrganismos para produzir alimentos, materiais e energia" e uma bioeconomia próspera é a chave para criar uma economia circular na Europa

Desafios

- Nossas economias são baseadas em sistemas de produção lineares usando recursos não renováveis
- As zonas rurais enfrentam graves desafios demográficos, de pobreza e climáticos
- Conhecimento da bioeconomia rural e a transferência de tecnologia não são adequadamente apoiados

...Mas as oportunidades existem

- Existem soluções e redes de Bioeconomia Circular
- Maior apoio a políticas, pesquisa e inovação para uma Bioeconomia circular
- Novas inovações de base biológica estão apoiando consistentemente a transição para uma economia circular

Objetivo

"O objetivo da BioRural é criar uma Rede Europeia de Bioeconomia Rural para promover soluções de base biológica de pequena escala em áreas rurais e expandir o mercado da Bioeconomia"

Specific Objectives

- Evaluate the current status of the European Bioeconomy
- Identify factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions
- Create a European rural Bioeconomy network
- Assess and promote bio-based solutions in rural areas
- Facilitate knowledge exchange and capacity building for the rural Bioeconomy
- Develop and continuously optimise an online open stakeholders' tool (BioRural Toolkit)
- Create rural development blueprints for Bioeconomy businesses from conception to scale

Metodologia

O BioRural está apoiado em três pilares que suportam o Conjunto de Ferramentas BioRural, disponível para utilização pública de forma aberta

Pilares

Pilar 1: Conhecimento

- Análise de lacunas de informação
- Ações de divulgação
- Conjunto de Ferramentas BioRural

Pilar 2: Rede de Partilha

- 4 Plataformas Regionais de Bioeconomia Rural
- Histórias de sucesso sobre economia circular
- Sinergias com projetos de Bioeconomia inovadores, passados e em curso
- Ações de formação e workshops regionais
- Concurso Europeu sobre Bioeconomia

Pilar 3: Modelos de Negócios

- Modelos de planos de negócios específicos para cada tema
- Continuidade dos meios de suporte no pós-projeto

Brochure sides A&B [Macedonian]

Очекувани резултати

- 1 Европска Мрежа за Рурална Биоeкономија
- 4 Регионални Платформи за Биоeкономија
- 20 Успешни Приказни од Руралната Биоeкономија
- 42 работилници за зајакнување на капацитетите
- 4 Регионални работилници
- 1 Предизвик на Европската Биоeкономија
- 440 Интервјуа со корисници/експерти
- 5 Работилници за размена на знаења
- 5 Бизнес модели за Биоeкономија
- Препораки за политики
- > 400 Информативни материјали за Биоeкономијата
- Сиверни работилници
- 8 видео за успешни приказни
- Интеграција во центарот за знаења за Биоeкономијата на EУ

Забрзана интеграција на циркуларни био-базирани решенија во руралните региони во Европа

Поврзување на клучните точки за

ОТКЛУЧУВАЊЕ НА ПОТЕНЦИЈАЛОТ

На руралните региони во Европа

на патот кон циркуларна БИОЕКОНОМИЈА

Регистрирајте се на платформата за Биоeкономија на БиоРурал за да се вклучите во Европските мрежи за Биоeкономија!

[biorural.eu](https://www.biorural.eu)

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Проект од програмата Хоризонт Европа
1 Септември 2023 – 31 Август 2025

Финансирано од Европската Унија

Вовед

„Биоекономијата подразбира примена на обновливи биолошки ресурси како што се земјоделски култури, шумариба, животни и микроорганизми со цел производство на храна, материјали и енергија“ (Европска Комисија) и развистата биоeкономија е клучна во создавањето на циркуларна економија во Европа

Предизвици

- Нашите економии се базирани на линеарни производствени системи кои користат необновливи навори
- Руралните средини се соочуваат со акутни предизвици (демографски промени, сиромаштија и климатски промени)
- Знаењата за руралната биоeкономија и трансферот на технологија не се соодветно поддржани

...но постојат можности

- Постојат мрежи и решенија за Циркуларната Биоeкономија
- Зголечена поддршка за политиките, истражувањата и иновациите за циркуларната Биоeкономија
- Новите био-базирани решенија континуирано ја поддржуваат транзицијата кон циркуларната економија

Цел

Целта на БиоРурал е формирање на Европска Мрежа на Рурална Биоeкономија за промоција на био-базирани решенија од мал обем во руралните региони и зголемување на уделот на Биоeкономијата

Специфични цели:

- Евалуација на моменталната состојба на Европската Биоeкономија
- Идентификација на факторите кои влијаат врз иновацијата, примената и дифузијата на био-базирани решенија
- Создавање на Европска Мрежа за Рурална Биоeкономија
- Проценка и промоција на био-базирани решенија во руралните области
- Овозможување на размена на знаења и градење на капацитети за руралната биоeкономија
- Развој и континуирана оптимизација на отворена дигитална алатка наменета за сите членови (Збир на алатки на БиоРурал)
- Креирање на насоки и модели за развој на бизнис во биоeкономијата во руралните области од концепт до целосна реализација

Пристап

БиоРурал е поставен на три столба кои допринесуваат во јасно достапен збир на алатки на Био Рурал

Столбови

Столб 1: Знаења

- Анализи на недостатоците на информации
- Работилници за размена на знаења
- Збир на алатки на БиоРурал

Столб 2: Вирежување

- 4 Регионални Платформи на Рурална Биоeкономија
- Успешни приказни за циркуларноста
- Сиверни со завршени и тековни иновативни проекти во биоeкономијата

Столб 3: Бизнес модели

- Бизнес модели за секоја област
- Одржливост по завршување на проектот

Brochure sides A&B [Greek]

Αναμενόμενα αποτελέσματα

- 1 Ευρωπαϊκό δίκτυο αγροτικής Βιοοικονομίας
- 4 Περιφερειακές πλατφόρμες Βιοοικονομίας
- 20 Επιλεγμένα παραδείγματα αγροτικής Βιοοικονομίας
- 42 Εργαστήρια ανάπτυξης καινοτομιών
- 4 Περιφερειακά εργαστήρια
- 1 Ευρωπαϊκές Διαγωνισμός Βιοοικονομίας

- 440 συνεντεύξεις με τελικούς χρήστες/ιδιοκτήτες
- 5 Εργαστήρια ανταλλαγής γνώσεων
- 5 Επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα Βιοοικονομίας Πολιτικής Συστάσεις

- >400 Υλικό σχετικά με τη Βιοοικονομία
- Μαγνητοσκοπημένα Εργαστήρια
- 8 Βίντεο επιλεγμένων επιχειρημάτων Βιοοικονομίας
- Ενσωμάτωση στο Ευρωπαϊκό Κέντρο Γνώσης Βιοοικονομίας

Επικεντρώνοντας την μετάβαση προς μια κυκλική βιοοικονομία στις αγροτικές περιοχές της Ευρώπης

Συνδέοντας τα σημεία για την **ΑΝΑΔΕΙΞΗ ΤΩΝ ΔΥΝΑΤΟΤΗΤΩΝ** των Ευρωπαϊκών αγροτικών περιοχών προς μια κυκλική **ΒΙΟΟΙΚΟΝΟΜΙΑ**

Πρόγραμμα ΟΡΘΟΝΟΜΙΑ ΕΡΕΥΝΑ 1 Ιανουαρίου 2022 - 31 Αυγούστου 2023

Με τη χρηματοδότηση της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης

→ Κάνε εγγραφή στην πλατφόρμα του Biorural για να γίνεις μέλος στα Ευρωπαϊκά δίκτυα βιοοικονομίας!

[bioruraleu](https://www.bioruraleu.com)

in biorural | @bio_rural | facebook.com/bioruraleu | Biorural | Biorural channel

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Εισαγωγή

"Βιοοικονομία σημαίνει η χρήση ανανεώσιμων βιολογικών πόρων, όπως οι καλλιέργειες, τα δέντρα, τα ζώα και οι μικροοργανισμοί για την παραγωγή τροφής, υλικών και ενέργειας" (IEE) και μια ακριβώς βιοοικονομία αποτελεί το κλαδί για την δημιουργία μιας κυκλικής Ευρωπαϊκής οικονομίας

Επιπλέον κυκλική οικονομία (πορτο, κατακόρυφο, κερσό)

Βιολογικές προϊόντων και υπηρεσιών βιολογικής προέλευσης

Βιολογικά πρώτα υλικά

Κανονισμός Βιολογικής προέλευσης

Στόχος

"Στόχος του Biorural είναι η δημιουργία ενός Ευρωπαϊκού Δικτύου Αγροτικής Βιοοικονομίας ώστε να προωθήσει εγκαταστάσεις βιοοικονομίας μικρής κλίμακας στις αγροτικές περιοχές αυτώντας το μερίδιό της βιοοικονομίας"

Ευρωπαϊκό δίκτυο Αγροτικής Βιοοικονομίας

Βόρειο-Δυτικό: Ελλάδα, Γαλλία, Πορτογαλία, Αυστρία

Βόρειο-Ανατολικό: Σλοβενία, Τσεχία, Πολωνία, Ουγγαρία, Σλοβακία, Βουλγαρία, Ρουμανία

Νότιο: Ισπανία, Πορτογαλία, Ιταλία

Προσέγγιση

Το Biorural επικεντρώνεται σε φέρις πυλώνες που τροφοδοτούν μια δημόσια διαθέσιμη εργαλειοθήκη

Γνώση

Βιολογική Καινοτομία

Επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα

Προκλήσεις

- Η οικονομία είναι δομημένη σε ένα γραμμικό σύστημα παραγωγής κρησιμοποίησης μη ανανεώσιμης πηγής
- Οι αγροτικές περιοχές αντιμετωπίζουν μια οξεία δημογραφική κρίση και κλιματικές προκλήσεις
- Η μετάβαση της γνώσης και της τεχνολογίας της αγροτικής βιοοικονομίας δεν υποστηρίζεται επαρκώς

...όμως ευκαιρίες υπάρχουν

- Υπάρχουν Κυκλικές λύσεις βιοοικονομίας και δικτύα
- Αναπτυσσόμενες πολιτικές, έρευνες και καινοτομίες που υποστηρίζουν τη βιοοικονομία
- Νέες βιολογικές προέλευσης καινοτομίες υποστηρίζουν την μετάβαση σε μια κυκλική οικονομία

Συγκεκριμένοι Στόχοι

- Αξιολόγηση της υφιστάμενης κατάστασης της Ευρωπαϊκής βιοοικονομίας
- Προσδιορισμός παραγόντων που επηρεάζουν την καινοτομία, την υιοθέτηση και τη διάδοση εγκαταστάσεων βιοοικονομίας
- Δημιουργία Ευρωπαϊκού Δικτύου βιοοικονομίας
- Αξιολόγηση και προώθηση λύσεων βιοοικονομίας στον αγροτικό τομέα
- Δευκόλυση ανταλλαγής γνώσεων και ανάπτυξης καινοτομιών για την αγροτική βιοοικονομία
- Ανάπτυξη και συνεχή βελτίωση της ανοικτής διαδικαστικής εργαλειοθήκης
- Δημιουργία προτύπων για αγροτικές επιχειρήσεις βιοοικονομίας από την σύλληψη στην μεγάλη κλίμακα

Πυλώνες

Πυλώνας 1: Γνώση

- Ανάπτυξη κάποιων πληροφοριών
- Εργαστήρια ανταλλαγής γνώσεων
- Εργαλειοθήκη Biorural

Πυλώνας 2: Δίκτυο

- 4 Περιφερειακές Πλατφόρμες Αγροτικής βιοοικονομίας
- Επιλεγμένα παραδείγματα κυκλικότητας
- Συνέργειες με προηγούμενα ή τρέχοντα πρωτοπόρα εγκαταστάσεις βιοοικονομίας
- Περιφερειακά Εργαστήρια Ανάπτυξης Καινοτομιών και Ευρωπαϊκές Διαγωνισμός βιοοικονομίας

Πυλώνας 3: Επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα

- Πρότυπα επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα για κάθε κλάδο βιοοικονομίας
- Βιωσιμότητα μετά το πέρας του έργου

Brochure sides A&B [Polish]

Oczekiwane rezultaty:

- 1 Europejska Sieć Biogospodarki działająca głównie na Obszarach Wiejskich
- 4 Regionalne Platformy Biogospodarki
- 20 Historii Sukcesu Biogospodarki na Obszarach Wiejskich
- 42 Warsztaty dla budowy potencjału
- 4 Warsztaty na poziomie regionalnym
- 1 Wyzwanie dla Europejskiej Biogospodarki
- 440 Ankietowanych ekspertów i praktyków
- 5 Warsztatów służącym wymianie wiedzy
- 5 Modeli biznesowych służących rozwojowi biogospodarki
- Zalecenia i rekomendacje prawne
- >400 Materiałów dotyczących biogospodarki
- Nagrania wideo z warsztatów
- 8 Filmów prezentujących historie sukcesu przedsiębiorstw z sektorów biogospodarki
- Materiały spójne z Unijnym Ośrodkiem Wiedzy na temat Biogospodarki

Przyspieszenie integracji bio-rozwiązań gospodarki cyrkularnej na europejskich obszarach wiejskich

którego celem jest
UWOLNIENIE POTENCJAŁU
europejskich obszarów wiejskich oraz transformacja i dążenie do **BIOGOSPODARKI O OBIEGU ZAMKNIĘTYM**

Projekt sfinansowany w ramach programu Horizon Europa 1 września 2022 - 31 sierpnia 2023

→ Zarejestruj się na platformie biogospodarki utworzonej przez BioRural i dołącz do europejskiej sieci biogospodarki!

[biorural.eu](https://www.biorural.eu)

in biorural | @bio_rural
f biorural | BioRural
a BioRural channel

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Finansowane przez Unię Europejską

Wprowadzenie

*Termin biogospodarka oznacza wykorzystywanie odnawialnych zasobów biologicznych, takich jak rośliny uprawne, lasy, ryby, zwierzęta i mikroorganizmy do produkcji żywności, materiałów i energii (KE), a obszar prosperująca biogospodarka jest kluczem do stworzenia europejskiej gospodarki o obiegu zamkniętym

Gospodarka cyrkularna w szerszym ujęciu

Przemysł i usługi oparte na biobiozobach: Biomasa, Bioproducty, Biomateriały

Biobiozobacja: Leśnictwo, żywność, rolnictwo, akwakultura

Cel projektu

"Celem projektu BioRural jest utworzenie Europejskiej Sieci Biogospodarki Obszarów Wiejskich dla promowania małoskalowych (niezawodnych) biozwiązków wdrożonych na obszarach wiejskich i zwiększenia znaczenia biogospodarki na tych terenach"

Plan działania

Projekt BioRural opiera się na trzech filarach, które składają się na ogólnodostępny Zestaw Narzędzi BioRural

Wyzwania

- Nasze gospodarki opierają się na systemach produkcji liniowej, wykorzystującej zasoby nieodnawialne
- Obszary wiejskie borykają się z problemami demograficznymi, ubóstwem i skutkami zmian klimatu
- Transfer wiedzy i technologii opartych na biogospodarkę do obszarów wiejskich nie jest wystarczająco wspierany

...oraz istniejące szanse

- Dostępne rozwiązania z zakresu biogospodarki cyrkularnej oraz istniejące sieci interesariuszy
- Zwiększone wsparcie w zakresie wdrażanych zmian legislacyjnych, rozwiązań naukowych oraz innowacji dla biogospodarki cyrkularnej
- Innowacyjne biozwiązki wspierające transformację w kierunku do gospodarki o obiegu zamkniętym

Cele szczegółowe

- Ocena obecnego stanu biogospodarki na poziomie europejskim
- Identyfikacja czynników wpływających na przyjmowanie i spowolnienie biozwiązków na obszarach wiejskich
- Utworzenie Europejskiej Sieci Biogospodarki dla Obszarów Wiejskich
- Ocena i promowanie przykładów historii sukcesu biozwiązków stosowanych na obszarach wiejskich
- Ułatwienie wymiany wiedzy i budowa potencjału dla rozwoju biogospodarki na europejskich obszarach wiejskich
- Opracowanie i stała optymalizacja ogólnodostępnych cyfrowych narzędzi dedykowanych dla interesariuszy (Zbiór Narzędzi BioRural)
- Opracowanie projektów skalowania cyrkularnych biozwiązków na obszarach wiejskich

Filary:

- Wiedza**
 - Analiza braków aktualnej wiedzy
 - Warsztaty służące wymianie wiedzy
 - Zestaw Narzędzi BioRural
- Sieć kontaktów**
 - 4 regionalne Platformy Biogospodarki Obszarów Wiejskich
 - Przykłady historii sukcesu wdrożonych biozwiązków
 - Synergie z poprzednimi i aktualnymi projektami dotyczącymi innowacyjnych zastosowań dla biogospodarki
- Modele Biznesowe**
 - Projekty i propozycje modeli biznesowych dla każdego obszaru tematycznego
 - Trwałość wypracowanych praktyk po zakończeniu projektu

Brochure sides A&B [Danish]

Forventede resultater

- 1 Europæisk netværk for bioøkonomi i landdistrikterne
- 4 Regionale Bioøkonomi platforme
- 20 Succeshistorier om bioøkonomi i landdistrikterne
- 42 Kapacitetsopbyggende workshops
- 4 Regionale workshops
- 1 Europæisk Bioøkonomisk udfordring
- 440 Interviews med brugere/eksparter
- 5 Workshops for vidensudveksling
- 5 Foretningsmodeller for bioøkonomi
- Politiske anbefalinger
- >400 Forskellige materialer om bioøkonomi
- Filmede workshops
- 8 Succeshistorier på video
- Integration med EU's videncentre for Bioøkonomi

bio ruraleu

in bio rural

f bio ruraleu

yt BioRural channel

→ Registrer dig til BioRural's platform for tilslutning til det Europæiske bioøkonomi netværk

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Frmskyndelse af integrationen af cirkulær biobaserede løsninger i europæiske landdistrikter

Sammenkobling af elementer for at

FRIGØRE POTENTIALET

i de Europæiske landdistrikter

i retning af cirkulær BIOØKONOMI

Et Horizon Europe-projekt
1. september 2022 - 31. August 2023

Finansieret af Den Europæiske Union

Introduktion

"Bioøkonomi betyder udnyttelse af vedvarende biologiske ressourcer, som afgrøder, træ, fisk, dyr og mikroorganismer til fødevarerproduktion, materialer og energi" (EC) og en blomstrende bioøkonomi som en nøgle til at skabe en Europæisk cirkulær økonomi

Udfordringer

- Vores økonomier er baseret på lineære produktionssystemer som forbruger ikke vedvarende ressourcer
- Landdistrikterne står over for akutte udfordringer om demografi, fattigdom og klima
- Viden om bioøkonomi og teknologioverførsel understøttes ikke tilstrækkeligt i landdistrikterne

... men muligheder eksisterer

- Cirkulære bioøkonomiske løsninger og netværk eksisterer
- Øget politik, forskning og innovationsstøtte til en cirkulær bioøkonomi
- Nye biobaserede innovationer støtter hele tiden overgangen til en cirkulær økonomi

Målsætning

"BioRural's mål er at skabe et Europæisk Bioøkonominettværk i landdistrikterne for at fremme mindre bioøkonomiske løsninger i landdistrikterne og øge bioøkonomiens andel"

Specifikke målsætninger

- Evaluere den nuværende status for Europæisk bioøkonomi
- Identificere faktorer, der påvirker indførelsen af innovation og spredningen af biobaserede løsninger
- Opbygge et europæisk bioøkonomisk netværk i landdistrikterne
- Bedømme og promovere biobaserede løsninger i landdistrikterne
- Fremme vidensdeling og kapacitetsopbygning for bioøkonomien i landdistrikterne
- Udvikle og løbende optimere et online (BioRural værktøjskasse) for interessenter
- Skabe planer for udvidelse af bioøkonomivirksomheder fra opstart til fuld skala

Procedure

BioRural er centreret på 3 søjler, som passer i den offentligt tilgængelige BioRural værktøjskasse

Søjler

Søjle 1: Viden

- Analyse af informationskæften
- Workshops med vidensdeling
- BioRural værktøjskasse

Søjle 2: Netværk

- 4 regionale bioøkonomiske platforme i landdistrikterne
- Cirkulære succeshistorier
- Synergier med tidligere og igangværende projekter om innovativ bioøkonomi
- Kapacitetsopbygning og regionale workshops,
- Bioøkonomi udfordring

Pillar 3: Business Models

- Planer for foretningsmodeller for hvert tema
- Bæredygtighed efter projektet

Brochure sides A&B [Dutch]

Verwachte resultaten

- 1 Europees netwerk voor bio-economie in de landbouw
- 4 Regionale platformen voor bio-economie
- 20 Succesverhalen over bio-economie in de landbouw
- 42 workshops gericht op het vergroten van de deskundigheid
- 4 regionale workshops
- 1 Europese bio-economie Uitdaging
- 440 Interviews met eindgebruikers/experts
- 5 Workshops kennisuitwisseling
- 5 Bedrijfsmodellen voor bio-economie
- Aanbevelingen voor de beleidsmakers
- >400 Informatiematerialen over bio-economie
- Gefinnde workshops
- 8 Video's succesverhalen
- Integratie met EU-kenniscentrum voor bio-economie

De verbindingen tot stand brengen om het **POTENTIEEL** van de Europese landbouw: naar een **CIRCULAIRE BIO-ECONOMIE TE ONTWIKKELLEN**

→ Registreer voor BioRural's Bio-economie platform om deel te nemen aan Europese BioEconomy netwerken!

biorural.eu

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Een Horizon Europa Project
1 september 2022 - 31 augustus 2025

Gefinancierd door de Europese Unie

Introductie

"Een biobased economie betekent het hergebruik van biologische hulpbronnen, zoals gewassen, bossen, vissen, dieren en micro-organismen om voedsel, materialen en energie te produceren" (EC) en een bloeiende biobased economie is de sleutel tot het creëren van een circulaire Europese economie.

Uitdagingen

- Onze economie is gericht op traditionele productiesystemen die gebruik maken van niet-herbruikbare natuurlijke grondstoffen.
- De landbouw wordt geconfronteerd met acute demografische, klimaatproblemen en soms een slecht verdienmodel.
- De overdracht van kennis en technologie op het gebied van biobased economie in de landbouw wordt onvoldoende ondersteund.

... Maar er zijn kansen

- Er bestaan oplossingen en netwerken binnen de kringlooeconomie
- Meer steun voor beleid, onderzoek en innovatie voor een circulaire bio-economie
- Nieuwe biobased innovaties ondersteunen consequent de overgang naar een circulaire economie

Doelstelling

"BioRural heeft als doel een Europees netwerk voor biobased economie in de landbouw te creëren om kleinschalige biobased oplossingen in de landbouw te stimuleren en het aandeel van de biobased economie te vergroten"

Specifieke doelstellingen

- De huidige stand van de Europese bio-economie evalueren
- Factoren in kaart brengen die de toepassing van innovatie en de verspreiding van biobased oplossingen beïnvloeden
- Een Europees netwerk voor biobased economie in de landbouw opzetten
- Biobased oplossingen in de landbouw beoordelen en promoten
- Kennisuitwisseling en het vergroten van deskundigheid voor de biobased landbouweconomie vergemakkelijken
- Een online open tool voor belanghebbenden (BioRural Toolkit) ontwikkelen en voortdurend optimaliseren
- Ontwikkel routekaarten voor bedrijven, die helpen bij de ontwikkeling van biobased landbouw, van idee tot grootschalige uitvoering

Aanpak

BioRural rust op drie pijlers die de basis vormen voor een openbaar toegankelijke BioRural Toolkit

Pijlers

Pijler 1: Kennis

- Analyse van kennisinitiatieven
- Workshops voor kennisuitwisseling
- BioRurale Toolkit

Pijler 2: Netwerk

- 4 regionale platformen voor biobased economie in de landbouw
- Circulaire succesverhalen
- Synergie met eerdere en lopende innovatieve biobased economie projecten
- Opbouw van deskundigheid en regionale workshops, Uitdagingen voor de bio-economie

Pijler 3: Bedrijfsmodellen

- Businessmodellen voor ieder thema
- Blijvende duurzaamheid na projecten

Brochure sides A&B [Spanish]

Resultados esperados

- 1 Red Europea de Bioeconomía Rural - ERBN
- 4 plataformas regionales de la ERBN
- 20 casos de éxito, documentados y compartidos
- 42 talleres de transferencia e intercambio
- 4 talleres internacionales de soluciones innovadoras
- 1 concurso europeo de soluciones innovaciones
- 440 entrevistas a usuarios y expertos
- 5 talleres de intercambio de información
- 5 dossiers con modelos de negocio y recomendaciones políticas
- >400 documentos y videos informativos
- 8 videos de casos de éxito

Integración con el centro de conocimiento para la Bioeconomía de la UE

→ ¡Regístrate en la plataforma de BIORURAL para unirse a la Red Europea de Bioeconomía Rural!

bioruraleu

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BioRural channel

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Un proyecto Horizonte Europa
1 Septiembre 2022 – 31 Agosto 2025

Financiado por la Unión Europea

Acelerando la integración de soluciones circulares biobasadas en zonas rurales en Europa

Conectando los agentes para

DESBLOQUEAR EL POTENCIAL

de zonas rurales Europeas

hacia la

BIOECONOMÍA CIRCULAR

Introducción

"La bioeconomía comprende las partes de la economía que utilizan recursos biológicos renovables de la tierra y el mar, como cultivos, bosques, peces, animales y microorganismos, para producir alimentos, materiales y energía" (CE), y una bioeconomía próspera es clave para crear una economía Europea plenamente circular

Desafíos

- Nuestra economía se basa en modelos lineales que utilizan recursos no renovables
- Las zonas rurales se enfrentan a la despoblación, reducción de la actividad económica y al cambio climático
- La transferencia de conocimiento y la adopción de tecnología e innovaciones en zonas rurales es un proceso complejo

... pero hay oportunidades

- Las soluciones tecnológicas y los modelos a menudo ya se han desarrollado
- Las políticas, la investigación y la innovación están fuertemente orientadas hacia una economía circular
- Las soluciones innovadoras de base biológica son una oportunidad en la transición a una economía circular

Objetivo

"El objetivo de BioRural es crear una Red Europea de Bioeconomía Rural que promueva soluciones biobasadas en pequeña escala para aumentar el papel de la bioeconomía en las zonas rurales"

Objetivos específicos

- Evaluar el estado actual de la bioeconomía en Europa
- Identificar los factores que influyen en la adopción y difusión de soluciones biobasadas innovadoras
- Promover las soluciones biobasadas innovadoras aplicables en zonas rurales
- Crear una Red Europea de Bioeconomía Rural
- Facilitar el intercambio de conocimientos y la formación en pro de la Bioeconomía rural
- Desarrollo y optimización de una plataforma en línea para los agentes interesados
- Creación de itinerarios estratégicos para puesta en marcha de innovaciones en bioeconomía (del concepto a la aplicación)

Estrategia

BioRural se enfoca en 3 pilares que convergen en una herramienta gratuita: el Kit de Herramientas de BioRural

Pillars

Pillar 1: Conocimiento

- Análisis de carencias y necesidades
- Organización de talleres de intercambio
- Kit de herramientas BIORURAL

Pillar 2: Redes de contactos

- 4 plataformas regionales
- Casos de éxito de bioeconomía circular
- Sinergias con proyectos finalizados y en curso centrados en innovaciones en bioeconomía
- Transferencia, talleres internacionales y concurso europeo

Pillar 3: Modelos de negocio

- Dossiers de modelos de negocio para cada área temática de la bioeconomía
- Sostenibilidad tras el proyecto

Brochure sides A&B [Latvian]

Sagaidāmie rezultāti

- 1 Eiropas lauku bioekonomikas tīds
- 4 reģionālās bioekonomikas platformas
- 20 lauku bioekonomikas veiksmes stāsti
- 42 kapacitātes stiprināšanas semināri
- 4 reģionālie semināri
- 1 Eiropas bioekonomikas izziņojums

- 440 intervijas ar galalietotājiem/ekspertiem
- 5 zināšanu apmaiņas semināri
- 5 bioekonomikas uzņēmējdarbības modeļi
- > 400 bioekonomikas materiālu
- 8 veiksmes stāstu video

Integrācija ar ES bioekonomikas zināšanu centru.

Aprites principos balstītu biorisinājumu veicināšana lauku apvidos Eiropā

Sadarbības veicināšana, lai attīstītu aprites **PRINCIPOS BALSTĪTAS** bioekonomikas potenciālu

EIROPAS LAUKU APVIDOS

*Apvienotais Eiropa projekts
2022. gada 1. septembris -
2025. gada 31. augusts

→ Reģistrējieties BioRural Bioeconomy platformā un pievienojieties Eiropas BioEconomy tīkliem!

[biorural.eu](https://www.biorural.eu)

[@bio_rural](#)
[#BioRural](#)
[BioRural channel](#)

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Finansē Eiropas Savienība

Ievads

"Bioekonomika nozīmē izmantot atjaunojamus bioloģiskos resursus, piemēram, kultūraugus, mežus, zivis, dzīvniekus un mikroorganismus, lai ražotu pārtiku, materiālus un enerģiju" (EK), un bioekonomikas izsauzme ir būtiska, lai izveidotu Eiropas aprites ekonomiku

Mērķi

"BioRural mērķis ir izveidot Eiropas lauku bioekonomikas tīklu, lai veicinātu mazo mēroga bioloģiskas izcelsmes risinājumus lauku apvidos un palielinātu bioekonomikas īpatsvaru"

Pieeja

BioRural ir virzīts trīs pāros, kas iekļauj publiski pieejamā BioRural tiešsaistes rīku

Izaicinājumi

- Ekonomika balstās uz lineārām ražošanas sistēmām, kurās izmanto neatjaunojamus resursus
- Lauku apvidi saskaras ar akūtām demogrāfiskām, nabadzības un klimata problēmām
- Lauku bioekonomika, zināšanu un tehnoloģiju nodošana netiek pienācīgi atbalstīta

... Taču iespējas pastāv

- Pastāv aprites bioekonomikas risinājumi un tīkli
- Lielākā politikas, pētniecības un inovācijas atbalsts aprites bioekonomikai
- Jaunas bioloģiskas izcelsmes inovācijas patērētājiem atbalsta pāreju uz aprites ekonomiku

Konkrētie mērķi

- Novērtēt Eiropas bioekonomikas pašreizējo stāvokli
- Ideificēt faktorus, kas ietekmē inovāciju pielāgošanu un bioloģiskas izcelsmes risinājumu izplatīšanu
- Izveidot Eiropas lauku bioekonomikas tīklu
- Novērtēt un veicināt bioloģiskas izcelsmes risinājumus lauku apvidos
- Veicināt zināšanu apmaiņu un kapacitātes stiprināšanu lauku bioekonomikas jomā
- Izstrādāt un pastāvīgi optimizēt ieinteresēto personu publisko tiešsaistes rīku (BioRural Toolkit)
- Izveidot lauku atbilstības plānu bioekonomikas uzņēmējdarbībai no koncepcijas izstrādes līdz mērogam

Pilāri

- 1.pilārs: zināšanas**
 - Informācijas trūkuma analīze
 - Zināšanu apmaiņas semināri
 - tiešsaistes rīks BioRural Toolkit
- 2.pilārs: ieinteresēto personu tīkls**
 - 4 reģionālās lauku bioekonomikas platformas
 - Aprites veiksmes stāsti
 - Sinerģija ar iepriekšējiem un pašreizējiem inovatīviem bioekonomikas projektiem
 - Kapacitātes stiprināšanas un reģionālie semināri
- 3.pilārs: biznesa modeļi**
 - Uzņēmējdarbības modeļu plāni katrai bioekonomikas tīmai
 - Pācprojekta īstenošana

Brochure sides A&B [Lithuanian]

Laukiami rezultatai

- 1 Europos kaimo bioekonomikos tinklas
- 4 regioninės bioekonomikos platformos
- 20 kaimo bioekonomikos sėkmės istorijų
- 42 gebėjimų ugdymo seminariai
- 4 regioniniai seminariai
- 1 Europos bioekonomikos iššūkis
- 440 interviu su galutiniais vartotojais ir ekspertais
- 5 keitimosi žiniomis seminariai
- 5 bioekonomikos verslo modeliai
- Politikos rekomendacijos
- >400 informacinių šaltinių apie bioekonomiką
- Filmuoti seminariai
- 8 filmuotos sėkmės istorijos
- Integracija su ES bioekonomikos žinių centru

Žiedinių biosprendimų integravimo į Europos kaimo vietoves spartinimas

Žiedinės
BIOEKONOMIKOS POTENCIALO IŠLAISVINIMAS

Europos kaimo vietovėse užpildžius žinių ir idėjų spragas

→ **Prisiregistruokite** prie BioRural Bioekonomikos platformos ir prisijunkite prie Europos bioekonomikos tinklų!

- in bio_rural
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Finansuoja Europos Sąjunga

Ižanga

"Bioekonomika – rėmimo atsinaujinančių išteklių, tokių kaip pašalai, mėsos, žuvys, gyvūnai ir mikroorganizmai, naudojimo maistui, medžiagai ir energijai gaminti" (EK), o kvestinti bioekonomika yra raktas į Europos žiedinės ekonomikos sukūrimą.

Tikslas

"BioRural tikslas – sukurti Europos kaimo bioekonomikos tinklą, siekiant skatinti nedidelio masto biosprendimus kaimo vietovėse ir didinti bioekonomikos dalį"

Metodas

BioRural yra sutelktas į tris ramsčius, kurie įtraukiami į viešai prieinamą BioRural priemonių rinkinį

Iššūkiai

- Mūsų ekonomikos yra pagrįstas linijinėmis gamybos sistemomis, naudojančiomis neatsinaujančius išteklius
- Kaimo vietovės susiduria su dideliais demografiniais, skurdo ir klimato iššūkiais
- Kaimo bioekonomikos žinių ir technologijų perdavimas nėra pakankamai remiamas

... bet yra galimybių

- Egzistuoja žiedinės bioekonomikos sprendimai ir tinklai
- Padidėjusi politikos, tyrimų ir inovacijų parama žiedinei bioekonomikai
- Naujos biologinės naujosios nuosėdai nema perėjimą prie žiedinės ekonomikos

Konkretūs tikslai

- Ivertinti esamą Europos bioekonomikos būklę
- Identifikuoti veiksmus, darančius poveikį naujovių taikymui ir biosprendimų sklaidai
- Sukurti Europos kaimo bioekonomikos tinklą
- Ivertinti ir skatinti biosprendimus kaimo vietovėse
- Palenginti keitimąsi žiniomis ir gebėjimų ugdymą kaimo bioekonomikoje
- Sukurti ir nuolat optimizuoti internetinį laisvos prieigos suinteresuotųjų šalių tinklą (BioRural Toolkit)
- Sukurti kaimo vyatymosi planus nuo idėjos iki platus taikymo su bioekonomika susijusiems verslams

Ramsčiai

1 ramstis: Žinios

- Informacijos stoko analizė
- Keitimosi žiniomis seminariai
- BioRural priemonių rinkinys

2 ramstis: Tinklas

- 4 regioninės kaimo bioekonomikos platformos
- Žiedikumo sėkmės istorijos
- Sinergija su buvusiais ir vykdomais inovatyviais bioekonomikos projektais
- Gebėjimų ugdymo ir regioniniai seminariai, bioekonomikos iššūkis

3 ramstis: Verslo modeliai

- Verslo modelių vūjos pagal kiekvieną temą
- Tvarumas po projekto

Brochure sides A&B [Romanian]

Rezultate aşteptate

- 1 Reţea Europeană de Bioeconomie Rurală
- 4 Platforme Regionale de Bioeconomie
- 20 Cazuri de succes în Bioeconomie Rurală
- 42 Ateliere de lucru de dezvoltare a capacităţilor
- 4 Ateliere de lucru regionale
- 1 Competiţie europeană în bioeconomie
- 440 interviuri cu utilizatori finali/ experţi
- 5 ateliere de lucru de schimburi de cunoştinţe
- 5 modele de afaceri în bioeconomie
- Recomandări de politici
- > 400 materiale cu tema bioeconomiei
- Ateliere de lucru filmate
- 8 materiale video despre cazuri de succes
- Integrarea rezultatelor în Centrul de cunoştinţe în Bioeconomie al UE

→ **Inscrieţi-vă pe platforma Bioeconomy a proiectului BioRural pentru a vă alătura Reţelei Europene de Bioeconomie**

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[yt](#) BioRural channel

Contact: **Boglárka Vajda**, Coordonator din România, vajda@greendust.ro

Stimularea integrării soluţiilor bio-bazate circulare în zonele rurale europene

Crearea condiţiilor pentru a **VALORIFICA POTENŢIALUL** zonelor rurale europene prin dezvoltarea **BIOECONOMIEI CIRCULARE**

Proiect Horizon Europe
1 septembrie 2022 - 31 august 2025

Finanţat de Uniunea Europeană

Introducere

"Termenul de bioeconomie se referă la utilizarea resurselor biologice regenerabile de pe uscat și din mare, cum ar fi culturile, produsele forestiere, pești, animalele și microorganismele, pentru a produce alimente, materiale și energie." (CE) și o bioeconomie prosperă este cheia creării unei economii europene circulare.

Obiective

"Obiectivul BioRural este de a crea o reţea europeană care să promoveze soluţii pentru valorificarea bioeconomiei la scară mică, în vederea creşterii rolului bioeconomiei în zonele rurale."

Abordarea

BioRural se axează pe trei piloni care se integrează în Instrumentul BioRural, accesibil publicului

Provocări

- Economia noastră se bazează pe modele liniare folosind resurse neregenerabile.
- Zonele rurale se confruntă cu sărăcia, depopularea și schimbările climatice
- Răspândire de cunoştinţe referitoare la bioeconomia rurală și transferul de tehnologii nu sunt susţinute adecvat

... dar există și oportunităţi

- Există soluţii și reţele de Bioeconomie Circulară
- Susţinere din partea de politici, cercetare și inovare în bioeconomia circulară
- Noi inovări bio-bazate susţin în mod consistent tranziţia spre o economie circulară

Obiective specifice

- Evaluarea stadiului actual al bioeconomiei în Europa
- Identificarea factorilor care influenţează adoptarea și răspândirea bioeconomiei în zonele rurale
- Crearea unei Reţele europene de Bioeconomie rurală
- Evaluarea și promovarea soluţiilor bio-bazate în zonele rurale
- Facilitarea schimbului de cunoştinţe și a formării pentru a crea profesionalism în zonele rurale
- Dezvoltarea și optimizarea unei platforme online pentru părţile interesate
- Crearea de proiecte de afaceri pentru bioeconomie, de la concepţie până la aplicarea reală

Piloni

Pilonul 1: Cunoştinţe

- Analiza lacunelor de cunoştinţe
- Ateliere de lucru de schimb de cunoştinţe
- BioRural Toolkit

Pilonul 2: Reţea

- 4 platforme regionale de Bioeconomie Rurală
- Exemple de succes din economia circulară
- Sinergie cu proiecte inovative din bioeconomia circulară
- Ateliere de lucru regionale de dezvoltare a capacităţilor, competiţie europeană de bioeconomie

Pilonul 3: Modele de afaceri

- Proiectare modele de afaceri pentru fiecare temă
- Sustenabilitatea post-proiect

Brochure sides A&B [German]

Erwartete Ergebnisse

- 1 Europäisches Netzwerk an ländlichen Akteuren der Bioökonomie
- 4 Regionale Bioökonomie Plattformen
- 20 Erfolgsgeschichten der ländlichen Bioökonomie
- 42 Workshops zum Kapazitätsaufbau
- 4 Regionale Workshops
- 1 Herausforderung der europäischen Bioökonomie
- 440 Interviews mit Endnutzern/Experten
- 5 Workshops zum Wissensaustausch
- 5 Bioökonomie Geschäftsmodelle
- > 400 Gefilmte Workshops mit Bioökonomie Material
- 8 Videos zu Erfolgsgeschichten
- Integration mit dem EU- Wissenszentrum für Bioökonomie

Beschleunigung der Integration bio-basierter Kreislaufösungen in den ländlichen Gebieten Europas

Verknüpfung der Punkte zur **ERSCHLIESSUNG DES POTENZIALS** europäischer, ländlicher Gebiete für eine kreislaforientierte **BIOÖKONOMIE**

→ **Registrieren Sie sich auf der BioRural Bioökonomie Plattform, um am europäischen Bioökonomie-Netzwerk teilzunehmen**

biorural.eu

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Horizon Europe Projekt
 1. September 2022 – 31. August 2025

Finanziert von der Europäischen Union

Einleitung

Bioökonomie bedeutet die Nutzung erneuerbarer biologischer Ressourcen wie Pflanzen, Wälder, Fische, Tiere und Mikroorganismen zur Erzeugung von Lebensmitteln, Materialien und Energie. Eine florierende Bioökonomie ist der Schlüssel zur Schaffung einer europäischen Kreislaufwirtschaft.

Herausforderungen

- Unsere Volkswirtschaften basieren auf linearen Produktionssystemen, die nicht erneuerbare Ressourcen nutzen
- ländliche Gebiete stehen vor akuten Herausforderungen in Bezug auf Demografie, Armut und Klima
- Der Wissens- und Technologietransfer im Bereich der ländlichen Bioökonomie wird nicht ausreichend gefördert

... aber es gibt Möglichkeiten

- es gibt Lösungen und Netzwerke für die Kreislaufwirtschaft in der Bioökonomie
- verstärkte Unterstützung von Politik, Forschung und Innovation für eine kreislaforientierte Bioökonomie
- neue bio-basierte Innovationen unterstützen konsequent den Übergang zu einer Kreislaufwirtschaft

Zielsetzung

Das Ziel von BioRural ist die Schaffung eines europäischen Netzwerks für die Bioökonomie im ländlichen Raum, um kleine biobasierte Lösungen in ländlichen Gebieten zu fördern und den Anteil der Bioökonomie zu erhöhen.

Spezifische Ziele

- Bewertung des aktuellen Stands der europäischen Bioökonomie
- Ermittlung der Faktoren, die die Übernahme von Innovationen und die Verbreitung von biobasierten Lösungen beeinflussen
- Schaffung eines europäischen Netzwerks für die Bioökonomie im ländlichen Raum
- Bewertung und Förderung bio-basierter Lösungen in ländlichen Gebieten
- Erleichterung des Wissensaustauschs und des Aufbaus von Kapazitäten für die ländliche Bioökonomie
- Entwicklung und kontinuierliche Optimierung eines offenen Online-Tools für Akteure (BioRural Toolkit)
- Erstellung von Entwürfen für die ländliche Entwicklung von Bioökonomie-Unternehmen von der Konzeption bis zur Skalierung

Herangehensweise

Biorural stützt sich auf drei Säulen, die in ein öffentlich zugängliches BioRural-Toolkit einfließen

Säulen

Säule 1: Wissen

- Analyse des Informationsflusses
- Workshops zum Wissensaustausch
- BioRural Toolkit

Säule 2: Netzwerk

- 4 Regionale Bioökonomie Plattformen
- Zirkuläre Erfolgsgeschichten
- Synergien mit vorherigen und laufenden innovativen bio-ökonomischen Projekten
- Kapazitätsaufbauende und regionale Workshops, Herausforderung Bioökonomie

Säule 3: Geschäftsmodelle

- Entwürfe zu Geschäftsmodellen für jedes Thema
- Nachhaltigkeit nach dem Projekt

BioRural banner: English version and translations in partners' languages

Banner [English]

Banner [French]

BIOrural
Accélérer les solutions circulaires et biosourcées au sein des zones rurales européennes

Connaissance
Réseautage
BIOrural Boîte à outils
Business Models

Connecter les acteurs pour
LIBÉRER LE POTENTIEL
des zones rurales européennes vers la
BIOÉCONOMIE CIRCULAIRE

Delphy, INSEAL, NaturePlace, izes, iung, CBE, AIEL, e-reframe, IICO, algem, etc.

Financé par l'Union européenne <https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Italian]

BIOrural

Stimolare l'integrazione delle soluzioni bio-based nell'economia circolare delle aree rurali europee

Informazioni

Network

BIOrural Toolkit

Business Models

Creare le condizioni per
RIMUOVERE GLI OSTACOLI
 Allo sviluppo sostenibile della
BIOECONOMIA
 Nelle aree rurali europee

 Finanziato dall'Unione europea

<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Portuguese]

BIOrural

Apoiando a integração de soluções circulares de base biotecnológica nas áreas rurais da Europa

Conhecimento

BIOrural Ferramentas de Apoio

Rede de Partilha

Modelos de Negócio

Ligando os pontos para **DESBLOQUEAR O POTENCIAL** das zonas rurais da Europa rumo à **BIOECONOMIA CIRCULAR**

 Financiado pela União Europeia
 <https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Macedonian]

Biorural
Забрзана интеграција на циркуларни био-базирани решенија во руралните региони во Европа

Знања
Виртување
Бизнис модели

Поврзување на клучните точки за
ОТКЛУЧУВАЊЕ НА ПОТЕНЦИЈАЛОТ
На руралните региони во Европа на патот кон циркуларна
БИОЕКОНОМИЈА

 Funded by the European Union
<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Greek]

BIOrural

Επιταχύνοντας την μετάβαση προς μια κυκλική βιοοικονομία στις αγροτικές περιοχές της Ευρώπης

Τίτλος

Δίκτυο

Επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα

BIOrural Εργαλειοθήκη

Συνδέοντας τα σημεία για την **ΑΝΑΔΕΙΞΗ ΤΩΝ ΔΥΝΑΤΟΤΗΤΩΝ** των Ευρωπαϊκών αγροτικών περιοχών προς μια κυκλική **ΒΙΟΟΙΚΟΝΟΜΙΑ**

Delphy, KIBORON, iizes, iung, CBE, AIEL, reframe, IGO, Aigen

Με τη χρηματοδότηση της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης

<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Polish]

BIOrural
Przyspieszenie integracji bio-rozwiązań gospodarki cyrkularnej na europejskich obszarach wiejskich

Wiedza
Siec kontaktów
Model Biznesowy
BIOrural Zestaw Narzędzi

którego celem jest
UWOLNIENIE POTENCJAŁU
europejskich obszarów wiejskich
oraz transformacja i dążenie do
BIOGOSPODARKI O OBIEGU ZAMKNIĘTYM

 Europejski program Unia Europejska
<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Danish]

BIOrural
 Fremskyndelse af integrationen af cirkulær biobaserede løsninger i europæiske landdistrikter

Viden
 Netværk
 Business modeller
 BIOrural værktøjskasse

Sammenkobling af elementer for at
FRIGØRE POTENTIALET
 i de Europæiske landdistrikter
 i retning af cirkulær
BIOØKONOMI

Delphy, BIOrural, Nature's Place, izes, iung, CBE, AIEL, refraim, Jovet, IFO, Aalborg, etc.

Finansieret af Den Europæiske Union
<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Dutch]

BIOrural
 Versnellen van de circulaire en biobased oplossingen in Europese landbouwgebieden

Kennis
 Netwerk
 BIOrural Toolkit
 Bedrijfsmodellen

De verbindingen tot stand brengen om het **POTENTIEEL** van de Europese landbouw naar een **CIRCULAIRE BIO-ECONOMIE TE ONTWIKKELEN**

 Gefinancierd door de Europese Unie
 <https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Spanish]

BIOrural
 Acelerando la integración de soluciones
 circulares biobasadas en zonas rurales en Europa.

Conocimiento
 Red de contactos
 BIOrural
 Kit de herramientas
 Modelos de negocio

Conectando a los agentes para
**DESBLOQUEAR
 EL POTENCIAL**
 de zonas rurales Europeas
 hacia la
BIOECONOMÍA CIRCULAR.

 Financiado por
 la Unión Europea

<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Latvian]

BIOrural

Aprites principos balstītu biorisinājumu veicināšana lauku apvidos Eiropā

zināšanas

ieinteresēto personu tīkls

BIOrural tiešsaistes rīks

biznesa modeļi

Sadarbības veicināšana, lai attīstītu aprites **PRINCIPOS BALSTĪTAS** bioekonomikas potenciālu **EIROPAS LAUKU APVIDOS**

Delphy, MIBRAC, NaturePlast, izes, iung, CBE, AIEL, reframe, iCo, algen

Finansēta Eiropas Savienība

<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Lithuanian]

BIOrural
 Žiedinių biosprendimų integravimo į Europos kaimo vietoves spartinimas

Žinios
 Tinklas
 Premorū rinkinys
 BIOrural Verslo modeliai

Žiedinės
**BIOEKONOMIKOS
 POTENCIALO
 IŠLAISVINIMAS**
 Europos kaimo vietovėse
 užpildžius žinių ir idėjų spragas

Delphy, AgriKAC, iizes, iung, CBE, AEL, IIC, Agri, Agri

Finansuojama Europos Sąjunga
<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Romanian]

BIOrural
Stimularea integrării soluțiilor bio-bazate
circulare în zonele rurale europene

Diagram illustrating the BIOrural Instrument cycle:

- Cunoștințe** (Knowledge) - represented by a lightbulb and a person working.
- Rețea** (Network) - represented by people at a computer.
- Modele de afaceri** (Business Models) - represented by a building and a line graph.
- BIOrural Instrument** - represented by a hand holding a calculator and a bar chart.

Crearea condițiilor pentru a
**VALORIFICA
POTENȚIALUL**
zonelor rurale europene
prin dezvoltarea
**BIOECONOMIEI
CIRCULARE**

Logos of partner organizations: Delphy, INERAC, D3, IZES, IUNG, etc.

Finanțat de
Uniunea Europeană
https://biorural.eu

Banner [German]

BIOrural
Beschleunigung der Integration bio-basierter
Kreislaufösungen in den
ländlichen Gebieten Europas

Wissen
Netzwerk
BIOrural
Toolkit
Geschäftsmodelle

Verknüpfung der Punkte zur
**ERSCHLIEßUNG DES
POTENZIALS**
europäischer ländlicher
Gebiete für eine
kreislauforientierte
BIOÖKONOMIE

Delphy MEDICAL N izes iung
ICORE avoBiom CBE AIEL reframe
ICO

Finanziert von der Europäischen Union
<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Slovenian]

BIOrural
Spodbujanje krožnih bio-osnovanih rešitev na evropskem podeželju.

Omrežje
Znanje
Poslovni modeli
BIOrural Zbirka orodij

Z vzajemnim učenjem in povezovanjem
SPROŠČAMO POTENCIAL KROŽNEGA BIOGOSPODARSTVA
na evropskem podeželju.

Delphy, MRSKAL, Nature Plast, izes, IUNG, CBE, AIEL, refraim, IGO, Valgen

Financira Evropska unija
<https://biorural.eu>

Press release template

The image shows a two-page press release template. The left page is a blank space for the text of the press release, with a BioRural logo and the text 'Press Release | Date' in the top right corner. The right page contains contact information for the Project Communication and Project Coordinator, a Social Media section with links to Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube, and a footer with the website 'www.biorural.eu'.

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 despoina@foodscalehub.com

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 a.balafoutis@certh.gr

Social Media

Facebook	BioRural
Twitter	bio_rural
LinkedIn	BioRural
YouTube	BioRural

www.biorural.eu

Annex D: Deliverable template

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

Enter your deliverable title here

Responsible Author: [Author Name and Surname (Partner's short name)]

biorural.eu

DX.X: Deliverable Title

Grant Agreement No.	101060166
Project Acronym	BioRural
Project Title	Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas
Type of action	CSA - Coordination and Support Actions
Horizon Europe Call Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2021-CIRC-BIO-01-08: Mainstreaming inclusive small-scale bio-based solutions in European rural areas
Start – ending date	1 September 2022 – 31 August 2025
Project Website	https://biorural.eu/
Work Package	WP.V: Title of the WP
WP Lead Beneficiary	Partner's full name (Short name)
Relevant Task(s)	Task Title of the Task
Deliverable type Dissemination level	R – Report; DEC – Websites, press & media actions, videos, etc; OTHER: Software, etc. PU: Public; SEN: Sensitive; CI: Classified
Due Date of Deliverable	DD Month 20YY
Actual Submission Date	DD Month 20YY
Responsible Author	[Author Name and Surname (Partner)]
Contributors	[Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)]
Reviewer(s)	[Reviewer's Name and Surname (Partner)]

Document History

Date	Version	Changes	Contributor(s)
DD/MM/YYYY	VO.1	[Description of changes]	Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)
DD/MM/YYYY	VO.X	[Description of changes]	Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)

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DX.X: Deliverable Title

Participant No.	Participant name	Short name	Country
1	ETHIKO KENTRO EREYNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIAS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
2	DELPHY BV	DELPHY	NL
3	ASSOCIATION DU POLE DE COMPETIVITE VALORIAL	VALORIAL	FR
4	NATUREPLAST SAS	NATUREPLAST SAS	FR
5	DES GMBH	DES	DE
6	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	AU	DK
7	INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENIA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA, PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY	IUNG-PIB	PL
8	VYTAUTO BRUZOVO UNIVERSITETAS	Vytauto	LT
9	LATVIAS LAUKSARNAMECIBAS UNIVERSITATE	LLU	LV
10	ASOCIACION ESPAÑOLA DE LA VALORIZACION ENERGETICA DE LA BIOMASA	AVEBIOM	ES
11	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	UC	PT
12	CENTRO DA BIOMASSA FARA & ENERGIA	CBE	PT
13	AIEL ASSOCIAZIONE ITALIANA ENERGIE AGROFORESTALI	AIEL	IT
14	TODSCALE HUB GREECE ASSOCIATION FOR ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND INNOVATION ASTRO NI KERDOSKOPHI ETAREIA	FSH	EL
15	INCOMMON NON-PROFIT CIVIL LAW COMPANY	ICD	EL
16	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	UL	SI
17	ALGEN, CENTER ZA AIGNE TECHNOLOGIJE, DOO	ALGEN	SI
18	ASOCIATIA GREEN ENERGY	GEA	RO
19	ZDRUZENJE PLATFORMA ZA ZELEEN RAZVOJ SKOPJE	GGP	MK

DX.X: Deliverable Title

Executive Summary

Goal of the executive summary section is to provide a short summary for the deliverable and inform the reader on:

- The subject of the deliverable
- Summary of the work carried out
- The main conclusion(s)
- The purpose of the deliverable

DX.X: Deliverable Title

Table of Contents

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3	References	9
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List of Figures

Figure 1: Example caption for figures 6

List of Tables

Table 2: Example caption for tables 8

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation #1	Acronym #1

DX.X: Deliverable Title

1 Heading 1

1.1 Heading 2

1.1.1 Heading 3

1.1.1.1 Heading 4

1.1.1.1.1 Heading 5

1.1.1.1.1.1 Heading 6

Table 1: Example caption for tables

Title #1	Title #2

Figure 1: Example caption for figures

Annex E: Event Planning Template

BioRural EVENT PLANNING

Please complete the following form with events that you are already planning on attending over the next 6 months, or any that you are aware of, and feel would be well suited for BioRural participation.

BioRural Event Planning						
#	Name and Type of event	Event link	Date(s) / Location(s)	Scale	Target groups	Potential BioRural involvement

Annex F: Synergy Mapping Template

BioRural SYNERGY MAPPING

Please complete the following form with projects, initiatives and/or networks that you are involved with or are aware of and that could provide an opportunity for joint activities and collaboration.

BioRural Synergy & Liaison mapping						
#	Type of Initiative	Full name	Website	Initiative Leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities

Annex G: Publication Planning Template

BioRural PUBLICATION PLANNING

Please complete the following form with peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, any other publication you plan to make.

BioRural Publication Planning			
#	Type of publication	Publication website	Estimated submission date

Annex H: BioRural brand book

colors

CMYK

	0 50 100 0
	0 40 60 0
	0 20 100 0
	0 60 60 40
	0 100 100 30
	80 25 100 10
	90 0 100 0
	60 0 95 0
	60 0 5 0
	30 0 10 0

#Hex

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	#E1A86E
	#EFC A1E
	#955D4A
	#9A282C
	#66873F
	#54A148
	#92B849
	#8AC5E8
	#C7E...

typeface

iCiel Gotham Thin
(outlined with round corners and round caps)

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee
 Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj
 Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo
 Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt
 Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy
 Zz

Example

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions
integration in European rural areas

Annex I: Identification of new KERs & IPR process

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)		Scope of exploitation					Target groups [to whom]	Means of exploitation (how)	Linked IPRs to the KERs		
KER no	Please add any other exploitable results if relevant						For additional KERs please see note for the list of target groups	For additional KERs please describe the means of exploitation.	Please indicate what might be the possible IPRs, where relevant (one KER might be subject to more than one type of IPR)		
									IPR	IPR	if other please specify

END OF DOCUMENT